

Deliverable Report

Definition of selected business cases and scenarios

(D6.2b)

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This project has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 735485. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and Hydrogen Europe and N.ERGHY

This work is supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 17.00009.

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4443226>

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Project 735485 - QualyGridS

Standardized qualifying tests of electrolysers for grid services

Version:	1.07	Date: 19.8.2019	Released
Project Title:	Standardized qualifying tests of electrolyzers for grid services		
Acronym:	QualyGridS	Contract N°:	735485
Topic:	FCH-02-1-2016	Project Coordinator:	DLR, Germany
Document Classification:	Public		
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Distribution:	All QualyGridS Partners and advisory board members		

Revisions

Version	Changes
0.02	Ready for review
1.01	Released
1.02	Release date corrected
1.03	Added Vanesa Gil, Teresa Villuendas, Valérie Seguin to the list 'Approved (Partner)'
1.04 (D6.2b)	New data sources taken into account, and thus updated price information for France (aFRR), Denmark (aFRR+), Denmark (aFRR-). Added UK RR+ and RR-.

1.05 (D6.2b)	Added chapters <i>Competing technologies and future scenarios</i> as well as <i>Effect of scenarios on future market prices</i> to section 2.
1.06 (D6.2b)	Updated Appendix 10.1 Re-arranging section 2.
1.07	<p>Considering review feedback:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chapter 6.4: adding a footnote to explain why the WE receives energy for (almost) free. -Chapter 2.4.3: adding a statement to clarify the meaning of flexibility -Chapter 2.4.3: adding a statement to distinguish that 2.4.3 discusses long-term flexibility and 2.4.4 discusses short-term flexibility. -Chapter 2.4.3.1: adding a remark mentioning grid-flexible VRES as a future flexibility option. -Chapter 2.4.3.1: changing 'Conventional power plant...' title to 'Power plant ...' - Chapter 2.5.3: extending text to include the aspect of the effects of price volatility -Chapter 2.5.3: deleted text 'Therefore, in order to assess...changing market rules.'

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Abbreviations and definitions

Term	Definition
aFRR	Automatic FRR
Asymmetrical service	Asymmetrical means that the positive service capacity is unequal to the negative service capacity [1].
Availability of an RPU	The RPU is kept available for being called, but it's not yet providing control energy (own definition).
BE	Balancing Energy
BMC	Business model canvas
BoP	Balance of Plant
BRP	Balancing Responsible Party
BSP	Balance Service Provider
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CM	Congestion Management
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DFR	Distributed Flexibility Resource
DPS	Distributed Power Source
DSO	Distribution System Operator.
DSR	Demand Side Response
Dynamic service	The electric power of the service providing unit or group follows a continuous signal (own definition).
EEG	Erneuerbare Energien-Gesetz (renewable energy regulation) in Germany
ENTSO-E	European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity
EVA	Economic Value Added
FC	Fuel Cell
FCEV	Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle
FCR	Frequency Containment Reserves means the Operational Reserves activated to contain System Frequency after the occurrence of an imbalance (from [NC OS]) Frequency Deviation means the difference between the actual System Frequency and the Nominal Frequency of the Synchronous Area which can be negative or positive [2].
FCR-D	Frequency Containment Reserve - Disturbance
FCR-N	Frequency Containment Reserve - Normal
FLH	Full-load hours
FRR	Frequency Restoration Reserves means the Active Power Reserves activated to restore System Frequency to the Nominal Frequency and for Synchronous Area consisting of more than one LFC Area power balance to the scheduled value [2].
GB	Great Britain

Term	Definition
GLEB	ENTSO-E Guideline on Electricity Balancing [3]
HRS	Hydrogen Refuelling Station
LCCA	Life-Cycle Cost Analysis
LCOH	Levelised Cost of Hydrogen
LFM	Local Flexibility Market
LHV	Lower Heating Value
MCE	Multi-Criteria Evaluation
mFRR	Manual FRR
NG	Natural Gas
NO 4	Norwegian bidding zone of the Nordic power market (Tromsø)
Non-dynamic or static service	The electric power of the service providing unit or group switches between discrete values. The number of discrete values is two for asymmetric services and three for symmetric services (own definition)
NPV	Net Present Value
P2P	Peer-to-peer
PCT	Price Comparison Tool (Denmark)
PSO	Public Service Obligation (Denmark)
PtG	Power to Gas
PtH	Power to Hydrogen
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RKOM	mFRR Availability in Norway
Reserve Providing Group	Reserve Providing Group means an aggregation of Power Generating Modules, Demand Unit and/or Reserve Providing Units connected to more than one Connection Point fulfilling the requirements for FCR, FRR or RR [2].
RPU	Reserve Providing Unit means a single or an aggregation of Power Generating Modules and/or Demand Units connected to a common Connection Point fulfilling the requirements of FCR, FRR or RR [2]
Rotating mass / inertia	Inertia is the fact that a rotating rigid body such as an Alternator maintains its state of uniform rotational motion. Its angular momentum is unchanged, unless an external torque is applied [4]
RR	Replacement Reserves means the reserves used to restore/support the required level of FRR to be prepared for additional system imbalances. This category includes operating reserves with activation time from Time to Restore Frequency up to hours [2]
SMR	Steam Methane Reforming
STOR	Short Term Operating Reserve
Symmetrical service	Symmetrical means that the positive service capacity is equal to the negative service capacity
TSO	Transmission System Operator
Utilisation of an RPU	The RPU is called and provides control energy (own definition)

Term	Definition
VRES	Variable Renewable Energy Source
WACC	Weighted Average Cost of Capital
WE	Water Electrolyser
WP	Work package

Summary

The aggregation of smaller scale, distributed renewable energy systems for the provision of grid services already exists in several European countries. There are reports on countries adapting to the market rules in order to comply with the harmonization efforts of the EU [5], thereby opening opportunities for water electrolyzers to earn additional income from the provision of grid services. The water electrolyser, as a key technology of sustainable hydrogen production, can offer high operational flexibility for grid services such as frequency control and congestion management. Servicing those markets as a by-product, the WE can stack value that is relevant for bridging the gap towards market parity. This report identifies the best opportunities for the European grid service markets to be served by water electrolyzers. Data is available for 25 European countries including Norway and Switzerland. 85 TSO grid services within 12 countries are identified as commercially and technically feasible candidates. With eight such cases a more detailed economic analysis is conducted. It was found that offering the water electrolyzers' flexibility to the grid service markets can reduce the levelized cost of hydrogen by approximately 10%.

This document reports on the results of work packages 6.1 and 6.2 of the FCH QualyGridS project. It provides a coarse analysis of the attractiveness of existing grid service markets in the European Union plus Norway and Switzerland, which have the potential to contribute to a reduction in hydrogen production cost for water electrolyzers. Moreover, it gives the result of a thorough analysis of eight promising business cases: seven TSO grid services and one DSO grid service.

Transmission system operator (TSO) grid services are generally valorised by two means: remuneration for the availability ('power reserve') of the Reserve Providing Unit, and remuneration for the utilisation ('energy'). Since several countries do not publish detailed utilisation data, the two sources of income cannot be easily compared in many cases. To identify the most interesting cases, scenarios considering the impact of the data quality are defined, leading to insight with regard to sensitivities of key evaluation parameters. The analysis reveals that Germany has the most attractive market conditions for most cases, even though other countries may pay higher remuneration for grid services. As a second country, Norway is selected for further analysis, too.

With a total of seven cases, five from Germany and two from Norway, a more thorough simulation is performed. The identification and categorisation of today's most profitable water electrolyser business case operations [6] is essential for the formulation of constraints on hydrogen supply. Two categories of such business cases are identified as being profitable, namely "industry with limited constant demand of hydrogen", referred to as category A, and "distributed hydrogen refuelling stations", referred to as category C. To meet the inflexible demand of hydrogen at any time, it is assumed that for both categories a day-storage is installed. Hence, the common constraint of these two categories is the daily production target of hydrogen with the flexibility of scheduling the production over the course of a day freely. The constraint in which the categories differ is the full-load hours. In a next step, methods of finding the optimal water electrolyser scheduling with the objective of reducing the electricity cost are developed and tested with historical data. With these methods and data, the levelised cost of hydrogen (LCOH) for both types of water electrolyzers – alkaline and PEM – are computed. In order to assess the impact of the different grid services, the difference between LCOH with and without grid service provision is calculated. FCR turns out to be the most advantageous product for business case category C – for alkaline as well as for PEM electrolyzers – whereas for business case category A, aFRR shows the highest potential for Alkaline and FCR for PEM water electrolyzers.

For distribution system operator (DSO) grid services, no relevant established market with transparent price information, product definitions and market rules could be found in Europe. Existing market conditions such as subsidy rules and price levels set by fossil technologies as of yet hinder the profitable operation of a water electrolyser for the provision of DSO grid services. In spite of that, and because of the obvious relevance and potential of distributed renewable energy systems, congestion management is selected as a case for this group of services. In order to investigate the underlying economics and to assess the added value congestion management provides to the distribution grid as a means of providing flexibility, a model is developed showing the potential impact of congestion management on the LCOH for all full load hours and grid strength levels.

1 Introduction

With the FCH-JU public-private partnership under the EU Horizon 2020 framework, the EU supports research in sustainable hydrogen production. The FCH project ELYntegration reports a maximum sustainable hydrogen production cost of 8-10 €/kg to be competitive with conventional fuel for vehicles [7, p. 14]. Grid services may contribute as a secondary revenue stream to achieve this goal, as the flexibility of water electrolysers (WE) may be offered to TSOs for example as frequency containment reserve (FCR), frequency restoration reserve (FRR), or to DSOs for congestion management and voltage control among others [8, pp. 37-38].

QualyGridS work package (WP) 1 analyses the technical aspects for the application of WEs in the grid service markets. Basing on it, WP 6 aims to identify the most promising business cases for the application of WEs in the European grid service markets at different levels of the electricity grid. This report refers to WP 6.1 and 6.2 (Figure 1), which, as a first step towards achieving the goals of WP 6, identify and select market opportunities based on relevant constraints and criteria then assess the most promising grid service products by considering current WE business cases and features. To this end, the interrelations and the economic flows are considered, together with relevant legal and environmental aspects. Additionally, differences and particularities in relation to the member states are elaborated.

In WP 6.1, four TSO grid service products in two countries, Germany and Norway, have been identified as particularly attractive for WEs. For Germany, FCR, mFRR and aFRR were found to be the most promising grid service products, while for Norway the product mFRR was selected for further analysis. To make the cases comparable, they were quantified with regard to levelised cost of hydrogen (LCOH) savings. The four most promising products are proposed for further analysis in WP 6.3 and 6.4.

Figure 1: Embedding of WP 6.1 and 6.2 within the QualyGridS work packages WP 1.1 and 6.3 to 6.5. WP 6.1 identifies 8 grid service candidates, and WP 6.2 deepens the analysis, resulting in the four highest potential scenarios.

In Chapter 2, the background of the grid service and hydrogen markets is described, supporting the later evaluation of the business cases. Typical applications of WEs drawn from literature are categorised. An outlook on the power system regarding competing flexibility technologies and future scenarios is discussed, from which future market price implications and trends are reasoned. Chapter 3 introduces the methodology applied for this research: it specifies the multi criteria evaluation including the definition of decision criteria and weights and explains the survey that was conducted in 2017/2018 amongst European TSOs and DSOs. Since the data available for the grid service products widely differs between nations, different scenarios for the comparison of the grid service products are built which unveil the sensitivity of the missing data. Following on from that, the concept of the business model canvas is introduced in addition to a method applied for the

characterisation of the grid service markets, and the economic business case calculations. Chapter 4 then explains the logic of the TSO grid service markets and the relations between the relevant stakeholders. Due to the harmonisation efforts of European countries and ENTSO-E in particular, the aggregator model is widely accepted and national differences at this level are minor or are anticipated to disappear in the near future. Chapter 5 introduces a ranking for more than 50 European grid service products based on the criteria introduced in Chapter 3.1, and specifies which of the candidates will be analysed with greater detail in Chapter 6. There, TSO grid services from Germany and Norway are considered. As shown with the example of Germany, it turns out that the question of the most interesting grid service depends on the full-load hours (FLH): for high FLH-operation, automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve (aFRR) in Germany is the most attractive grid service, whereas for FLH below 6000 h Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) is more attractive. Furthermore, Chapter 6 considers a hypothetical case of a DSO grid service based on congestion management. There the number of curtailed hours has to be unrealistically high. Finally, Chapter 7 draws the conclusion from the overall task objective.

2 Background

Deliverable 1.1 of the QualyGridS report lists grid services known from literature and evaluates their suitability for the WE business case based on technical considerations [8]. In section 2.1, this is taken as a starting point for this work. Sections 2.2 and 2.3 review the literature on power-to-gas technologies providing grid services in recent projects and draw the probable change of the grid service market design under the regime of Entso-E. In order to understand the potential of WEs competing with other technologies, section 2.4 summarises what is known from literature about the future market development, and section 2.5 explains future price expectations. The European hydrogen market potential is summarized in the literature review of section 2.6, which is found to be equally relevant for the evaluation of promising grid service markets. Furthermore, in section 2.7, typical applications of WEs from literature are categorised, as applications have a direct impact on how a WE is operated and thus how it can reasonably provide grid services.

2.1 Grid services

2.1.1 TSO grid services

The following grid services¹ are rated suitable² for provision by WEs to TSOs [8, pp. 37-38]:

- FCR (rating: medium)

‘Frequency containment reserve (FCR), also referred to as primary frequency reserve, is an automatic operating reserve designed to stabilise the power system frequency and to make sure that the frequency will not further deviate from 50Hz. In many countries, FCR is mandatory for large capacity generators and implemented using droop-based frequency controllers. These reserves have to be activated fast (typically within 30sec) and are required to be online for a relatively short period (typically up to 15 minutes). The volume of the primary reserve is set by the ENTSO-E. The global reaction of FCR according to ENTSO-E regulations must be a symmetrical and linear activation with a total activation at a frequency deviation of $\pm 200\text{mHz}$ [3]. However, in order to allow different types of flexibility (generation, demand, storage, etc.) to participate in FCR, asymmetrical solutions (upwards/downwards) dedicated to specific frequency ranges (such as between -200mHz and -100mHz) are also implemented in some countries.’ [8, p. 15]

- aFRR and mFRR (rating: high)

‘Frequency restoration reserve (FRR) is intended to replace FCR and restore the frequency to the target frequency, in Europe usually 50.00Hz. Two types of FRR are distinguished, i.e. automatic FRR (aFRR) and manual FRR (mFRR). aFRR is normally understood as the new terminology to replace secondary frequency reserve/load frequency control (LFC) and activated by using an electronic actuating signal/control set-point instructed by the TSO; while mFRR is often referred to as fast tertiary frequency reserves that are dispatched remotely by TSOs through messages or phone calls. Both types of FRR are operating reserves used for restoring the power balance to the scheduled value and consequently the system frequency to the nominal value. Similar to FCR, the implementation of FRR also varies from country to country primarily due to historical reasons.’ [8, p. 15]

- Replacement reserve (RR) (rating: high)

‘Replacement reserve (RR), sometimes referred to as slow tertiary reserves, is an optional manual reserve with an activation lead time normally exceeding 15 minutes that may last up to hours. RR is used to restore the required level of operating reserves to be prepared for a further system imbalance.’ [8, p. 16]

¹ Demand Side Response (DSR), which is also referred to in WP1, is covered by the other grid service products.

² Suitability rating: medium, high or very high

- Congestion management (rating: medium)

‘Congestion management refers to avoiding the thermal overload of system components by reducing the amount of power transferred. The reason for network congestion is normally due to insufficient network capacity, therefore congestions can be observed at cross-border levels, national levels, transmission networks and distribution networks. Solutions to congestion management can be either implemented at the planning stage through grid reinforcement or implemented at the operational stage by optimally dispatching the regulatory capacity offered by service providers. Similar to voltage control (see section 2.1.2), congestion management is also a location-dependent service. The corresponding requirements on capacity, service time window, ramp rate and reactive capabilities etc., therefore vary from case to case.’ [8, p. 19]

The TSO grid services can be further characterised as follows:

- Asymmetric positive products: the power output of the reserve providing unit (RPU; WE in our case) can be increased if it is a power generator, or the power consumption can be decreased if it is a load, the latter corresponding to a WE in our case.
- Asymmetric negative products: the power output of the RPU can be decreased if it is a power generator, or the power consumption can be increased if it is a load, the latter again corresponding to a WE in our case.
- Symmetric products: the RPU operates at a working point at which it is possible to either increase or decrease its operating power. An RPU, which provides one direction of flexibility only, can still contribute to symmetrical products if the missing side is provided by the aggregator. If, as an example, the TSO orders 5 MW at 20 € per MW and hour of availability, that could be delivered with either one RPU offering 5 MW symmetrically, receiving a remuneration of up to 20 € per MW and hour. Or, if the TSO accepts aggregation of asymmetric RPUs, it could be delivered with two RPUs, one providing power up and the other providing power down; both together with the aggregator sharing the remuneration of 20 € per MW and hour.

2.1.2 DSO grid services

The following grid services are rated suitable³ for provision by WEs to DSOs [8, p. 38]:

- Congestion management (rating: high)

For details see chapter 2.1.1

- Voltage control (rating: medium)

‘Voltage control is accomplished by managing reactive power on an AC power system, wherein reactive power can be produced and absorbed by both generation and transmission equipment at specified service points. In Europe, the provision of reactive power is typically an obligation to large-scale generators (50MW in UK) implemented via grid code or is from other reactive power facilities (e.g. capacitors and Static Var Compensators) connected to the transmission network. In some countries like Denmark, reactive power reserve can be acquired through a market-based tendering process. However, because there are only a few power plants that are qualified, the competition is little.’ [8, p. 19]

‘Services for voltage management include two service products to address the voltage issues,

- Voltage Support: Event-based voltage management through regulating active and reactive power.
- VAR Support: Reactive power reserve.’ [8, p. 21]

³ Suitability rating: medium, high or very high

2.1.3 BRP, P2P, and other service requesters

The following grid services are rated suitable⁴ for provision by WEs to BRPs and other service requesters, including P2P configurations [8, p. 38]:

- Self-balancing (rating: very high)
'Self-balancing: is the reduction of imbalance by the BRP within its portfolio to avoid/reduce imbalance charges.' [8, p. 22]
- Day-ahead portfolio optimisation (rating: very high)
'Enables the BRP to optimally reduce its overall electricity purchase costs or to increase its revenue from selling electricity based on the forecast' [8, p. 22].
- Peer-to-peer (P2P) energy trading (rating: very high)
'Today, there are many P2P energy trading platforms developed and tested. The most notable ones include the Brooklyn microgrid [9], Vandebro platform [10], and Open Utility [11], etc. Brooklyn microgrid is a community microgrid with P2P energy market for local end users and local RES to freely choose each other within the community. The latter two platforms are launched in the Netherlands and UK, aiming to enable electricity end-users to freely select and prioritise electricity suppliers (can sometimes be prosumers who have excessive energy production) at national or international scales. As the name indicates, P2P energy trading is oriented towards energy products at the current stage. Correspondingly, the requirements on energy products/services consider primarily the availability and the amount of the energy to be traded.' [8, p. 22]

2.2 Power-to-gas technologies providing grid services today

With regards to the state of the grid service markets, several publications recently reported on possible business models and economic aspects for the introduction of sustainable hydrogen technologies:

In the FCH project H2FUTURE, the deliverable 2.6 details use case descriptions for the quasi-commercial operation of WEs, considering hedging, day-ahead optimisation and intraday optimisation [12].

Breyer, Tsupari, Tikka, & Vainikka were looking for profitable business models for the Power-to-Gas (PtG) technology in Finland. They report on two cases: The PtG integration into an existing pulp mill, as well as the integration into a bio-diesel plant. Profitable operation with commercially available technology is identified in the case where grid services are offered [13].

For France, Bennoua, Duigou, Quéméré & Dautremont simulated the application of hydrogen technologies for balancing markets and load in combination with nuclear power plants. They report a sustainable hydrogen production cost of 3 to 4.5 €/kg without electricity cost, by use of a salt cavern for storage. By considering additional benefits from the balancing markets, the authors expect to reach production cost near a reference cost of 0.9 €/kg [14]. In addition, Guinot, Montignac, Champel & Vannucci simulated the profitability of electrolysis-based hydrogen production providing *frequency containment reserves* (FCR) for the French market. They concluded that the current commercial conditions would not allow for an attractive business case. Production costs were reported to actually increase under the FCR regime. An increase in remuneration by a factor two or three would be needed in order to reach break-even when offering FCR availability in France [15].

The Smart Energy Demand Coalition SEDC reflects the status of the European grid service markets in the context of *demand response* applications, where WEs can be seen to be operational as well. In France, Belgium, Switzerland, Great Britain, Ireland and Finland, aggregated demand response is considered *commercially active*. Germany, Austria, Netherlands, Denmark, Norway and Sweden are considered *partially open*. In these countries, regulatory barriers for aggregated demand response are an issue. Portugal, Spain, Italy and Estonia are considered *closed* markets.

⁴ Suitability rating: medium, high or very high

A preliminary development is seen in Poland and Slovenia, which opened some of their markets to load participation, but not to aggregated load. Therefore, they disqualify all except the largest industrial consumers [16].

Furthermore, the FCH project Grid Integrated Multi Megawatt High Pressure Alkaline Electrolysers for Energy Applications (ELYntegration) reports in its task 2.3 on nine possible business models for future application of WEs, based on outlooks for the years 2014, 2024 and 2034. It identifies and values nine possible grid services, one based on arbitrage trading, six for TSOs and two combinations [7]. In task 6.4 the same authors identify drivers and risks for these nine models [6].

2.3 Evolution of grid service market designs

The EU's harmonisation efforts for the TSO grid service markets [5], as well as national initiatives will further impact the markets. For example, Finland has taken measures to enhance market transparency in the grid service markets [17]. Moreover, the TSO grid service market in Finland will double in capacity, as the government intends to develop the TSO grid service system towards enhanced flexibility [18]. Denmark has a new online portal where all prices/products offered on the electricity market for consumers with an annual consumption below 100 MWh have to be reported [19]. Increased market transparency is a very desirable trend to assess market opportunities for WEs in grid applications more accurately.

According to ENTSO-E the market design may be expected to further evolve by the introduction of a single grid service marketplace. In a 2017 working paper⁵ aiming at simultaneously facilitating the integration of distributed flexibility resources⁶ (DFRs) for congestion management (CM) and other flexibility purposes shown in Figure 2, ENTSO-E makes recommendations on the EU level on how a future grid service market should be organised in accordance with the guideline on electricity balancing (GLEB) and for the realisation of the internal energy market.

Figure 2: Spheres of interest for distributed flexibility. Adapted from [20]

Figure 3 illustrates a high-level market design that would be set to benefit the commercial interests and technical capabilities of the DFRs in addition to meeting the requirements of the electrical system as a whole. This is thought to be achievable due to the coordination between the market processes (intra-day and day-ahead markets and balancing and CM), which would enable the DFRs to be activated at the location and time that offers the highest value. It is stressed that CM should not be limited to DSOs at the distribution grid level (a scheme known as a 'cascading principle') but should also include TSOs at the transmission level to ensure market liquidity, greater flexibility options for system operators, and via a single flexibility market, prevent double or counter activation of the same service at the same time.

⁵ The policy paper was published in December 2017 with final recommendations [20].

⁶ Conventional generation plants, storage facilities, manageable RES, industrial or small consumers with demand management capability, etc.

Figure 3: ENTSO-E-proposed market organisation for equal access of distributed flexibility resources (DFRs) to all markets. Adapted from [20]

Exemplified in Figure 4 is a single flexibility market that serves to fulfil the ENTSO-E’s market design recommendations of transparency, neutrality, non-discrimination, liquidity and efficient market implementation. The single flexibility marketplace accepts flexibility bids (capacity or energy) from reserve providing units (RPU), in Figure 4 called *flexibility service providers*, for CM, balancing and/or bids that serve both market processes. TSOs and DSOs communicate their network limitations before sending activations to the RPU. In addition, TSOs forward the relevant balancing bids (for FRR and RR) to the common European balancing merit order lists (MOLs). The marketplace provides updated activation information and access to all bids including locational information (relevant for CM). Whether grid operators (TSOs and DSOs) activate flexibility directly or via the marketplace depends on the country’s assumed implementation strategy.

Figure 4: Example of a single flexibility marketplace for balancing TSO and DSO CM processes [1].

As a starting point, DSOs would have the responsibility of making their needs for flexibility in their networks explicit. Namely, reliability and the amount of activation needed (length, times and number of activations). With TSO and DSO flexibility needs considered, CM products that are

suitable for both purposes (i.e. harmonised products) should only then be created with the same bidding process for simplicity.

2.4 Competing technologies and future scenarios

The grid services presented in Chapter 2.1 can be offered by various technology types. In order to analyse the potential of other technologies competing with water electrolyzers (WEs) for the provision of grid services, forecasts – especially price trajectory forecasts of today’s and future technologies – have to be made. In order to evaluate whether and to what extent a certain technology is likely to penetrate a market, a prediction of tomorrow’s market is essential. Therefore, two topics worth examining together are: “*competing technologies*” and “*future scenarios*”. To do so, scenarios of the future energy system are selected from literature, basing predominantly off of the International Energy Agency (IEA) [21]. After a brief description of these scenarios, the role that certain competing technologies will play in such scenarios in the long term are analysed with regard to flexibility. Thereby, system-flexibility is viewed as a whole rather than as single flexibility products. As we will later see, the reason behind this approach is that predicting the demand of single flexibility products in the long term is not reasonably possible. For the near future, however, the likely development of flexibility markets and how WEs compare to competing technologies is analysed. Finally, likely price implications (for wholesale electricity prices as well as grid service prices) of long-term scenarios are discussed and price assumptions for the further assessment of the potential of WEs are presented.

2.4.1 Future power system

The power system within the European Union (EU) is undergoing a transition to a low carbon economy, where a strong focus is being placed on renewable energy sources, energy efficiency measures and electrification of transport and heat for buildings. The new 2030 targets laid out in the “Clean energy for All Europeans” package highlight the crucial role renewables will take on as the backbone of the EU’s energy system. A renewable gross final energy consumption of 32% [21, p. 367], and an overall RES electricity generation reaching 55% in 2030 and 63% in 2040 [21, p. 76] are all indications of this. Inroads have been made with respect to the increasing shares of variable renewable energy in the generation mix, with wind alone (170 GW) matching coal capacity for the first time in 2017 [21, p. 368]. The opening for variable renewable energy sources (VRES) comes off the back of the uncertain future for nuclear power and mothballing coal power plants (which represent the EU’s two largest electricity generation sources).

As the share of VRES surges to 40% in 2040 [21, p. 76], flexibility requirements will undoubtedly increase significantly. In fact, flexibility sources are expected to double by 2040 [21, p. 324], posing challenges to the electric grid to accommodate new flexibility providers. The combined effect of the growing need for grid flexibility and insufficient conventional power plants to provide flexible generation will cause an increase in the value of flexibility, as well as create conditions that necessitate the inclusion of other technologies capable of providing it.

2.4.2 Scenarios

Different scenarios are referred to for the discussion of the expansion rate and the degree of future VRES penetration. Assumptions and estimates throughout this discussion are based on scenarios outlined in the IEA’s 2018 World Energy Outlook (WEO) [21]. The scenarios outlined differ primarily in terms of quantity CO₂ emissions.

In the least sustainable scenario (Current Policy Scenario) it is assumed that the focus of political decision-makers is more on economic growth than on the decarbonisation of the energy system. Since it is very questionable that there will be a significant demand for sustainably produced hydrogen in such a scenario, we do not consider this scenario in the further analysis. In the Sustainable Development Scenario (SDS) and the New Policy Scenario (NPS) further efforts to reduce CO₂ emissions are implied. While the NPS builds on the ambitions of policy makers today, the goal of the SDS strategy is to meet CO₂ emissions under the Paris Agreement.

The IEA is the most influential think tank in regard of future energy forecasts. However, the IEA has been criticized for constantly underestimating future growth-rates of VRES [22]. M. Metayer, C. Breyer and H.-J. Fell [23] argue, that the linear growth-rate assumption made by the IEA was not describing accurately the exponential growth we have seen. According to W. Brent [24], the

exponential growth in recent years was mainly due to PV-growth in China, which in turn was driven by strong policies. The author considers it unlikely that exponential growth-rates will continue in the coming years. In fact, the IEA report on renewable capacity growth [25] has shown, that VRES-growth stalled in 2018 at 177 GW additional net capacity globally. To achieve the SDS VRES projections, an average growth rate of 300 GW/a between 2018 and 2030 is required [25]. Hence, despite earlier critics of the IEA's conservative forecasts for VRES growth, the SDS appears to be an ambitious scenario that is well suited for our analysis.

As seen in Figure 5, the SDS and NPS forecasts exhibit a dramatic increase in VRES. While today, roughly 14% of the electricity is generated by VRES in the European Union, this number is expected to increase to 38% and 41% in the NPS and the SDS, respectively. Hence, a dramatic increase in VRES is expected in both the less ambitious NPS in terms of greenhouse-gas reduction as well as in the more ambitious SDS. As a result, the assumption that there will be an increased demand for flexible power sources can be regarded as relatively robust. However, the VRES shares in 2040 illustrate that under the SDS the majority of electricity generated within the European Union will still be produced with dispatchable power plants. While the global flexible capacity by 2040 can be expected to double in comparison to today's capacity, centralized power plants will still contribute to the bulk of this flexibility [21].

Figure 5 Gross electricity production in 2017 and in 2040 (own figure with data sourced from [21]).

Hence, it can be concluded that the demand for flexibility will be increasing in the next decades. However, since roughly 60% of the European electricity generation is made up of dispatchable conventional power plants, it is likely that these power plants will continue to satisfy the majority of the flexibility demand.

2.4.3 Long-term flexibility technology development

Flexibility is the “ability of a power system to reliably and cost-effectively manage the variability and uncertainty of demand and supply across all relevant timescales” [21, p. 17]. In this section when referring to the future in the long-term, we refer to flexibility in accordance with this definition, whereas, grid service markets discussed in the following section 2.4.4 refer to the short-term future where it makes up a part of short-term flexibility. In energy only markets, scarcity price signals will trigger new investments. Flexible power plants or flexible loads profit the most from such price peaks, since they can either capture (power plants) or avoid (load) these peaks. However, extreme price peaks can be politically controversial and as a result, market designs are or will be introduced in order to avoid them. To incentivise investments in flexibility, non-energy products therefore have to be introduced. This can already be seen in some markets that have, in addition to grid service products, capacity markets and operating reserve prices [21].

Generally, the way in which flexibility is rewarded is very much politically driven. While it is possible to forecast the amount of economically reasonable flexibility based on different scenarios, it is impossible to foresee how different flexibility technologies will be rewarded long term. Therefore, all technologies that offer flexibility must be included in the longer-term analysis of future competing technologies. Furthermore, all technologies are exposed to the risk of changing market rules.

Flexibility in general can be brought to the electrical system by dispatching supply (**power plant flexibility**), flexible demand (**demand side management**), **storage** or **interconnections** [21]. In order to evaluate future competing technologies, all four means of flexibility have to be evaluated in terms of their future potential.

2.4.3.1 Power plant flexibility

Flexibility offered by conventional power plants (mainly hydropower and gas plants) is the main source of flexibility today. Technologically, the flexibility capability can be increased by either retrofitting existing plants or by the replacement of power plants with more flexible ones. Traditional band power providing power plants, such as nuclear as well as coal power plants, can be updated so that they can also provide a certain flexibility [21]. In the future we could see VRES becoming a greater contributor to grid services from the suite of flexible power plants available as they are being designed to become grid-flexible power generators as demonstrated by [26]. As displayed previously in Figure 5, dispatchable power plants even in 2040 contribute more than half of the European gross electricity production under the two scenarios SDS and NPS. Therefore, conventional power plants will very likely continue to be the cornerstones of the flexibility needed in the electrical system. Globally, a flexible capacity of 3400 GW is contributed by conventional power plants today. This number will increase to 5200 GW under the NPS in 2040 [21].

2.4.3.2 Demand side management

Today, demand side management (DSM) contributes only about 0.5% of the total global flexibility. Mainly industrial and commercial consumers offer such flexibility. However, smart grid infrastructure, such as smart meters and sensors open possibilities to offer demand flexibility on an end-user level. Especially with the rise in electric vehicles (EVs) and heat pumps, demand could bring interesting opportunities for DSM. However, since only a part of these new loads (EV and heat pumps) are flexible, an increase of such new loads not only increases the flexible load in a system, but also the inflexible and as a result, also leads to an increased demand for flexibility [21].

Recent studies suggest a technical potential for the total DSM in Germany and Northern Europe of about 10-15 % of the national peak load [27], [28]. Since DSM usually causes high opportunity costs for industrial loads and relatively high investment costs for smaller loads, DSM is not free [22]. In other words, only a portion of the technical potential can be regarded as cost effective. Therefore, the technical potential is a rather theoretical value and the actual flexibility contribution will be significantly less. As a consequence of this, in the NPS the global flexibility contribution of DSM increases from today's 0.5% to a modest 3% in 2040 [21].

The CAPEX of DSM are usually lower compared to the CAPEX of batteries [29]. The WE business cases outlined in Section 6 are a form of DSM with very low opportunity costs. WEs are used for the primary purpose of supplying various industries with sustainably produced hydrogen, therefore most of its CAPEX are sunk costs for the secondary purpose of balancing the grid, as most of the CAPEX is amortized by the hydrogen sales revenue stream. In other words, the flexibility offered by WEs can be viewed as cost-effective when it comes to offering load flexibility.

2.4.3.3 Storage

Today, the vast majority of electrical storage is provided by pumped hydro (97% globally). However, the costs of utility-scale battery storage have significantly decreased over the last years, leading to a dramatic growth in new installations. However, since these batteries are installed for the primary use of providing flexibility to the grid, the flexibility revenue is required to amortize the CAPEX. The costs of a four-hour system (i.e. C-rate = C/4) are expected to fall from 400 \$/kWh in 2017 to only 220 \$/kWh in 2040 [21, p. 365]. With such price-trajectories, battery storage is expected to contribute 4% of the global flexibility in 2040 under the NPS. Under the more extreme SDS scenario which is characterised by steeper learning curves (100 \$/kWh in 2030) and the use of second life batteries originally used in EVs, the global battery storage capacity would increase to 540 GW (10%) in 2040 [21, p. 366]. We therefore can conclude that the importance of battery

storage as a flexibility source will increase considerably. However, it is unlikely that this technology will replace other flexibility technologies completely.

2.4.3.4 Interconnections

Interconnections between different areas can lower flexibility demand by enlarging balancing areas. More specifically, interconnections can lower mismatches between demand- and VRES production-profiles by pooling each of them together. Hence, interconnections reduce the demand of flexibility and can therefore be regarded as flexibility providers. An additional 100 GW of transmission interconnections is expected to be installed within the EU market by 2040. Globally, interconnections will contribute 11% of electrical flexibility in 2040 under the NPS [21, p. 362].

2.4.4 Future grid service markets and short-term technology developments

For short-term forecasts, estimates of the grid-service demand can be made. Since battery storage and DSM are increasingly penetrating the balancing markets, we discuss likely developments in market size as well as market shares of these two technologies.

The size of a grid service market and the market share of each technology providing the service highly depend on the specific characteristics of the energy system at hand and on the availability of competing technologies. To give a sense of this, we draw on EU projected control reserve sizes and expected market shares for batteries to estimate the expected remaining market share to be captured by other technologies that generally include DSM and WEs. Kessels et al. [30] project the future size of FCR and aFRR based on EU TSO data and project the market share for stationary batteries based on EU and European Commission targets. Starting with the reference year 2016, FCR is expected to remain constant at its current size of 3'000 MW through 2020 up until 2025, whilst aFRR is expected to increase gradually from 8'400 MW to 9'200 MW and 10'000 MW respectively. For FCR, stationary batteries are projected to cover 10%-20% in 2025 and 10%-20% for aFRR.

Unlike batteries whose potential is for the most part cost dependent, DSM – especially for smaller loads – is also affected by additional dependencies that are currently hindering their rate of market diffusion. Most notably, on one hand are consumer acceptance, behaviour and education, whilst on the other, market and regulatory frameworks that enable and encourage consumer participation in markets with the help of low entry thresholds [31]. DSM is the wild card of the three technologies because there already exists a large demand side flexibility resource that remains untapped. However, activation of these assets depends on how the before mentioned hurdles evolve, meaning that the DSM flexibility market share could explode at any time.

WEs are in the infancy stages as grid connected RPU's and therefore have much ground to cover when it comes to competing with batteries and smart grids.

2.4.5 Synthesis

As seen in Chapter 2.4, investments in batteries and DSM providing grid services are likely to increase in the short-term. Costs (of batteries and opportunity costs for DSM) as well as the lack of consumer acceptance (for small load DSM) are likely to prevent these technologies from dominating the balancing markets. As we switch to the longer-term outlook, we need to look at the system flexibility as a whole. As discussed in 2.4.2 and depicted in Figure 6, electric flexibility demand is expected to grow dramatically as the demand profile changes and the share of VRES rises. While conventional power plants remain fundamental to flexibility, interconnections, DSM and battery storage expansion will play an important role in meeting the needs for flexibility by complementing conventional power plant contributions. We can therefore conclude, that, also in the long-term, despite the entry of new flexibility technologies, we cannot see any reason to believe there will be a dominating flexibility providing technology. Hence, we see no evidence supporting the notion that there is a major risk of collapsing revenue streams for WEs offering flexibility as a result of technological developments or the market entrance of other flexibility providers. The way flexibility is rewarded, however, depends on market rules. These rules can penalize or incentivise certain technologies and all technologies are exposed to the risks of changing market rules.

Figure 6 Global flexibility in 2017 and in 2040 under NPS assumption (sourced from [21])

2.5 Effect of scenarios on future market prices

2.5.1 Day ahead prices

For both scenarios, SDS and NPS (section 2.4.2), electricity costs are expected to rise within the EU, under the SDS more so than the NPS⁷. As described in Section 2.4, in energy only markets with a high penetration of VRES, high price peaks, or scarcity prices are expected. On the other hand, zero to low variable costs of VRES suggests many hours will be characterised by low prices, too. Therefore, higher price fluctuations or price volatility is likely. Based on primary energy price predictions, weather variables, cross border capacity and other parameters, Energy Brainpool predicts energy prices by modelling the power system using IEA's commodities assumptions for the SDS [32]. As can be seen in Figure 7, not only is the baseload price expected to rise, but also the monthly fluctuations as well as the overall price volatility. The baseload price rises from 45 €/MWh in 2020 to roughly 85 €/MWh in 2040. This corresponds to a 90% increase. Over the same time period, the maximum difference in monthly baseload prices within a year will more than double while the Q10/Q90-percentile-based spread increases by more than 50%.

⁷ As evidenced by the published residential electricity prices in WEO [21, p. 471].

Figure 7 Price prediction (upper: monthly baseload price, lower: yearly baseload-price with box-plot) for selected EU countries [32]. A larger difference between Q90 and Q10 implies a higher volatility.

2.5.2 Balancing market prices

Hirth and Ziegenhagen [33] argue that due to the stochastic nature of VRES infeed, an increase in flexibility demand in general and of balancing power in particular can be expected. The same authors show that in Germany, despite a dramatic increase in VRES from 27 GW to 78 GW, the TSOs' demand for balancing reserves has actually been reduced by 15%. Ocker and Ehrhart [34] argue, that an increased VRES infeed does not necessarily mean an increased demand in balancing power. Reason being, in Germany for example, the higher demand for flexibility is traded through the intraday market. Thus, higher intraday trading volumes reflect higher flexibility demands.

A contributory factor to lower balancing prices lies in the ongoing harmonization of European balancing markets. Cross-border cooperation has therefore led to efficiency gains. Ocker and Ehrhart have also shown that participants in the German balancing markets are bidding on a non-competitive price level. Harmonization will lessen the likelihood of such bidding strategies persisting. As a result, a harmonization of European balancing markets will not only lead to converging prices, but also to more competitive price levels overall, and thus lower prices in areas where such non-competitive bidding strategies are observed.

In conclusion, it can be stated that demand for flexibility is increasing as more VRES are integrated. For a given supply, an increase in demand usually leads to higher prices. However, the volume and price of balancing products do not only depend on the flexibility demand and supply, but more importantly on market rules. As already discussed in Section 2.4.5, the development of such market rules is mainly politically driven and therefore, difficult to predict. It is therefore suggested to use a persistence-model as a baseline forecast.

2.5.3 Synthesis

Through an in-depth analysis of model outputs using the premises made for our reference scenario (SDS), it can be concluded that baseload power prices will rise substantially as well as price volatility, hence more hours will be characterized by very low and very high prices. While more VRES will most likely lead to a higher price spread and thus, incentivise flexibility in general, it is very uncertain how the volume and prices of grid service products will develop.

2.6 Hydrogen market potential

As mentioned before, the European hydrogen market potential is found to be relevant for the evaluation of promising grid service markets. Therefore, a short literature-based market overview and outlook are given here.

Total hydrogen production amounted to about 60 Mt/year globally in 2018 [35]. One hydrogen market covering different applications does not exist at the moment. Instead, the hydrogen market can be split in 3 parts: industrial captive production, merchant hydrogen shipped for relatively specialist applications in industry, and emerging markets such as PtG and hydrogen for mobility. The estimated 2018 market shares are roughly 95% for industrial captive hydrogen, 4% merchant hydrogen, and PtG plus hydrogen for mobility <1% [36].

Industrial captive production is divided into the segments chemical (63% of market share), refineries (31%), and metal processing (6%) [7]. Most of the industrial captive hydrogen is produced in a side process of ammonia production from natural gas by means of steam methane reforming (SMR). In this way, natural gas is the key cost factor of industrial hydrogen production and therefore defines the price level for industrial hydrogen applications [7, p. 12]. The chemical segment consists mainly of the production of ammonia, methanol, and polymers such as polyurethane. National numbers for hydrogen demand therefore also depend on the number and size of production sites for ammonia, methanol, polymers, and refineries that are operating in a country, and are not readily available. Based on ammonia production and the number of refineries, especially Germany, Poland, Netherlands, Italy, and France currently have a large demand for (industrial) hydrogen [7, p. 15].

The European hydrogen demand accounts for approximately 6.2 Mt/year or 16% of the global hydrogen demand. [7, p. 10]. Studies state that this demand will rise by a yearly rate of around 1% and reach around 50 Mt in 2025 [37]. Although industrial prices are not transparent, also because trading is taking place bilaterally with individualised contracts rather than in organised exchange

type of markets with standardised contracts, current prices are estimated to be around 10-60 €/kg depending on the purity level and the location of consumption [37]. Currently, production of hydrogen by electrolysis is neglected as it is not cost-competitive for industrial use [38, p. 42]. Sustainable hydrogen production therefore aims at other forms of hydrogen applications such as mobility, storage or industrial applications with a high interest in sustainability. However, high transaction costs of hydrogen could foster the deployment of distributed WEs as they provide scalable local production. In particular, if hydrogen has to be transported over a longer distance than 100 km, transaction costs of about 43 €/MWh LHV (about 1.5 Euro/kg) are incurred [38, p. 37].

In the emerging markets - hydrogen for mobility and PtG - the demand is currently <500 kt/year, but estimated to double by 2028, thereby reaching a market share of 2% [36]. According to strategy consultancy Hincio [39], and based on national H₂ mobility scenarios, by 2030 the EU could reach a H₂ consumption of 7.86 Mt. However, according to first estimations made in the ELYntegration project, the hydrogen demand of mobility will only reach 1.7-3 Mt by 2030 [7, p. 16].

Prices will gradually decrease as markets become more mature and the technology further develops. The current retail price for hydrogen in mobility is around 10 €/kg, while prices could drop to 5-7 €/kg by 2030 [37]. Green hydrogen might achieve a higher price due to renewable energy targets or low-carbon regulations. However, the added value of carbon neutral H₂ is estimated to be below 0.5 €/kg even if CO₂ prices are seven times higher than they are today [37]. The same authors expect that about 15% of all hydrogen produced - roughly 1.4 million tons per year - could originate from renewable and/or low-carbon sources by 2030.

Table 1: Emerging hydrogen market - 2018 and 2028.

	Emerging hydrogen market in 2018 (mobility, PtG)		Hydrogen market potential in 2028 (mobility, PtG etc.)	
	Volume	Pricing	Volume	Pricing
EU	<500 kt/year [36]	10 €/kg [37]	6 Mt/year (estimated using figures from [36] and [39]) 1– 2.1 Mt/year (estimated using figures from [36] and [7, p. 16])	5.8-7.5 €/kg (derived from estimates for 2030 in [37])
Additional income	-	-	-	“Green H ₂ surcharge” <0.5 €/kg [37]

2.7 Categories of typical WE applications

Typical WE use cases for larger scale units (ca. 100 kW and above) can be split into four categories. Since the main objective of this study constitutes the identification of cases for which the power reserve offering contributes to a profitable business case, only cases that are regarded as being profitable within the short- to mid-term future are selected for further analysis.

2.7.1 Category A: industry with limited constant demand of hydrogen

Certain industrial processes, such as edible oil processing, glass production or metal processing, require relatively small and constant streams of process hydrogen [40]. Depending on the site, a WE can economically be favourable compared to a centralised production with additional storage and transportation costs. Hence, WEs in this category are installed in order to reduce production cost. As a result, the WEs are dimensioned with the objective of minimising the hydrogen production cost. According to [36], in such a setup capital expenditure usually is the dominant factor, resulting in a minimal sizing of the electrolysers while meeting hydrogen production demand. Therefore, the units are required to run most of the time close to their nominal power.

For further analysis, it is therefore assumed, that the WEs in this category are running at 100% of their nominal power for approximately 8'000 hours a year. To balance the demand fluctuations, the hydrogen is stored in a relatively small temporary storage. For further analysis, a one-day storage is assumed. Hence, in order to meet the daily demand of hydrogen, the WE production corresponds to the production of 22 hours at nominal power for each day, but the scheduling of the hydrogen production over the course of a day can be chosen by the operator.

2.7.2 Category B: industry with high demand of hydrogen

Industries with a high demand of hydrogen, such as ammonia and crude refineries, often install WEs solely for the purpose of public relations [36]. The global hydrogen demand of the petroleum refining industry amounts to 15 million tons per year [41], whereby the hydrogen is mainly obtained from natural gas by a steam methane reforming process [42]. WEs installed at such sites only produce a marginal amount of the total process-hydrogen demand. As a result, neither an upper nor a lower demand limit for electrolyser-based hydrogen is needed. Therefore, the full-load hours remain unfixed, making WEs installed in those industries suitable for any balancing product. Since the rationale for installing a WE is not strictly economic, category B is not further analysed in this study.

2.7.3 Category C: distributed hydrogen refuelling stations

According to [43], hydrogen refuelling stations can be divided into two categories. The hydrogen is either produced centrally and later transported to and stored at the station ("stations with hydrogen delivery") or it is produced on-site ("distributed refuelling stations"). In 2015, distributed hydrogen refuelling stations with on-site, grid-connected WE accounted for roughly 40% of all hydrogen refuelling stations⁸. To cope with the fluctuating demand, even stations with on-site hydrogen production are equipped with hydrogen storage. To further increase the flexibility, some stations with on-site hydrogen production are additionally fed by centrally produced hydrogen and therefore represent a combination of the two refuelling station categories [44].

For further analysis, distributed refuelling stations are considered, for which it is assumed that the storage can hold as much hydrogen as one average day of operation without hydrogen input from the WE. The time required to fill the storage from 0 to 100% – whilst still being in operation – is also assumed to last one day. Hence, the units installed in this category are characterised by 4'380 full-load hours (FLH) and – due to the storage – have a certain flexibility.

2.7.4 Category D: power to gas connected to the natural gas grid

Category D refers to facilities in which the hydrogen is fed into the natural gas grid. Up to a certain percentage, the hydrogen is either injected directly into the gas-grid, or it is first transformed into a synthetic natural gas [45].

To date, a profitable business case in this category is doubted by several authors, even under rather optimistic scenarios [46], [47], [48]. This is mainly due to the high production costs for hydrogen in comparison to the lower natural gas prices. Therefore, this category is not further considered.

⁸ Own calculation according numbers given in [44]

3 Methodology

Based on the results from WP 1.1 [8], profitable TSO and DSO grid services were searched and the most interesting cases were further analysed. Therefore, a market data analysis (price levels, environmental conditions and business logic analysis) was conducted with the help of a literature review, a survey, expert interviews, a multi-criteria evaluation and business case calculations. Relevant information was also collected thanks to the Grid Service Market Symposia GSM 2017 and 2018, which were carried out on behalf of the QualyGridS project (www.gridservicemarket.com). The following section details the key elements of the approach consisting of: the survey, the multi-criteria evaluation (MCE), the business model canvas (BMC) and the business case calculation method. Moreover, it introduces the approach with which congestion management was assessed in terms of the added value it offers to the distribution as a means of providing flexibility to the grid, evaluated with the metric savings in LCOH.

3.1 Multi criteria evaluation

The most promising cases are identified based on a MCE. The MCE is a structured approach to formalise a decision and to compare alternatives. In the given context, it is used to rank alternative grid services based on a set of evaluation criteria defining their attractiveness (multi-attribute decision-making) [49].

The MCE is implemented through the following steps:

Step 1: selection of the criteria

Relevant criteria for the evaluation of the market opportunities are identified and chosen based on literature research and expert interviews. The interviews were conducted at the QualyGridS workshop, which took place on 4 July 2018. The selection considered criteria with the least correlations and the potential to differentiate national markets. To illustrate this, from the two criteria *cost of renewable hydrogen production* and *electricity price* only the latter was chosen since the electricity price has a major impact on the renewable hydrogen production cost, i.e. the cost of renewable hydrogen production closely correlates with the electricity price. Moreover, the criteria differ between *constraints* and *factors*.

Constraints limit the possible alternatives. The *constraints* must be fulfilled; otherwise the grid service is not suitable for application with the WE. Example: the acceptance of loads for the provision of grid services is a constraint, since WEs are loads, and services that do not accept loads drop out. The constraints considered for this study are:

- 1.) Technical market requirements have to be fulfilled (see D 1.1).
- 2.) Non-rotating mass has to be accepted for the provision of the grid service.
- 3.) Loads have to be accepted for the provision of the grid service.
- 4.) The market has to be transparent, i.e. information on prices and rules are available.⁹
- 5.) If aggregation is not allowed, the minimum power requirement for a WE to provide grid services shall be 10 MW at most.¹⁰

Factors on the other hand are not mandatory, but enhance or diminish the attractiveness of a grid service. As an example, revenue as a *factor* adds to the attractiveness of a grid service. Figure 8 shows the factor tree used for the MCE, in which factors on the same hierarchical level are weighted against each other.

⁹ This criterion does not mean every detail must be at hand, but at least basic price information and business rules must be published or provided on request.

¹⁰ A power level of 10 MW should be reached by WEs within 10 years, though nowadays the limit would be closer to 1 MW. In fact, it turned out that constraint 5 did not exclude any product.

Figure 8: MCE factor tree

Economic value added of the grid service

The evaluation of the economic value added (EVA) bases on the availability price and possibly the activation price for the grid services. Since not all data is available in all relevant countries, the sensitivity of the evaluation is tested with different scenarios (see chapter 3.3). Calculation of the EVAs is described in chapters 5.1 and 5.2. The EVA inherently covers further aspects of the current market design, such as current available storage capacity and current RES volumes.

Future H₂ market potential

Hydrogen sales prices have a strong impact on the implementation of a positive business case, for which investment decisions mainly depend on the price expectation for the near future, i.e. the price expectation in 10 years. Expected regional differences are therefore to be considered in the selection of the highest potential grid service products. The future hydrogen market potential is elaborated in chapter 5.3 based on a literature review.

RES potential

Environmental trends determine the expected future market development with respect to RES capacities. A high future share of RES indicates an increasing need for grid services and thus can be understood as an indicator for attractive future market prices. The environmental trends are derived from recent literature [50, p. 68]. RES potential is to be considered twice: once impacting the grid service market potential, and once impacting the electricity price expectation.

Today's electricity price level

The wholesale electricity price is included in the multi-criteria evaluation as a decisive factor to evaluate market opportunities for WEs, as it determines the basic operating cost.

Aggregation is possible

Possibility of aggregation extends business opportunities to WEs that would otherwise not fully comply with TSO's prequalification criteria, or that would not be profitable in a stand-alone configuration. Typically, the limiting factor for WEs is the rated power.

Availability of information

Access to information is considered as a key barrier to market entry. Where complete absence of basic market information is to be considered a *constraint*, quality and details of information available as well as responsiveness of responsible persons are considered as evaluation *factors*.

Delimitations

Today’s available storage capacity in a country is not considered as a separate evaluation criterion, as it is already reflected in the grid service prices. Attractiveness of the current hydrogen market by itself is not considered either. The market for renewable hydrogen is not well developed yet, depending largely on incentives and policies, and significant changes could occur in this market in all countries during the next couple of years.

Grid fees, taxes and subsidies (i.e. exemption from end-user charges such as taxes, levies and network charges for the electrolyser) are considered in the business case calculation in Chapter 6. For a long-term perspective, subsidies must be expected to phase out. On the other hand, grid fees and taxes are not to be applied for WEs in many practical cases.

Step 2: standardisation of the values

The values of the *factors* must be transformed to comparable units (*scores*). The standardisation schemes are given in Table 2. If no data is available for a specific factor, a score of 0 is assigned.

Table 2: Factors for the selection of the TSO grid services.

Factor	Scale	Score	
Market potential	EVA of the grid service (→ current economic value added by the grid service to the WE business, base 2016, see Chapter 5).	Linear scale: 0 = no or negative EVA, 9 = maximum value from the sample set	0..9
	RES potential (→ expected future share of fluctuating renewable energies in 2034)	Linear scale: 0 = no data or zero share, 9 = maximum future share of renewable energy (wind + solar) from the sample set	0..9
	Today’s electricity price level (→ average day ahead hourly wholesale price, base 2016)	Linear scale: 0 = maximum value from the sample set or unknown, 9 = minimum value from the sample set	0..9
	Aggregation is possible	0 = no or unknown 9 = yes	0, 9
	Future H ₂ market potential (→ How well can H ₂ be sold in 10 years.)	For each of the applications considered (mobility and PtG) a ranking ‘high’ adds 4 ½ points to the score, a ranking ‘medium’ adds 2 ¼ points and a ranking ‘low’ or no data available’ adds 0 points.	0..9
Barriers to market entry	Availability of information	0 = no access to information or some relevant information is not available in English 6 = responsive contact person, but not all relevant information is available in English 9 = responsive contact person and all relevant documentation is available in English	0, 6, 9

Step 3: weighting of the factors

The relevance of the introduced factors typically is not equal, so factors must be weighted, which is not explicit and thus not trivial. Therefore, a pairwise comparison approach based on the *analytic hierarchy process* theory [9] is followed. The evaluation of the weights takes place in multiple steps:

1. Comparison of the relevance of level 1 factors. In Figure 9, this concerns the following factors: *Barriers to market entry* and *market potential*.
2. Evaluation of the relevance of level 2 factors:
 - a. Within the group *barriers to market entry*, there is only one element – no further evaluation needed
 - b. Within the group *market potential*, an evaluation takes place between the following factors: *Aggregation is possible*, *energy price*, *future H₂ market potential*, *grid service market potential*.
3. Evaluation of the relevance of level 3 factors accordingly.

In each group, the relevance of every factor is compared with every single other factor of the same group, according to the following scheme:

Table 3: Comparison of relevance, example for the two factors Barriers to market entry and Market potential

Criteria A	A dominates	A much more relevant	A more relevant	A slightly more relevant	A and B equally relevant	B slightly more relevant	B more relevant	B much more relevant	B dominates	Criteria B
Barriers to market entry										Market potential
Intensity value (balanced scale)	9	4	2.33	1.5	1	1.5	2.33	4	9	

A balanced scale is applied to transfer the ratings into *intensity* values [9, p. 15]. The rating took place at the QualyGridS review meeting on 4 July 2018, as geometric averages of the ratings of the individual participants. Figure 9 shows the resulting weights.

Figure 9: MCE weights. w_{tot} are the resulting weights of the factors applied to the MCE

Step 4: aggregation of the weighted scores

For each candidate, the values of the *factors* are evaluated, and the scores are determined, weighted and summed up, resulting in an overall candidate score. The result is given in Chapter 5.

Step 5: sensitivity analysis

Since the MCE in many steps contains heuristic approaches and bases on incomplete data, the stability of the outcome is taken into account by the additional evaluation of the scenarios defined in chapter 3.3. This additional step can point to grid service products that would otherwise be ignored. The impact of the sensitivity analysis is considered in Chapter 5.9.

Step 6: validation of the results

The QualyGridS team and advisory board both reviewed the *factor* weighting and the selection of candidates. The review took place in August 2018 as a desk review.

3.2 Survey

Due to the lack of reliable market data in the literature, a survey was conducted. The survey was based on written questionnaires, one specifically for TSOs, and a second one specifically for DSOs. The TSO questionnaire asked about grid service product information and prices for the year 2016. The DSO questionnaire asked about the need and valuation of a load, which could be used for DSO grid services. For both questionnaires, the number of questions were kept to a minimum in order to increase the probability of a response. Both questionnaires were reviewed internally and tested with partner TSOs and DSOs. They were sent to 36 TSOs from 30 countries (28 EU countries plus Switzerland and Norway) and a selection of DSOs in winter 2017/2018. The templates can be found in the Appendices 10.2 and 10.3. The results were cross-checked with available literature, mainly from [10], [11], and [51]. If necessary for clarification of the answers, the respondents of the survey were contacted multiple times during 2018.

TSO questionnaires were sent by email to the mailbox available through the official web page of each TSO, as well as to their official postal addresses. 12 TSOs answered. DSO questionnaires were sent to 143 DSOs by email to the mailbox available through the web page of each DSO, and partly, where available, to individual members of those DSOs. Only 6 DSOs answered the survey. Those were DSOs from Spain, Bulgaria, Ireland, Latvia, Slovenia and Czech Republic.

Figure 10: Country overview of data origins for TSO services: ENTso-E: [10], European Commission: [11], [5]

Figure 10 illustrates TSO data availability in the 30 countries covered. For some countries, for which no survey answers were received, there was data available from literature, in particular [10], and [11] for UK. Partly expert interviews were conducted in addition. The French TSO was contacted multiple times, directly as well as through our French research partner CEA. Unfortunately, no answer was returned, thus information solely bases on literature. For other countries like Spain and Portugal answers were given by local DSOs, making clear that these two countries as per 2016 don't accept distributed loads as reserve providing units (RPUs). For Italy, Belgium, Slovenia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary and Romania information bases on literature solely.

3.3 Scenario definition

For TSO grid services, some market data turned out not to be comparable. In particular, a comparison of the revenue streams from utilisation and availability would require knowledge about the activation probability.¹¹ However, for many countries this information was not available. There were similar issues with the factor *future H₂ market potential*, for which there was no data available for some countries. Therefore, the impact of the data missing was evaluated by considering the following scenarios:

Scenario 1): availability only

This scenario considers remuneration from availability provision only, i.e. the RPU's readiness to be called. It favours countries like Switzerland, in which the remuneration from availability clearly excels remuneration from activation. In such a situation, it is reasonable to seek for high availability prices.

¹¹ *Activation probability* = *activation hours* / *availability hours*, where *availability hours* = number of hours an RPU is kept available to be activated on demand; *activation hours* = number of hours an RPU is called to provide control energy.

Scenario 2): availability plus activation

This scenario considers real data for countries, in which remuneration for grid service products can be calculated based on both, availability and activation remuneration. This requires activation probabilities to be available. For countries with missing data, the additional income from activation is ignored, which leads to an underestimation of the potential of those grid service products.

Scenario 3): black horse

The impact of the missing data issue in scenario 2) is evaluated by the following approach: for products with missing activation probability, the maximum probability is taken from the others. The effect on the final evaluation is then observed and interpreted as potential improvement.

Scenario 4): Ignore the factor *future H₂ market potential*

There is little data available considering national differences of the future H₂ market. Therefore, the sensitivity of the criterion *future H₂ market potential* is observed by an additional ranking for which this criterion is excluded.

3.4 Business model canvas

A business model describes the key characteristics of how a business unit generates economic value, while being impacted by business strategy and business development. Business models bridge customer and company needs and serve as mediators between technology and economic success by providing a value proposition to customers and a revenue model for companies [52].

An exact description of the business logic of a company and its interaction with the environment is not practicable. *Business model canvases* are particularly advantageous in drafting and summarizing business ideas instead. For the given purpose, it is built on the ideas of Bieger & Reinhold [53].

Figure 11: Business model canvas template [53]

The *business model canvas* summarises key aspects of the creation and proposition of value, distribution, value capture and dissemination and development. Its application shall be strictly human centred; thus the customer / market segment is one of the key fields ([53]). It is elaborated by answering the following questions:

- Key questions about customer segments / market segments: Which customers / market segments are addressed? What value do the addressed customers have to the organisation?

- Key question about the value proposition: What value does an organisation offer to its customers? 'A value proposition is a short, clear, and simple statement of how and on what dimensions a product concept will deliver value to prospective customers. The essence of 'value' is embedded in the trade-off between the benefits a customer receives from a new product and the price a customer pays for it.' [54, p. 465]
- Key questions about value communication and value transfer (*channels*): What groups shall be addressed for what purpose and through which channels? How shall a contact be designed to be perceived valuable from the point of view of the customer in their specific buying cycle?
- Key questions about value creation: What is the role of the organisation within the value chain? How are external resources and capabilities integrated into the value chain? How are transactions in the value chain coordinated?
- Key questions about value capture: Which values are created at which places? How can value be made visible to the customer? How can value be captured as revenue?
- Key questions about value dissemination: What is the value contribution of the different organisations in the value chain? How is the value contribution rewarded in order to assure a sustainable value creation?
- Key questions about value development: How does the organisation grow with the given business model? What is the impact of changes of the business model on organisation's architecture and elements? Are there intrinsic or extrinsic reasons for the organisation to adapt its business model?

Within this work, the *business model canvas* is used in order to identify and describe the relevant aspects of business logic for the TSO grid services.

3.5 Business case calculation approach

To estimate the influence of grid services, operation strategies are defined for different grid services. Based on the defined strategies and historical data, annual electricity costs can be derived. To further evaluate the potential of different grid services in more detail levelised cost of hydrogen (LCOH) assuming the former electricity costs is calculated, basing on a life-cycle cost analysis (LCCA). The LCOH approach is chosen in deviation from the original project description, as it is a more widely applied economic indicator in the hydrogen industry.

4 Business models for TSO grid services

With multiple parties involved, the TSO grid service market has a higher complexity than the DSO grid service market, which typically is organized bilaterally between the reserve providing unit (RPU) and the DSO. ENTSO-E makes efforts to harmonize the European markets, with the effect that most European TSO grid service markets nowadays develop towards similar structures. As the survey conducted in this work has shown, many countries support an aggregator model, where distributed RPUs are summed up in order to build a virtual power plant (VPP). By that the requirements a single RPU has to fulfil, such as the minimum size requirement are achieved.

The following section introduces the ENTSO-E aggregator market model, as it may reasonably be expected to be approached by the far majority of European TSO grid service markets. At the same time that model together with the corresponding guidelines defines a common vocabulary which is widely understood amongst European TSO and DSO representatives.

Further national and market specific details can be found in Chapters 5.8 and 6.2.

4.1 Relationship between relevant actors

Although at the time being the market design for TSO grid services differs between countries, the EU tends to harmonise the market with the recent publication of the Guideline on Electricity Balancing (GLEB) [55] and [5]. Therein the following roles and market participants are defined in particular: the balance responsible party (BRP), the balancing service provider (BSP), the *reserve providing unit*, the *reserve providing group*, the *distribution system operator* (DSO) and the *transmission system operator* (TSO). Figure 12 shows a simplified schematic of how the parties interact in a harmonised balancing market in the TSO-BSP model outlined in the GLEB.

Figure 12: Relations between relevant market participants for the TSO-BSP model according to GLEB

4.1.1 Definition of actors

The TSO-BSP model introduces the following roles of actors, where in practice a single physical actor may cover more than one role:

Reserve providing unit

According to ENTSO-E, a Reserve Providing Unit (RPU) is defined as: “A single or an aggregation of power generating modules and/or demand units connected to a common connection point fulfilling the requirements to provide FCR, FRR or RR.” In this case, an RPU could be a WE, which

passed the prequalification tests and is accepted by the TSO for the provision of specific grid service products.

Reserve providing group

RPU's can be aggregated into a reserve providing group. It is defined by ENTSO-E as: "An aggregation of power generating modules, demand units and/or reserve providing units connected to more than one connection point fulfilling the requirements to provide FCR, FRR or RR."

Balancing service provider

A balancing service provider is a market actor that provides balancing services to its connected or contracted TSO. According to the GLEB, the BSP is defined as a market participant with reserve providing units or reserve providing groups able to provide balancing services to the TSO [5].

Balance responsible party

According to GLEB, the balance responsible party is a market participant or its chosen representative responsible for its imbalances. It is required to pay for the imbalance settlement within its imbalance area (referred to as Market Balance Area in Figure 12) [5].

Transmission system operator

The transmission system operator is a natural or legal person responsible for operating, ensuring the maintenance of and, if necessary, developing the transmission system in a given area and, where applicable, its interconnections with other systems, and for ensuring the long-term ability of the system to meet reasonable demands for the transmission of electricity [56, pp. 55-93].

Distribution system operator

The distribution system operator ensures a safe and reliable operation of the electricity distribution system. Regarding grid services, the DSO can determine the regulatory terms between the RPU and itself [56, pp. 55-93].

4.1.2 Definition of market models

In GLEB, two models are suggested that can govern how balancing services are traded in a harmonized market:

- 1) TSO-BSP model
- 2) TSO-TSO model

TSO-BSP model

According to ENTSO-E, the TSO-BSP model is defined as: "A model for the exchange of balancing capacity or the exchange of balancing energy where the contracting TSO has an agreement with a balancing service provider in another responsibility area or scheduling area when appropriate." According to GLEB, the TSO-BSP model is defined as: "A model for the exchange of balancing services where the balancing service provider provides balancing services directly to the contracting TSO, which then provides these balancing services to the requesting TSO."

TSO-TSO model

ENTSO-E defines this model as: "A model for the exchange of balancing services exclusively by TSOs." GLEB defines it as: "A model for the exchange of balancing services where the balancing service provider provides balancing services to its connecting TSO, which then provides these balancing services to the requesting TSO." Figure 13 displays the market interaction in a TSO-TSO model, as outlined in GLEB.

Figure 13: Relations between relevant market participants for the TSO-TSO model according to GLEB

Relevant for the evaluation of the TSO grid service market potential of WEs is the TSO-TSO model, i.e. the WEs nowadays offer their services either directly or via an aggregator to the national TSO.

4.2 Business logic

This section describes the generic business model principles applicable to TSO grid service markets from an RPU's perspective. The criteria applied base on the business model canvas theory introduced in chapter 3.4. An example of the business logic for a specific case is given in Appendix 10.7.

4.2.1 Customer segment

Large RPUs may directly offer their service to the TSO, whereas 'small'¹² RPUs offer their service to an aggregator. The aggregator bundles multiple RPUs, building a virtual power plant (VPP). The aggregator then offers the grid service of the VPP to the TSO. Thereby it transforms the technical requirements (speed, minimum power rating, availability requirements etc.) as well as procedural requirements (e.g. call and accounting handling) of the TSO to requirements that can be fulfilled more easily by the RPU. For its service, the aggregator claims a share of the earnings. The exact value of the share depends on the bilateral agreement between the aggregator and the RPU.

4.2.2 Value proposition

The value an RPU provides to the TSO grid service markets is frequency containment, frequency restoration and congestion avoidance.¹³ RPUs can offer products with differences in speed and availability requirements, call times, etc. The RPU must be capable to offer both: availability and activation service.

Key requirements for the RPU from a market perspective are long-term reliability, speed and stability of the electrical power consumption. The power level further impacts the economic value an RPU has for the aggregator: the overhead to manage small units may exceed their value. The impact of variable power setting on the total production efficiency and life-time expectation, on the other hand, is a relevant economic factor from the perspective of the RPU.

¹² The assessment as 'small' depends on the TSO's minimum power requirement for direct participation in the market. Example values are 1 MW for FCR and 5 MW for FRR in Germany and Switzerland, or 2 MW for FCR and 5 MW for FRR in Austria [126].

¹³ Congestion management is further considered in chapter 5.8 as provision of congestion management services to TSOs or DSOs can be handled as one case.

4.2.3 Channels

Value communication: The TSO communicates via official publication of rules and regulations, e.g. through its web portal. The possible value communication of the aggregator is diverse, and may include a personal contact between the RPU and the aggregator, or be managed via web.

Value transfer: The TSO typically provides a bidding platform. The possible value transfer of the aggregator can be manifold again, e.g. through a bidding platform, personal contact between the RPU and the aggregator via telephone, email or an online control signal transmitted from the aggregator to the facility of the RPU.

The flexibility provided by the RPU is measured by an electronic power meter, either at the connection point to the grid, or – at least for some countries - inside the facility of the RPU operator. The latter configuration allows the flexibility an RPU provides to be measured independently from other equipment within that same facility. In the case of a WE used as RPU, it also allows to measure stack power independently from the balance of plant (BoP) power consumption, on the condition that stack and BoP power are not correlated [57].

4.2.4 Value creation

Capabilities required from the RPU are the technical performance, which typically needs to be proven in the prequalification process, and a communication infrastructure. E.g., aFRR typically requires a real time bidirectional data link. mFRR and RR may be operated via telephone or email, though several aggregators demand a real time bidirectional data link as well. The RPU's key partners in the grid service business, in addition to its customers, are the energy supplier and the DSO providing the grid connection.

The contracting situation depends on the market model implemented within a country. ENTSO-E has suggested different market models for enabling the participation of demand-side response in the reserves and energy markets [58].

Key requirements for an RPU from an aggregator's point of view are described in Chapter 4.2.2.

4.2.5 Value capture

The value perceived by the customer is given through the technological advantages of the RPU (e.g. speed, availability, rated power, stability and reliability), a reduced dependence of seasonal factors, and an enlarged supply market. The value perceived by the RPU is the profit received from availability and / or activation¹⁴ and therefore, in the case of a WE, the reduction of the H₂ production cost.

Availability of the RPU is remunerated on a base of payment per MW and hour of availability, expressed as € / MW/h. It is not to be confused with the payment for energy delivered, which is expressed as € / MWh.

When the RPU is called to deliver control energy, called *utilisation*, the RPU can either draw energy at a reduced rate in the case of negative control energy (*down regulation*), or receives a compensation for unused but owed energy¹⁵ in the case of positive control energy (*up regulation*). In both cases the economic value of the utilisation case for the RPU based on the difference between the regular energy price and the control energy price.

4.2.6 Value dissemination

The TSO remunerates the RPU via the aggregator for availability and/or activation. The revenue is split between the aggregator and the RPU, where the energy supplier and the Balance Responsible Party (BRP) may be involved as well. The remuneration procedures may differ considerably between countries. As an example, the different remuneration principles in Germany and Switzerland are explained in Appendix 10.9.

¹⁴ Some grid services pay for both, others pay for one only.

¹⁵ The RPU owes such energy to its supplier according to the supply contract.

The aggregator asks for a payment for its services. The share depends on the bilateral agreement between aggregator and RPU and depends on the size and quality of the RPU's flexibility service.

4.2.7 Value development

Market rules are changing in many countries, partly driven by the aim to further increase the market efficiency, partly driven by the harmonization and internationalization efforts of the EU [5]. Examples for market development projects are

- The Trans European Replacement Reserves Exchange (TERRE), which aims at border crossing exchange of Replacement Reserves (RR) [59];
- The Manually Activated Reserves Initiative (MARI), aiming at the introduction of a European mFRR platform [60]; and
- The Platform for the International Coordination of Automated Frequency Restoration and Stable System Operation (PICASSO) aiming at the introduction of an international exchange platform for aFRR [61].

Many countries such as Sweden, Finland, Germany, Netherlands, Switzerland, United Kingdom, Austria, Denmark, Norway and Slovenia, discuss adapting the technical and/or commercial requirements for some of their frequency control products. Plans are e.g. to shorten the minimum duration requirement of a frequency control call or to switch from weekly auctions to daily auctions, making it easier for new technologies to enter the market. Others such as Greece report to discuss the introduction of an aggregator model, and the acceptance of distributed loads as RPUs for at least some of their products [62].

4.3 Interim conclusion

With multiple parties involved, the TSO grid service market is of a certain complexity. However, in most European countries the TSO grid service markets develop towards similar structures, driven by the harmonization efforts of ENTSO-E. As such, many countries support an aggregator model, where distributed RPUs are summed up in order to build a VPP. By that, the requirements a single RPU has to fulfil, such as the minimum size requirement, are reduced, opening the market to WEs to act as RPUs.

Based on ENTSO-E's harmonization efforts, the generic business model principles can be described in a language and by principles that are nowadays broadly understood, easing the market entrance for international participants. In terms of that language, the WE can act as an RPU once being prequalified. Due to limitations such as size of the variable power, the WE operator will typically provide its balancing services as part of a VPP, operated by a BSP. This configuration makes the BSP the most important business partner for the WE operator.

5 Identification of the most attractive grid services

The evaluation of the TSO grid service cases bases on literature, expert interviews and the survey conducted within this project (chapter 3.2, [62]). The quality and amount of data available differs between countries, which makes market evaluation and entrance difficult in some cases. Figure 14 and Figure 15 give an overview of the situation by country.

Figure 14: Status of data gathering

Figure 15: Access to information

As no TSO exists in Malta, this country was excluded from the investigation of TSO grid services. Furthermore, 8 countries (Croatia, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Spain) were excluded from a further analysis, as they do not accept non-rotating masses and/or loads for the provision of TSO grid services. The following countries did not reply to the survey and were therefore also excluded: Italy, France, UK, Belgium, Bulgaria, Spain, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxemburg, Portugal, Romania, and Slovakia. For France, multiple attempts were made to contact the TSO with very active support from French QualyGridS partner CEA, however, without success. There was also no response from the UK. Nevertheless, it was possible to establish a working channel of communication with a TSO employee and to finally collect the data needed for the evaluation.

For the countries that did respond to the survey, together with France and UK (where the surveys were not returned but were investigated further due to their size and importance in the EU), the availability and utilisation prices, as well as contracted and activated volumes were researched. It was necessary to conduct further interviews and email exchanges with survey contacts and TSO experts for accurate interpretation of the retrieved data originating from the surveys or published literature. Further details can be found in Appendix 10.4.

As a result, within the 30 countries (28 EU countries plus Switzerland and Norway) 85 TSO grid services¹⁶ were identified as candidate cases for the application of WEs in the TSO grid service markets.

5.1 Availability prices

Figure 16 shows the set of the average availability prices per country and product for the year 2016. The references for the prices as well as the price details are given in Table 4. In Figure 16,

¹⁶ The list of TSO grid services can be found in Appendix 10.8.

the values for symmetrical products are divided by two, in order to be comparable with asymmetrical products.¹⁷

There are significant price differences among the countries. For example, availability of aFRR- is remunerated in Finland approximately 23 times higher than in Germany. Overall, the most favourable availability prices are exhibited by Finland, Switzerland and Denmark. In 2016 the Swedish TSO, Svenska Kraftnät, despite having FCR and aFRR products only demanded resources from mFRR (a product that is remunerated for utilisation only) [63], hence its absence from Figure 16.

Figure 16: Average availability prices 2016 for FCR, FRR and RR and country specific products [€/MW/h in 2016]. The bubble size corresponds to price. Values for symmetrical products are divided by two in order to be comparable with asymmetrical products. For Ireland, availability prices for FRR, POR, SOR, TOR, TOR2, RR are available but very low (≤ 3 €/MW/h), with products that are not standardized and therefore not shown in the plot. The numeric price data can be found in Table 4.

5.2 Utilisation prices

Figure 17 shows the economic value added (EVA) from utilisation per country and product for the year 2016. The bubble area is proportional to the EVA, where the additional income from activation is compared with a case where the RPU pays the regular electricity price which is assumed to be constant and equal to the average national SPOT base price. The price references and details are also contained in Table 4.

¹⁷ See also the explanation in chapter 2.1.

Figure 17: EVA 2016 from utilisation for TSO grid services. The area size corresponds to the EVA, where blue bubbles represent a positive profit, and white bubbles represent a loss.

Table 4: References for price data. Availability prices for symmetric products are expressed as x/y, where y=½ x the price comparable with asymmetric products.

Country	Product	Availability price [€/MW/h]	Utilisation price [€/MWh]	Reference
Austria ¹⁸	FCR (symmetrical)	14.76 / 7.38	NA	[64], [65]
	aFRR+ (weekly average)	1.12	101.73	
	aFRR- (weekly average)	2.1	-49.61	
	mFRR+ (weekly average)	1.25	171.9	
	mFRR- (weekly average)	1.52	-232.57	
Denmark	FCR+ (DK1, daily)	17.98	NA	[66], [67], [68]
	FCR- (DK1, daily)	1.56	NA	
	FCR-N (DK2, yearly, symmetrical)	25.34 / 12.67	NA	
	FCR-D+ (DK2, yearly)	6.18	NA	
	aFRR+ (DK1, DK2)	90 / 45 ¹⁹	13.4	
	aFRR- (DK1, DK2)	90 / 45 ²⁰	-13.4	
	mFRR+ (DK1)	0.62	37.43	
	mFRR- (DK1)	not traded	10.02	
	mFRR+ (DK2)	not traded	80.16	
mFRR- (DK2)	not traded	19.63		
Germany	FCR (symmetrical)	15.27 / 7.64	-	[69], [65]
	aFRR+	4.25	54.85	
	aFRR-	0.85	17.14	

¹⁸ Weekly averages are time weighted values based on weekly peak and off-peak products.

¹⁹ Course estimate based on January and August Contracts 2016

²⁰ Course estimate based on January and August Contracts 2016

Country	Product	Availability price [€/MWh/h]	Utilisation price [€/MWh]	Reference
	mFRR+	0.98	106.2	
	mFRR-	0.86	78.83	
Finland	FCR-N (yearly, symmetrical)	17.42 / 8.71	77 (up) 22 (down)	[70], [71]
	FCR-N (hourly, symmetrical)	34.7 / 17.36	77 (up) 22 (down)	
	FCR-D+ (yearly)	4.5	NA	
	FCR-D+ (hourly)	30.3	NA	
	aFRR+	23.4	77	
	aFRR-	19.7	22	
	mFRR+	3.6	77	
	mFRR-	not traded	22	
	France	FCR+	9.18	
FCR-		9.18	32.98	
aFRR+		10.04	27.14	
aFRR-		10.04	26.38	
mFRR+		2.37	50.84	
mFRR-		not traded	32.78	
RR+		2.23	47.97	
RR-		not traded	18.50	
Ireland	FRR+	2.06	NA	[74], survey, cross checked with [75] and [76]
	POR+	3.09	NA	
	SOR+	1.87	NA	
	TOR 1+	1.48	NA	
	TOR 2+	1.18	NA	
	RR+ (synchronized)	0.24	NA	
	RR+ (desynchronized)	0.53	NA	
Netherlands	FCR (symmetrical)	14.91 / 7.46	NA	[77], [65]
	aFRR (symmetrical)	12 / 6	55 (up) 16.93 (down)	
	mFRRda+	1.28	147	
	mFRRda-	not traded	-74	
Norway	FCR-N (symmetrical)	3.44 / 1.72	26.41 (up) 22.75 (down)	[78]
	aFRR+	7.05	32.31	
	aFRR-	6.78	29.30	
	mFRR+	1.44	34.39	
	mFRR-	not traded	17.72	
Slovenia	aFRR (symmetrical)	20.89 / 10.44	55.8 (up) 18.6 (down)	[79], [80]
	mFRR+	5.71	173.8	
	mFRR-	4.84	-180	
	RR+	NA	43.9	
	RR-	NA	13	

Country	Product	Availability price [€/MWh/h]	Utilisation price [€/MWh]	Reference		
Sweden ²¹	FCR-N (symmetrical)	25.65 / 12.83	SE1 35.89 (up) 20.01 (down)	[81], [71], [82], [83]		
			SE2 34.06 (up) 20.81 (down)			
			SE3 41.07 (up) 20.78 (down)			
			SE4 66.05 (up) 24.22 (down)			
			FCR-D (symmetrical)		6.21	SE1 35.89 (up) 20.01 (down)
						SE2 34.06 (up) 20.81 (down)
						SE3 41.07 (up) 20.78 (down)
						SE4 66.05 (up) 24.22 (down)
	aFRR+ SE1	18	35.89			
	aFRR- SE1	9.5	20.01			
	aFRR+ SE2	18	34.06			
	aFRR- SE2	9.5	20.81			
	aFRR+ SE3	18	41.07			
	aFRR- SE3	9.5	20.78			
	aFRR+ SE4	18	66.05			
	aFRR- SE4	9.5	24.22			
	mFRR+ SE1	NA	35.89			
	mFRR- SE1	NA	20.01			
	mFRR+ SE2	NA	34.06			
	mFRR- SE2	NA	20.81			
	mFRR+ SE3	NA	41.07			
mFRR- SE3	NA	20.78				
mFRR+ SE4	NA	66.05				
mFRR- SE4	NA	24.22				

²¹ Only mFRR is currently demanded by Swedish TSO, hence Swedish aFRR and FCR are not included in the price comparison shown in Figure 16 and Figure 17 and MCE.

Country	Product	Availability price [€/MWh/h]	Utilisation price [€/MWh]	Reference
Switzerland	FCR (symmetrical)	14.63 / 7.32	NA	[65], [84], [85]
	aFRR (symmetrical)	37.65 / 18.82	50.82 (up) 28.91 (down)	
	mFRR+ (weekly)	2.38	73.07	
	mFRR- (weekly)	4.03	-65.05	
United Kingdom	FFR (symmetrical) (FCR)	4.03 / 2.02	NA	[16], [86], [87]
	Fast Reserve+ (mFRR+)	5.3	2.77	
	DTU- (RR-)	1.8	73.08	
	STOR flex+ (RR+)	1.07	132.09	

5.3 Future H₂ market potential

Zubaryeva and Thiel evaluate the geographic differences of the European hydrogen markets for mobility applications for the years 2030 and 2050 [88]. Based on a literature research, the authors selected eight demographic, economic, political and social key drivers for the development of the hydrogen markets. They did a multi-criteria evaluation, in which the key drivers were weighted based on the opinion from eight experts. The MCE contains data for each factor in the period from 1990 to 2050 for the EU27 and NUTS2 regions. Historical data was extrapolated, considering regional differences. The result of the work is considered in Table 5 and assigned to the three coarse categories of low, medium and high potential. Empty cells indicate unavailable data. The evaluation of the potential for the mobility markets in the United Kingdom and Denmark are compatible with the evaluation by the FCH JU project CertifHy, which looks at mobility data for Germany, France, United Kingdom and Scandinavia. [40, pp. 21-26] These authors base their estimates on projections of the car fleet size and literature, which by 2025 predict a hydrogen consumption for mobility applications of:

- 60'000 t in Germany (0.69 kg per capita @ 86.6 Mio inhabitants),
- 22'000 t in France (0.31 kg per capita @ 71 Mio inhabitants),
- 30'600 t in the United Kingdom (1.78 kg per capita @ 17.2 Mio inhabitants),
- 27'000 t in Denmark (4.5 kg per capita @ 6 Mio inhabitants).

In this study, the expected hydrogen production per capita in Germany is clearly smaller compared to the United Kingdom and Denmark, though in absolute figures the German market would be leading.

Table 5: Country specific differences in the H₂ market outlook 2028, with indication of low, medium and high potential

Country	Mobility ²²	PtG
Austria	high	low
Denmark	high	
Germany	high	high
Finland	medium	
France	medium	
Ireland	low	high
Netherlands	medium	

²² Data bases on [88], where the following mapping is applied:
 high: lead market score 2030 > 0.4,
 medium: 0.4 >= lead market score 2030 > 0.2,
 low: 0.2 >= lead market score 2030.

Country	Mobility ²²	PtG
Norway		low
Slovenia	low	
Sweden	high	low
Switzerland		low
United Kingdom	high	high

Demand for stationary storage differs significantly between countries according to different electricity generation profiles. Large reservoir hydro capacity for example such as in Sweden is a carbon-free option to integrate intermittent renewables and eliminate the need for further storage [89, p. 36]. Exchange capacities also play an important role for the amount of storage that could be deployed economically in a system, as the demand for storage generally decreases with better exchange capacity. Islands or markets that miss exchange capacity could require storage, driven by curtailment of intermittent renewables and very high fossil generation cost. Depending on the island characteristics, there may be economic demand for storage reaching tens of percent of installed power generation capacity. As such:

Germany has currently about 7000 MW installed pumped hydro capacity and is expected to grow to 11'000 MW time-shift capacity by 2030 [89, p. 27]. Due to location and environmental constraints, only part of that increase will be covered by pumped hydro storage, creating opportunities for other storage technologies such as PtG within 10 years.

Sweden, Norway, Switzerland: Sweden and Norway have many conventional storage hydropower plants and can use those to balance their renewables portfolio. Even for projected high-RES scenarios in 2028, this will not change [89, p. 36]. Switzerland has a large amount of pumped hydro storage and likely, does also not need additional storage to balance growing intermittent renewables [90].

Crete (Greece), UK, Ireland: Crete already curtails approximately 44 GWh (about 1.5% of total electricity demand 2013) of wind energy. The curtailment occurs as a result of transport and distribution, and system stability constraints. Back-up generation capacity consists mostly of heavy fuel oil and diesel-powered units. Crete represents an example of an island system where demand for storage such as PtG is already existent and could be economically interesting. Model calculations suggest that 60 MW would be an economic amount of storage currently. This amount of storage would integrate about 25 GWh of excess energy into the system. Similar dynamics could be observed in other islands within the EU or island member states such as UK or Ireland [89, p. 38].

5.4 Ranking for scenario 1) *availability only*

Scenario 1), as defined in chapter 3.3, favours a high annual availability time mode of operation for the WE, accompanied with a low overall annual utilisation time i.e. where the remuneration from utilisation is minor. This may be the typical situation for operating the WE at its nominal power rating with maximum efficiency for as long as possible.

Based on the MCE procedure described in chapter 3.1, the top ten ranking products of each group: *asymmetrical negative*, *asymmetrical positive* and *symmetrical* are shown in Table 6. The complete list can be found in Appendix 10.8.

Table 6: Top ranks for scenario 1). The complete list can be found in Appendix 10.8.

Scenario 1): ignored activation								
Asymmetric negativ			Asymmetric positiv			Symmetric only		
Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score
1	Germany mFRR-	7.5	1	Germany aFRR+	7.6	1	Germany FCR (symmetric)	7.6
2	Germany aFRR-	7.5	2	Germany mFRR+	7.5	2	UK FFR (symmetric)	6.4
3	UK RR-	6.4	3	UK RR+	6.4	3	Finland FCR-N (hourly, symmetric)	5.3
4	Finland aFRR-	5.3	4	Finland FCR-D+ (hourly)	5.5	4	Netherlands FCR (symmetric)	5.2
5	Netherlands aFRR-	5.2	5	Finland aFRR+	5.4	5	Finland FCR-N (yearly, symmetric)	5.1
6	Netherlands mFRRda-	5.1	6	Netherlands aFRR+ (symmetric)	5.2	6	Austria FCR (symmetric)	5.0
7	Denmark FCR- (DK1, daily)	5.0	7	Netherlands mFRRda+	5.1	7	Denmark aFRR (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	4.9
8	Austria aFRR- (weekly average)	4.9	8	Finland FCR-D+ (yearly)	5.0	8	Norway FCR-N (symmetric)	4.9
9	Austria mFRR- (weekly average)	4.9	9	Finland mFRR+	5.0	9	Denmark FCR-N (DK2, yearly, symmetric)	4.3
10	Denmark aFRR- (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	4.9	10	Austria mFRR+ (weekly average)	4.9	10	Switzerland aFRR (symmetric)	3.9

While the products from Finland possess the best economic value added from grids service provision, the product scores belonging to the UK and Germany are boosted by a more optimistic hydrogen market perspective within the next ten years, thus contributing to their overall higher scores.

For symmetrical operation, where the WE can equally increase or decrease its electrical power, Germany's FCR product clearly leads, followed by the UK's FCR ('FFR'). The first non-FCR symmetric product is Denmark's aFRR ranked seventh.

Asymmetrical positive operation means the WE decreases its electric power consumption on demand of the TSO. Here the best result is obtained by Germany's aFRR+ product, closely followed by the its mFRR+ product. Ranked third is the UK's RR+ product.

Asymmetric negative operation means the WE increases its electric power consumption on demand of the TSO, from standby mode or from a power level below the maximum rating. Here, the German products mFRR- and aFRR- top of the list with virtually equal scores, followed by the UK's RR- product.

From the products listed in Table 6, FCR typically is the most demanding with regard to reaction time. There are few asymmetric FCR products on the market, such as the hourly and yearly FCR-D+ in Finland, the yearly FCR-D+ in Denmark East and FCR+ and FCR- in Denmark West.

5.5 Ranking for scenario 2) availability plus activation

Scenario 2) additionally considers the remuneration from the activation of the grid services, for those products with data available.²³ For products with unknown call probabilities, the additional income is ignored. All the products of each group: *asymmetrical negative*, *asymmetrical positive* and *symmetrical* are shown in Table 7.

²³ The remuneration from availability is evaluated based on an economic value added (EVA) consideration, where the additional income from activation is compared with a case where the electricity price is assumed to be constant and equal to the average national SPOT base price for the year 2016.

Table 7: Complete ranks for scenario 2). *blh* = black horse; *blh*->*x* indicates the improved ranking under scenario 3, where products with unknown activation probability are assumed to have an activation probability equal to the maximum value known for the other products – 23%. (see Chapter 5.6).

Scenario 2): activation + availability								
Asymmetric negativ			Asymmetric positiv			Symmetric only		
Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score
1	Germany aFRR-	7.5	1	Germany aFRR+	7.6	1	Germany FCR (symmetric)	7.6
2	Germany mFRR-	7.5	2	Germany mFRR+	7.5	2	UK FFR (symmetric)	6.4
3	UK RR-	6.4	3	UK RR+	6.4	3	Finland FCR-N (hourly, symmetric)	5.3
4	Finland aFRR-	5.3	4	Finland FCR-D (hourly)+	5.5	4	Netherlands FCR (symmetric)	5.2
5	Sweden mFRR- SE1	5.3	5, blh ->4	Finland aFRR+	5.4	5, blh ->4	Finland FCR-N (yearly, symmetric)	5.1
6	Sweden mFRR- SE2	5.3	6	Sweden mFRR+ (SE1)	5.3	6	Austria FCR (symmetric)	5.0
7	Sweden mFRR- SE3	5.3	7	Sweden mFRR+ (SE2)	5.3	7	Denmark aFRR (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	4.9
8	Sweden mFRR- SE4	5.3	8	Sweden mFRR+ (SE3)	5.3	8	Denmark FCR-N (yearly, DK2, symmetric)	4.3
9	Netherlands aFRR- (symmetrical)	5.2	9, blh ->7	Sweden mFRR+ (SE4)	5.3	9	Norway FCR-N (symmetric)	4.0
10	Netherlands mFRR-	5.1	10	Netherlands aFRR+	5.2	10, blh ->9	Switzerland aFRR (symmetric)	3.9
11	Finland mFRR-	5.0	11	Netherlands mFRRda+	5.1	11	Switzerland FCR (symmetric)	3.6
12	Norway aFRR-	5.0	12	Finland FCR-D (yearly)+	5.0	12	France aFRR (symmetric)	2.3
13, blh ->10	Austria aFRR- (weekly average)	4.9	13, blh ->12	Finland mFRR+	5.0			
14, blh ->4	Austria mFRR- (weekly average)	4.9	14	Norway aFRR+	5.0			
	Denmark aFRR- (DK1 & DK2) (symmetrical)	4.9	15, blh ->5	Austria mFRR+ (weekly average)	4.9			
16, blh ->15	Norway mFRR-	4.8	16, blh ->11	Austria aFRR+ (weekly average)	4.9			
	Denmark FCR- (DK1, daily)	4.1	17	Denmark aFRR+ (symmetric)	4.9			
18, blh ->17	Denmark mFRR- (DK2)	4.1	18	Norway mFRR+	4.9			
19	Switzerland aFRR- (symmetrical)	3.9	19	Denmark FCR+ (DK1, daily)	4.4			
20	Slovenia mFRR-	3.7	20	Denmark FCR-D+ (DK2, yearly)	4.2			
21	Switzerland mFRR- (Weekly)	3.7	21	Denmark mFRR+ (DK1)	4.1			
22, blh ->20	Slovenia RR-	3.6	22	Switzerland aFRR+ (symmetric)	3.9			
23	France aFRR- (symmetrical)	2.3	23	Slovenia mFRR+	3.7			
24			24	Slovenia RR+	3.6			
25			25	Switzerland mFRR+ (weekly)	3.6			
26			26	France aFRR+ (symmetric)	2.3			
27			27	France mFRR+	2.1			
			28	France RR+	2.1			

Again, the products from Germany possess the best economic value added from the grid service provision. As before, the German products profit from a more optimistic hydrogen market perspective within the next ten years. Hence, the products from this country lead the scores again.

Comparing the results of scenario 1) (Table 6) with scenario 2) (Table 7), it can be seen that for at least the first three ranks in each category, there are only minor differences. In the category *asymmetrical negative*, the German aFRR and mFRR products swap places, with virtually equal scores.

5.6 Ranking for scenario 3) black horse

Some of the products in Table 7 have no call probabilities due to unavailable data. In reality however, an additional income from activation can be expected. The impact on the MCE results is tested with a *black horse* approach as defined by scenario 3): for each product with unknown activation probability, it is assumed that the activation probability equals the maximum value known from the other products, which is 23%. The result of that simulation is indicated in Table 7 as “*blh* -> *x*”, where *blh* stands for *black horse*, and *x* is the improved rank the product achieved in the simulation.²⁴ The ranking shows the greatest impact can be observed in the asymmetric positive and negative products with Austria’s mFRR+ and mFRR- jumping 10 spots to fifth and fourth ranks respectively, displacing Finnish products in both cases.

The Austrian mFRR+ and mFRR- products used in the simulation are in fact time weighted averages based on the following price levels:

- mFRR+/- (Peak; Mo-Fr, 8-20: 60h/week),
- mFRR+/- (Off-Peak; Mo-Fr, 20-24,0-8: 60h/week),
- mFRR+/- (Sa+So Peak; Sa/Su, 8-20: 24h/week), and
- mFRR+ (Sa+So Off-Peak; Sa/Su, 20-24,0-8: 24h/week).

²⁴ For better readability, only rank improvements are given in Table 7.

5.7 Ranking for scenario 4) ignored future H₂ market potential

For the evaluation, in which the future H₂ market potential is not taken into consideration, the Finnish FCR-N hourly closely trails German FCR top scorer. For both asymmetrical positive and negative products, the Norwegian aFRR and mFRR products lead. Further details can be found in Appendix 10.8.

Table 8: Ranked grid service products for scenario 4) (remuneration from availability plus activation; criterion 'Future H₂ market potential' excluded)

Scenario 4): activation + availability, without H2 criterion											
Asymmetrical negativ							Asymmetrical positiv			Symmetrical only	
Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score
1	Norway aFRR-	5.0	1	Norway aFRR+	5.0	1	Germany FCR (symmetric)	4.7			
2	Norway mFRR-	4.8	2	Norway mFRR+	4.9	2	Finland FCR-N (hourly, symmetric)	4.5			
3	Germany aFRR-	4.7	3	Finland FCR-D (hourly)+	4.8	3	Netherlands FCR (symmetric)	4.5			
4	Germany mFRR-	4.6	4	Germany aFRR+	4.7	4	Finland FCR-N (yearly, symmetric)	4.4			
5	Finland aFRR-	4.6	5	Finland aFRR+	4.7	5	Norway FCR-N (symmetric)	4.0			
6	Netherlands aFRR- (symmetrical)	4.4	6	Germany mFRR+	4.6	6	Switzerland aFRR (symmetric)	3.9			
7	Netherlands mFRR-	4.3	7	Netherlands aFRR+ (symmetric)	4.4	7	Switzerland FCR (symmetric)	3.6			
8	Finland mFRR-	4.3	8	Netherlands mFRRda+	4.4	8	Austria FCR (symmetric)	3.6			
9	Switzerland aFRR- (symmetrical)	3.9	9	Finland FCR-D (Yearly)+	4.3	9	UK FFR (symmetric)	3.5			
10	Sweden mFRR- SE1	3.8	10	Finland mFRR+	4.3	10	Denmark aFRR (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	3.5			

5.8 Combining congestion management with WE applications

An example of CM in Germany points to a potential demand for such grid services, where a considerable amount of renewable energy is lost due to congestion issues (*feed-in management* in Figure 18). Figure 18 exhibits how relevant Germany's congestion energy is, reaching approximately 15 TWh p.a. [91], which is about seven times the amount of activated aFRR (2.1 TWh) in 2016. 93% of all redispatching hours were caused by grid elements where the overload lasted longer than 12 hours [92]. The main reasons for line overloading are the integration of more fluctuating renewable energy, delayed grid reinforcement, high minimum production of conventional power plants (must-run) and the integrated European market, which enable cross-border electricity flows between countries without considering the physical limits of the grid [91]. In Germany, measures for congestion management are differentiated as follows [91]:

1. **Redispatch:** Reduction and increase of the power input of conventional power plants by contractual agreement or a legal obligation with the grid operator with replacement of the costs.
2. **Feed-in management (EinsMan):** Derating/Curtailment of power input from renewable energy and CHP plants at the request of the grid operator with compensation. The legislator allows feed-in management only in cases where redispatching possibilities are exhausted.
3. **Adaptation measures:** Adjustments of electricity supply and/or electricity demand at the request of the grid operator if other measures are insufficient, without compensation.

Figure 18: Development of congestion management measures in Germany from 2015 until 2017. Curtailment (feed-in management) peaked in 2017; own representation with data from [93]

In 2017, the sum of curtailed work done by EEG²⁵ and CHP plants amounted approximately to 5'518 GWh (2016: 3'743 GWh) and reached so far its highest level [94, p. 27]. Figure 19 shows the rise in onshore wind and solar share of curtailment measures in Germany. It is clear that onshore wind energy is highly affected by curtailment whereas the solar share is small and is thus hardly affected. Looking to the future, with curtailment shown to rise, congestion management is also expected to rise causing a higher frequency in line overloading. Figure 20 illustrates the expected increase in RES curtailment over a decade owing to increasing RES feed-in. The transmission grid RES curtailment is anticipated to increase from 0.5TWh (2014) to 0.9TWh (2024) and could potentially rise to 9.8TWh (2024) in the event of delayed grid expansion [6]. [6] investigates the 10 best locations for CM which are all situated in Eastern Germany. In 2014, the full load hours necessary for congestion management from those locations ranged between 80-447 hours and is anticipated to range between 70-729 hours in 2024 and when factoring in delayed grid expansion these hours could inflate to more than 2'000.

Figure 19: Onshore wind and solar share of curtailment causes in Germany [61]

²⁵ EEG is short for the German renewable energy sources act

Figure 20: Frequency of (n-1) loading (top) causing curtailment (bottom) for 2014 and 2024 [6].

These figures make the case for congestion management, the grid services WEs could provide and their greater relevancy. According to [95] three scenarios can be considered for storage systems providing congestion management. Adapted to WE technology, it theoretically will either be an independent hydrogen producer, one or several wind turbine owners or the grid operator who manages the WE. In the case of an independent hydrogen producer, hydrogen production will be managed to maximize its profit. Therefore, when the electricity price is low, the producer will increase its hydrogen production. In the case of wind turbine owners managing the WE, the wind turbine owner would produce hydrogen during times when wind energy production would otherwise be curtailed. Finally, the use of a water electrolyser by the grid operator is linked to an economic weighting between the congestion cost, life cycle cost for grid reinforcement and life cycle cost of sustainable hydrogen production.

When looking at feasible business cases nowadays, it must be considered that RES from Germany and probably other countries benefit from fixed feed-in tariffs and compensation in the case of curtailment. However, compensation might be lost in case of the application of a WE for congestion management. On the transmission level, it is rather unsure that the TSO will accept an additional profit is made from hydrogen production. On the distribution level, no consistent rules exist for remuneration and only local markets would be possible. The grid operator on the other hand, has little commercial motivation since congestion management is a socialised cost passed on to end users via surcharges. For all these reasons, there is no existing case known where the curtailed energy is used for other business [96]. Thus, the application of WEs for congestion management for the time being is a somewhat hypothetical case but is being investigated [6], where the overall economic situation has to be considered instead of the interests of individual players.

5.9 Interim conclusion

The TSO grid service markets in the EU differ among countries with regard to price levels, market rules and market transparency. Average remuneration of availability for FCR, as an example, ranges from 3.4 €/MW/h in Norway (FCR-N) to 34.7 €/MW and hour in Finland (FCR-N hourly). Similar spreads can be seen with the other products. The harmonisation and internationalisation effort of the EU might, in the long term, lead to a reduced spread.

Due to the different levels of data availability, scenarios were introduced to enable a better basis for evaluation and ranking of the grid services. As a result, four scenarios, including the sensitivity considerations, were chosen describing comparable offering strategies for TSO grid services for each of the product categories: symmetrical and asymmetrical positive and negative in addition to a heuristically selected DSO case, as shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Scenarios and product categories, together with the first three ranking products for each field, with scores in brackets. Products underlined are selected for a more detailed evaluation. The complete rankings can be found in Appendix 10.8.

Product category	Symmetric	Asymmetric, positive	Asymmetric, negative
Scenario			
Scenario 1) <i>availability only</i>	<u>Germany FCR</u> (7.6) UK FFR (6.4) Finland FCR-N hourly (5.3)	<u>Germany aFRR+</u> (7.6) <u>Germany mFRR+</u> (7.5) UK RR+ (6.4)	<u>Germany mFRR-</u> (7.5) <u>Germany aFRR-</u> (7.5) UK RR- (6.4)
Scenario 2) <i>availability plus activation</i>	<u>Germany FCR</u> (7.6) UK FFR (6.4) Finland FCR-N hourly (5.3)	<u>Germany aFRR+</u> (7.6) <u>Germany mFRR+</u> (7.5) UK RR+ (6.4)	<u>Germany aFRR-</u> (7.5) <u>Germany mFRR-</u> (7.5) UK RR- (6.4)
Scenario 3) <i>black horse</i>	<u>Germany FCR</u> (7.7) UK FFR (6.5) Finland FCR-N hourly (5.8)	<u>Germany aFRR+</u> (7.6) <u>Germany mFRR+</u> (7.5) UK RR+ (6.7)	<u>Germany aFRR-</u> (7.5) <u>Germany mFRR-</u> (7.5) UK RR- (6.4)
Scenario 4) <i>availability plus activation, future H₂ market potential ignored</i>	<u>Germany FCR</u> (4.7) Finland FCR-N hourly (4.5) Netherlands FCR (4.5)	Norway aFRR+ (5.0) <u>Norway mFRR+</u> (4.9) Finland FCR-D (hourly)+ (4.8)	Norway aFRR- (5.0) <u>Norway mFRR-</u> (4.8) <u>Germany aFRR-</u> (4.7)
DSO/BRP/P2P grid service	<u>Congestion management for wind farms</u> (heuristically selected)		

Each product category affects the operation strategy of the WE, hence at least one member of each category is selected for further evaluation in WP6.2. Moreover, it is of interest to compare symmetric, asymmetric positive and negative products within one country, this is evidently Germany given how German FCR and FRR products align rather well with ENTSO-E recommendations [97] - at least up to a certain level of detail. Therefore, from the perspective of

the ongoing harmonisation efforts of the ENTSO-E, Germany is a reasonable choice for further analysis.

Finally, it is also of interest to compare the rules between two different countries, therefore Norway is selected as a second country given its high activation prices compared with Germany, which as a result may alter the operation plans for the WE.

6 Evaluation of the most attractive grid services

In this chapter, the most attractive grid services are evaluated in a more quantitative way. The main goal of doing so is to compare the different DSO and TSO grid services in more detailed. Therefore, the levelised cost of hydrogen (LCOH) at the WE outlet is calculated. As a base case, it is assumed that a WE-operator minimizes its electricity costs only at the day ahead power market. As a next step, the influence of different grid services on the WE-operator's strategy gets examined, so that electricity costs with grid services can be computed. This allows for a comparison of the LCOH resulting from different grid services with that of the base case (no grid service).

As described in Section 2.7, the two business case categories A and C are restricted with regard to daily production. We assume a daily production of 22 hours at nominal power for category A (industry with limited constant H₂ demand) and 12 hours at nominal power for category C (distributed refuelling stations), which results in 8030 (category A) and 4380 full-load hours (category C), respectively. Hence, today's profitable WE business-cases are characterized by a more or less stable hydrogen demand over the course of a few hours or few days. This restriction is considered in the following evaluation.

The calculation for the base-case as well as all grid-service cases are based on historical data of the years 2016 and 2017.

6.1 Business case calculations (LCOH)

For Germany, no EEG surcharge is considered. The costs for water are assumed to be 0.03 € per kg hydrogen [98]. Further assumptions for the Alkaline as well as PEM-WEs are based on [99] and depicted in Table 10.

Table 10: Basic assumptions

	ALK	PEM
Nominal Power	1MW	
Maximal Power	1MW	
Maximal Power (Positive Sensitivity)	1MW	2MW
Power Consumption	58 kWh _e /kg	63 kWh _e /kg
Lifetime - System	20 Years	
Stack - Lifetime	80'000 h	40'000 h
Degradation	not considered	
CAPEX - System	1'200€/kW	1'500€/kW
CAPEX - Stack replacement	420 €/kW	525 €/kW
OPEX	4%/CAPEX	
Weighted average cost of capital (WACC)	8%	

The costs for electricity are calculated according the assumptions and methodology described in chapters 6.3.1 and 6.4.1. These assumptions are implemented in a discounted cash flow model. In order to avoid unrealistic price jumps between different full load hour scenarios, stack-replacement costs are calculated as annuity costs²⁶. Based on the annuity payment equation and

²⁶ This corresponds to the amount the WE-operator has to spend every year in order to keep the stack in new-condition.

the present value of constant perpetuity, the annual payment due to stack replacement of a fictional WE with infinite operation years can be calculated as:

Present value of constant perpetuity:

$$PV = \frac{S_c}{r} \quad \text{Eq. 1} \quad [100]$$

$$PV = \frac{S_c}{(1+WACC)^k - 1} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$\text{Where: } k = \frac{S_r}{flh} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Annuity Payment:

$$\text{Annuity Payment} = PV \cdot \frac{WACC}{1 - (1+WACC)^{-n}} \quad \text{Eq. 4} \quad [101]$$

if $n \rightarrow \infty$

$$\text{Annuity Payment} = PV \cdot WACC \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

$$\text{Annuity Payment} = \frac{S_c}{(1+WACC)^{\frac{S_r}{flh}} - 1} \cdot WACC \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

- k =replacement period in years
- $WACC$ =Weighted Average Cost of Capital
- r =interest of stack replacement period
- PV =Present value of stack replacements over n years (Euro)
- S_c =Stack replacement costs (Euro)
- S_r =Replacement rate (hours)
- flh =Full-Load-Hours a year (hours)
- n =years of annuity

In order to evaluate the impact of grid-services, the LCOH at the stage of the WE-outlet is calculated²⁷. By forming the difference of the LCOH derived from the base-case (optimal scheduling without grid services) and cases with grid services, the cost reduction due to the grid services can be expressed as savings on LCOH, where LCOH is defined by:

$$LCOH = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^n \frac{C_t}{(1+WACC)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^n \frac{H_t}{(1+WACC)^t}} \quad \text{Eq. 7} \quad [101]$$

- $WACC$ =Weighted Average Cost of Capital
- C_t =Costs in year t (Euro)
- H_t =Hydrogen production in year t

6.1.1 Grid-fees and additional energy-depended surcharges

6.1.1.1 Germany

To finance the feed-in-tariffs of renewables, Germany has introduced a surcharge for energy consumption, the so-called EEG-surcharge. In 2018, this surcharge equated to 67.9 €/MWh [93]. According to [98] and [102] it cannot be avoided for WE business cases today. However, according to [103], the today's political discussion suggests that, in the medium-term, this surcharge will

²⁷ The ancillary and storage systems are neglected.

either be massively reduced or it may vanish completely for certain WE use cases, such as hydrogen refuelling stations. For that reason, and because EEG surcharges at this level would prevent any attractive business case in Germany, the EEG surcharges are neglected for the further business case analysis.

6.1.1.2 Norway

In order to foster additional renewable energy production, a Norwegian-Swedish certification scheme has been introduced, obliging electricity suppliers to purchase them. As concluded from pilot projects however, in certain configurations, the electricity price is neither affected by the certificates nor by the grid tariffs [104]. Furthermore, as for 2013, electricity consumption has been taxed with 13.8 €/MWh in Norway. However, energy intense industries enjoy tax privileges and certain process- and product-based exemptions, including electrolysis, are exempted from tax [105]. Hence, no additional energy-depending costs are assumed.

6.1.2 Base case

In the base case scenario, the WE-operator is assumed to minimise the electricity cost without making use of the option to offer grid-service-products. The lowest electricity costs are achieved when the WE operates at nominal power during the hours with the lowest electricity prices. It is further assumed, that the WE operator purchases electricity at the day-ahead-spot-market. In order to calculate the electricity costs, historical hourly day-ahead-prices of the years 2016 and 2017 were used. These prices are available at EPEX SPOT SE [106] and Nord Pool AS [107] for Germany and Norway, respectively. In Norway's case, different bidding zones exist. In order to further minimise the electricity costs, it was assumed, that the WE is located within the bidding zone with the lowest average price, which is NO 4 (Tromsø). The average price in this region in 2016 and 2017 was 25.39 €/MWh, whereas the average price in Germany was with 31.58 €/MWh about 6 €/MWh higher. The price-duration-curves (prices ordered in descending order) in Figure 21 indicate a higher price variation in Germany than NO4. This fact has to be considered for business cases that are characterised by few full load hours (see section 6.3.2).

Figure 21: Price-duration-curve of 2016 and 2017

6.2 Grid services overview

In the following section, relevant flexibility markets are being examined. Furthermore, the TSO and DSO grid services being analysed are described in more detail.

6.2.1 Flexibility market and relevant grid service products in Germany

Figure 22 gives an overview of the current German flexibility market design, based on [108]. For CM the DSOs directly enter bilateral agreements with RPUs. Furthermore, the German TSOs or the Netzregelverbund procure flexibility services for CM as well as other grid service products. The Netzregelverbund is a cooperation of the four German TSOs, which optimizes the procurement of

frequency control reserves and activations. The demand for frequency control services is further reduced by netting the demand within the International Grid Control Cooperation IGCC.

The current design doesn't generally support sharing the same flexibility between different markets. As such, for any time slot and amount of flexibility, the operator of the RPU has to explicitly choose whether he offers CM or frequency control services.

RPU: Reserve providing unit
 DSO: Distribution system operator
 TSO: Transmission system operator
 aFRR: automatic frequency Restoration reserve
 IGCC: International Grid Control Cooperation

Figure 22: German flexibility market design.

In Chapter 5.9, the following German TSO grid service products were identified as promising products for WEs: aFRR, mFRR and FCR. The following peculiarities have to be considered when offering these services to the German TSOs:

- **aFRR:** Availability is payed as bid. If a tenderer²⁸ gets called for availability, he can, as a next stage, offer utilisation, which is payed as bid, too. This mechanism is expected to change in the near future towards two independent pay-as-bid auctions [62]. Today, there are two weekly products, an off-peak and a peak product [93]. In 2019, these products are expected to be replaced with daily 4-hour products [62].
- **mFRR:** The availability and utilisation are as well payed as bid. This mechanism is also expected to change towards two independent pay-as-bid auctions for availability and utilisation offers in the near future [62]. The products are characterised by a contract duration of 4 hours [93].
- **FCR:** The availability is payed as bid and traded as a weekly product. This product is expected to be replaced by either 24-hour or 4-hour products in the near future [62]. FCR is a symmetrical product, for which only the availability is compensated. According to [62], there is a possibility that the FCR is split into two asymmetric products. However, this is unlikely to happen in the next few years (probability is less than 50%). The maximum time-period for which FCR is utilised is 30 minutes [62].

6.2.2 Flexibility market and mFRR in Norway

In Norway the TSO is tasked with the responsibility of ensuring sufficient grid flexibility is available in the power system. Today hydropower with reservoirs and large end-users are the RPUs providing the main source of Norway's flexibility which is procured by the TSO on the day-ahead,

²⁸ A tenderer in this refers to a Balancing Service Provider (BSP) that tenders grid service products to a TSO

intraday and balancing markets as well as via other arrangements. The Nordic day-ahead market is coupled with the rest of Europe, whilst the intraday market operates in the Nordic region, Baltic region, Germany and the United Kingdom. Both markets are hosted by the Nordic Power Exchange, Nord Pool, whereas the balancing market is run by the TSO.

On the local grid level DSO's can purchase demand flexibility by means of interruptible load tariffs. Figure 23 illustrates the buyers and sellers of flexibility in Norway's flexibility market. Changes towards an integrated flexibility marketplace are anticipated [109]. This would enable DSOs that currently do not have a marketplace to purchase local flexibility and manage congestion and other grid issues through flexibility trading on the local level.

Figure 23 Norwegian flexibility market design.

In Norway mFRR is called Tertiærreserver. In the Nordic power supply system, the mFRR utilisation is published by Nordpool, a common market place for energy trades. Nordpool refers to it as Regulating Power, while within the Norwegian TSO Statnett it's called Regulerkraftmarkedet (RK). As for availability (Regulerkraftopsjonsmarkedet, RKOM), data is published by Statnett [110].

Availability and utilisation are paid-as-cleared. There are two weekly availability products, an off-peak (12 pm – 6 am) and a peak (6 am – 12 pm) product. In the next five years, these products are expected to be replaced by daily products. Apart from the weekly products, availability is also traded as seasonal products. Until 2018, availability auctions existed only for positive products (mFRR+), while for utilisation, positive as well as negative products exist. It is expected that in the next five years also a market for mFRR- availability will be introduced [62].

Furthermore, RKOM is split into RKOM-H and RKOM-B, where RKOM-H is characterised by stricter requirements regarding activation duration and flexibility [111].

6.3 TSO grid services

The following section describes how the economic influence of TSO grid services on WE-business cases is evaluated. In Chapter 6.3.2 results from the evaluation are presented and discussed.

6.3.1 Combining selected TSO grid services with WE applications

As described in section 2.7, the two business-case-categories A and C are restricted with regard to daily production. As mentioned before, a daily production of 22 hours at nominal power is assumed for category A (industry with limited constant H₂ demand) and 12 hours at nominal power for category C (distributed refuelling stations), which results in 8030 (category A) and 4380 full-load hours (category C), respectively. Hence, today's profitable WE business-cases are characterised by a more or less stable hydrogen demand over the course of a few hours or few days.

The impact of the grid service business for these two application categories is evaluated by considering the following cases:

- A base case in which the WE is operated without participation in the grid service business
- Offering asymmetric power reserve products, and
- Offering a symmetric FCR product.

Changes in CAPEX and WE efficiency due to part- and over load resulting from the grid services are neglected. However, more detailed simulations in WP 6.3 and 6.4 will take these effects into account. The calculation for the base-case as well as all grid-service cases are based on historical data of the years 2016 and 2017. The following sections detail the conditions under which the respective calculations are based.

6.3.1.1 Asymmetric power reserve products (aFRR, mFRR)

It was assumed that aFRR as well as mFRR can be offered quarter-hourly, and the WE operator offers positive and negative products during the operation time and stand-by time, respectively.

- Positive control reserve products: The WE operator is compensated by an availability price for offering the flexibility to lower/switch-off the load during operation at nominal power.
- Negative control reserve products: The WE operator is compensated by the availability price for offering the flexibility to switch-on the load while the WE is in stand-by operation. The stand-by power consumption is neglected in this analysis.

The revenue from the grid services are subtracted from the electricity costs such that they lower the electricity costs. The impact of these grid service products on the electricity costs and the operation time is shown graphically in Figure 24. The figure shows the sorted day-ahead prices of one day (in ascending order). The red hatched area represents the base case for which the WE does not profit from reduced energy costs due to the compensation for its availability and utilisation offerings. Positive power reserve products are offered for the hours scheduled for operating at nominal power. For those hours, the electricity costs are reduced by the availability price ($P_{\text{Availability}}$).

For the positive utilisation that is called, the costs are further decreased by a utilisation compensation. However, the positive utilisation reduces the operational time and as a result, lowers the hydrogen production accordingly. The actual net cost for electricity corresponds to the blue hatched area in Figure 24.

The negative products affect the net cost analogous to the positive products. However, a BSP usually pays to the TSO for negative utilisation. As a result, the WE operator has to pay for the called utilisation on the one hand, but increases the hydrogen production on the other hand.

As described in section 6.2.1, the requirement for the contract duration as well as for the minimal power can be lowered by aggregating reserve providing units (RPUs) in a virtual power plant (VPP). This allows a WE to combine positive and negative products. Hence, it is assumed that whenever the WE runs, it offers its nominal capacity for mFRR positive. In the high price hours however, when the WE is not operating, mFRR negative is offered at nominal power.

In order to estimate the influence of utilisation, average utilisation prices as well as average utilisation amounts (duration and frequency) are assumed. It is important to keep in mind that the amount of utilisation varies depending on the bidding strategy, which in turn has an impact on the business case. However, the effect on the business case is expected to be marginal since a higher utilisation comes with lower revenues per MWh utilisation (due to the merit-order principle) and is therefore neglected.

Figure 24: The effect of the asymmetric power reserve product on the category C business case (12 hours operation per day)

The impact of these power reserve products on the electricity costs is computed with historical values of 2016 and 2017.

6.3.1.1.1 Data for German grid services

Regarding Germany, the relevant data is available from Bundesnetzagentur [112]. The historical dataset has a 15-minute resolution and consists of mFRR and aFRR positive and negative with the following time-series:

- Average prices for availability for the active products within the time slot [€/MW]
- Average prices of utilisation paid to BSPs within each 15-minute slot [€/MWh]
- Sum of utilisation of each 15-minute slot [MWh]
- Total reserved capacity [MW]

The availability prices used for the analysis were derived from the published average prices for availability in a given time-slot as €/MW/h. In regard to utilisation, average values are assumed for the utilisation price as well as for the amount. By dividing the sum of the called utilisation by the total reserved capacity for each 15-minute slot, a relative utilisation amount is derived. By knowing the reserved WE capacity and the relative utilisation amount, the absolute utilisation can be computed for every 15-minute slot.

6.3.1.1.2 Data for Norwegian grid services

Turning to Norway, the RKOM (availability) data from Statnett [78] for the years 2016 and 2017 is used. The dataset has a resolution of one hour and consists of the following time-series:

- RKOM-H price [NOK/MW/h]

Please note that the time-series only consists of weekly contracts. Hence, seasonal contracts are neglected. Furthermore, the price for the negative availability is assumed to be zero. This is due to the fact that only positive availability is traded. In order to convert the availability prices to Euro, the official daily exchange rate time series from Nordpool is used [107].

As for utilisation, a common market exists among all Nordpool zones [110]. Hence, the average utility is calculated by dividing the sum of all zones of the regulating bids volume by the sum of

regulating volumes in each hour. The data available from Nordpool [107] consists of the following hourly time-series:

- Up-volume of bids of all zones [MW] (available positive utilisation)
- Down-volume of bids of all zones [MW] (available negative utilisation)
- Up-volume of called utilisation [MW]
- Down-volume of called utilisation [MW]
- Up-regulating (positive utilisation) prices in [€/MWh]
- Down-regulating (negative utilisation) prices in [€/MWh]

6.3.1.1.3 Impact of contract durations on availability revenues

The prices for availability depend on the product duration. The reasons are explained in this section. Since the assumed contract durations for the WE are equal for all examined grid service products, an approach to correct duration differences and hence to make the grid services comparable is presented.

The value a WE provides to an aggregator with its grid service offering depends not only on speed, reliability or power, but also on the time of day or time of week at which the WE operator is willing to offer its services. This can be understood based on the following considerations:

As explained in section 2, mFRR in Germany, aFRR in Germany and mFRR in Norway are traded as daily 4-hour and weekly off-peak/peak products, respectively. For any further analysis, and to make the cases comparable, it is assumed that the product delivery period is split into 15-minute slots by the aggregator, and that there is no minimal requirement regarding contracted power. The difference in the contract duration between the actual products and the assumed 15-minute duration plays a role when it comes to assessing these products. This is due to the fact that the day-ahead prices affect the tender's willingness to offer power reserve products [113]. The operator of a flexible power-plant, for example a storage hydro power plant, usually plans its schedule to maximise its profit. Hence, the higher the day-ahead prices, the more attractive it gets to sell electricity. As a result, the operator offers negative power reserve products for the time slots with high day-ahead prices (when the turbines run) and positive products for the slots with low prices. The willingness to offer negative power reserve during low price hours usually is low and therefore characterised by high offering prices and vice versa. Usually, weekend day-ahead prices are lower, due to a decreased demand of electricity. However, aFRR and mFRR (Norway) are weekly products. Hence, an RPU gets compensated for a whole week (either for peak or off-peak hours) with one price. If a power plant operator offers a weekly product, let's assume aFRR negative, he commits to let the turbines run even during the unfavourable weekend hours. Therefore, he bids with a price that covers this additional opportunity cost. If he could decide without the restriction of having to offer for a whole week, he would likely offer aFRR negative for a lower price during high price hours when he scheduled to produce electricity anyway, and with a higher price for the low day-ahead price hours.

The effect of the contract duration on the value of power-reserve is estimated by analysing the German mFRR (4-hour products) prices as if they had been traded as weekly products:

The historical availability prices of mFRR (Germany) are aggregated over the same hours aFRR (Germany) products are traded (bi-weekly products). This is done by calculating two average mFRR (Germany) availability prices for each week, a peak and an off-peak price. The impact on the LCOH is calculated for this synthetically aggregated mFRR (Germany) time-series as well as for the historical time-series with the 4-hour products. By comparing the relative savings on LCOH, it is possible to estimate the impact of this aggregation. By assuming that the impact is similar for aFRR and mFRR in Norway, it becomes possible to calculate the reduction on relative LCOH savings on aFRR and mFRR (Norway) due to splitting the weekly product into 4-hour products and deriving a more realistic result²⁹. It is worth mentioning that contract durations of 15 minutes are assumed, and therefore it still is likely to overestimate the revenues from mFRR and aFRR. However, since there is no historical data with contract durations for less than 4 hours available,

²⁹ Referred to as aFRR-realistic and mFRR-realistic.

neither for mFRR nor for aFRR, this effect cannot easily be quantified and certainly is reduced by the procedure described.

6.3.1.2 Symmetrical power reserve product (FCR)

In order to evaluate the economic potential of FCR, the full capacity of the WE is used for FCR. To guarantee the symmetrical power reserve, the WE can maximally operate at half of its maximum power, which corresponds to its nominal power.

When FCR is offered, the FCR offering is not only generating an additional revenue, but also yielding opportunity costs. These opportunity costs are caused by the fact that the WE has to operate on part-load while selling the symmetrical grid service product. As a result, the WE gives up the opportunity to produce hydrogen at maximum power during the best day-ahead price hours only. This reduction needs to be compensated by other hours at 50% of nominal power that originally were not scheduled for operation.

With this mechanism in mind, a procedure is derived in order to identify the hours, in which an FCR offering is advantageous while operating the WE on part-load. This procedure as well as the impact on the cost of electricity is depicted in Figure 25. The two hours during which FCR is most advantageous consist of

- the hour with the highest day-ahead-price that was at the same time scheduled for operation in the base-case and
- the hour with the lowest price that was originally not scheduled for operation

In the example of Figure 25, these hours would be hour 12 and hour 13. This is due to the fact that the difference of these two hours is the lowest possible difference and therefore, causes the minimal opportunity costs. The opportunity-costs are represented by the difference of the grey line (electricity payment if load is 50%) and the day-ahead price. This grey line, in turn, is the average of the day-ahead-prices (where we reduce the load from 100% to 50%) and the mirrored day-ahead-prices (where we increase the load from 0% to 50%). As can be seen, the lowest opportunity costs are found in hour 12 and increase towards the left side.

If we now subtract the revenue of FCR-availability, the actual electricity price (green line) of offering FCR and being at 50% of nominal power is obtained. Lower values of the green line, as compared to the day-ahead-curve, imply that an FCR offering is advantageous. In this example, as depicted in Figure 25, this is the case if the day-ahead-price is in the range from 29 to 34 €/MWh. If the day-ahead-price is lower than 29 €/MWh, the opportunity costs are too high and it is more advantageous to produce with nominal power instead of offering FCR.

The cost reduction due to FCR is reflected by the difference between the red and the blue area.

Figure 25: The effect of the symmetric power reserve product (FCR) on the category D business case (12 hours operation per day)

6.3.1.3 FCR: positive sensitivity for PEM-WE

In some configurations, the maximal load of PEM-WE can be increased by up to 200% of the nominal power for a maximum of 15 minutes [99].³⁰ This enables operation at nominal power while offering symmetrical power-reserve products at the same time. However, as it is described in 6.2.2, a called utilisation period can last up to 30 minutes. Therefore, it is questionable whether this flexible peak power of PEM-WE offers any advantage. Nonetheless, to show the economic impact of this possibility, a positive sensitivity for PEM-WE is calculated. The underlining assumption of this sensitivity analysis is an operation as derived for the base-case. Hence, it is assumed that the WE operates at nominal power during the best hours while offering 100% of its nominal power as FCR. Therefore, opportunity costs due to a lower production in advantageous times can be avoided.

6.3.2 Results for TSO grid services

By implementing the procedures and model assumptions defined above, and testing them on the historical data described in 6.2, it is possible to derive the costs of hydrogen production depending on different setups. In order to make the impact of the different grid service products on the WE business cases comparable, savings due to these products on LCOH have been computed. These savings are depicted depending on full load hours in Figure 27, whereas the absolute LCOH are shown in Figure 26 (refer to Appendix 10.1 for detailed results). By comparing the absolute LCOH of the base cases from Germany and Norway (Figure 26, 'only Day Ahead'), the influence of the electricity price difference can be seen. For the highest FLH-scenario (8760 h), LCOH in Norway are significantly lower compared to the ones in Germany (by 0.36 and 0.39 €/kg for ALK-WE and PEM-WE, respectively). However, by decreasing the FLH, this difference gets smaller and

³⁰ That depends on design aspects such as the dimensioning of the power rectifier etc. However, in general such a flexibility increases the CAPEX.

disappears completely at roughly 3650 FLH. For even lower FLH scenarios, German prices result in a lower LCOH compared to Norway despite the higher German average electricity prices. This is due to the high variability of German electricity prices (see Section 6.1.2),.

Figure 26: Absolute LCOH

The influence of different grid services can best be examined by looking at LCOH savings in Figure 27.

Figure 27: Relative LCOH-savings (upper) and absolute LCOH-savings (lower) due to grid-services for ALK-WE (left) and PEM-WE (right)

Looking at the absolute FCR savings, the highest impact is found at low FLH scenarios (for the lowest FLH scenario 0.94 €/kg (PEM-WE) and 0.86 €/kg (ALK-WE)). As the operating hours increase, this value decreases steadily and reaches 0.56 (PEM) and 0.52 (ALK) €/kg at the 4380 FLH scenario. This decrease is caused by the opportunity costs of not having the possibility to concentrate the production during the lowest price hours (see Section 6.3.1.2). If the FLH are further increased, the number of hours available for part load (50% of nominal power) declines and restricts therefore the revenues of FCR even more. As a result, an even steeper decrease can be observed for FLH higher than 4380.

Rather constant relative savings over all possible FLH scenarios can be observed for aFRR and mFRR (Germany). The average savings are with 7.2% (PEM) and 9.0% (ALK) substantially higher for aFRR than for mFRR (Germany) with 2.3% (PEM) and 2.8% (ALK).

Due to the inexistence of a negative mFRR availability market in Norway, the relative savings of mFRR (Norway) steadily increase from almost zero for low FLH scenarios to 2.4% and 2.7% for PEM and ALK-WE, respectively.

As can be seen for PEM as well as for ALK-WE, the least promising grid services are mFRR (Germany) and mFRR (Norway). At less than 1000 FLH, aFRR shows the highest saving potentials with about 7% and 5% of savings on LCOH for ALK and PEM WE, respectively. Above 1000 FLH, FCR influences the LCOH even more and reaches relative savings of 13% and 11% on LCOH for 4380 FLH. Between 5700 and 8760 FLH aFRR is the dominant grid service product in terms of saving potential.

It is worth mentioning here, that many effects which limit savings from grid services could not be considered at this stage of the analysis. These effects include the costs of additional storage facilities and lower availability revenues due to the temporal splitting of availability contracts. Hence, the results show a more optimistic picture and should only be used to compare the grid service products relative to each other.

The most promising products for business cases categories A and C are depicted in Table 11. For category C, the best product for both WE-types is clearly FCR. By focusing on category A, aFRR outperforms the other products.

Table 11: The most promising grid service products for each business case category / WE-type (peak percentage of LCOH savings).

	ALK-WE	PEM-WE
Business Case Category A	aFRR (8%)	aFFR (7%) or FCR, positive Sensitivity (up to 22%*)
Business Case Category C	FCR (13%)	FCR (11%)

* if the influence of increased CAPEX due to over dimension is neglected

6.3.3 Results for FCR sensitivity for PEM-WE

If the relative savings on LCOH are computed under consideration of the restrictions defined for the positive sensitivity for FCR and PEM-WE (see section 6.3.1.3), up to 22% of savings can be observed for more than 8000 FLH. However, the increased CAPEX of the over dimensioning was not considered. If the additional CAPEX does not outweigh the FCR revenues, FCR might promise even higher savings for a PEM-WE.

6.4 DSO grid services – congestion management

In Europe, there are no practical cases where WEs are commercially run for CM purposes, and particularly no developed market with published prices exist. Therefore, instead of analysing a specific business case to determine the value of CM, a generic model for PV and wind is developed on the basis of a single grid connection point shared between a wind or PV farm and a WE as depicted in Figure 28. There the power line is subject to congestions in case of high infeed of wind. This is done to provide an overall picture of the economic value that CM would create in terms of savings in LCOH for any amount of FLH.

Figure 28: Electrical configuration of a WE sharing a connection point with a wind farm. Congestion takes place at the following power line [5]

An example of such a grid configuration of a power-to-gas (PtG) pilot project located in Germany is Windgas Haßfurt, where green hydrogen is produced with a 1.25 MW PEM WE from surplus wind and solar energy situated close to a wind farm sharing a common grid connection point. The

green hydrogen is injected into the natural gas grid and is sold to 14'000 customers at 59 €/MWh³¹ HHV for combustion in residential, commercial, and industrial buildings. A virtual power plant controls when the WE must start-up in order to consume electricity only when there is an abundance of renewable energy thus relieving pressure on the local and external distribution grid. Expounded in Appendix 10.11 are the specifics of the Windgas Haßfurt case.

The model bases on the following assumptions:

- The WE uses wind or solar photovoltaic electricity that would have been otherwise curtailed.
- The WE obtains electrical energy at the cheapest day ahead price or for free if curtailed³²
- The WE is exempted from EEG tariffs³³
- The WE is exempted from grid tariffs and taxes³⁴ other than value added tax (VAT) included in the electricity price
- The WE is owned by the wind park owner, therefore, the financial value added by CM doesn't need to be split between wind park and WE.
- For a given time slot, the CM service is not combined with other grid services, since the current market design doesn't support a single flexibility market place.

Since the power of the WE is considerably smaller than the rated power of the wind park, the WE can be assumed to operate at full power or zero, even in case of congestion, without introducing a relevant inaccuracy.

6.4.1 Combining DSO grid service with WE application

In order to estimate the influence of curtailment on the WE, the curtailed hours are estimated with the following approach. Based on historical data (2016, 2017) of the total German onshore wind and solar production [112], each quarter-hourly time period that exceeds a certain threshold in regards to either solar or wind power production is assumed to be curtailed. To this end, the total production is normalized with the respective peak production \hat{P} . This normalized solar or wind production profile is now assumed to be the profile of a fictive distributed power source (DPS). On comparison of these synthesized production profiles with actual distributed power sources (DPS) in regards to full load hours (FLH), it can be seen that the fictive wind DPS performs with 2'088 FLH, better than the average already installed German DPS (1760 FLH in 2017), but not as good as newly installed German wind-DPS [114]. As for the solar-DPS, the FLH derived from the fictional profile are unrealistically high with 1'262 for a solar DPS located in Germany [115] and therefore are scaled down such that 1000 FLH are reached. This synthesized profile is still a rather good performing but realistic DPS profile [115]. The load duration curves of both fictive DPSs are depicted in Figure 29.

³¹ [131, p. 11]

³² In times of curtailment, energy can be received for (almost) free if the wind park owner is remunerated for congested energy by the power line owner, or in an unregulated market where energy tariffs and wind force strongly correlate.

³³ As by the revision of 2017 (EEG2017), the WE is exempt from the EEG surcharges if hydrogen is used for the later reconversion to electricity. Other uses of hydrogen like mobility applications are not yet exempted, but discussions on this topic are ongoing [137].

³⁴ As by Art. 60 EEG exemptions, grid integrated electrolyzers are exempted from use of system charges, specific taxes and levies are possible when electrolyzers serve as storage for electrical energy, which is fed back into the grid at a later date. Also, when electrolyzers next to renewable power plants, where the electricity supply takes place without the use of the transmission or distribution network.

Figure 29: Normalised (and scaled with respect to solar) load duration curves of total onshore wind and solar production in Germany. By examining a high curtailment scenario as an example, curtailed hours totalled 1271 and 2160 hours a year for a solar and wind DPS, respectively

The number of curtailed hours is highly dependent on grid topology and grid strength in relation to nominal power of the DPS, $P_{Nom,DPS}$. To approximate the grid strength at a certain node, we introduce P_{Max} , the maximal infeed power the grid is capable of receiving at this specific node. Hence, it is assumed that all hours where the DPS-production $P(t)$ exceeds P_{Max} are being curtailed. In normalized terms, the curtailment hours are defined as all hours where

$$\frac{P(t)}{\bar{P}} > \frac{P_{Max}}{P_{Nom,DPS}}$$

It is assumed, that $P_{Nom,DPS} \gg P_{Nom,WE}$. Hence, the WE can produce with $P_{Nom,WE}$ in all curtailed hours without any electricity costs.

6.4.2 Results for CM

The LCOH as well as the absolute savings on the LCOH with respect to FLH and $P_{Max}/P_{Nom,DPS}$ are presented in Figure 30. It can be seen that, P_{Max}/P_{Nom} has to be relatively small so that curtailment has a relevant effect on the LCOH for solar as well as for a wind DPS. By comparing the contour lines of the solar DPS to the wind DPS and keeping P_{Max}/P_{Nom} constant, it can be concluded that curtailment of solar-DPS is more advantageous for business cases with relatively low FLH. This is mainly due to the fact that hours with high wind production correlate with low day-ahead power prices. However, for business cases characterized by high full load hours, the number of curtailed hours is becoming the dominating factor and as a result, wind-curtailment looks more attractive. At $P_{Max}/P_{Nom,DPS} = 0.4$ and 1000 FLH, CM leads to 0.2 € and 0.5 €/kg LCOH savings for wind and solar DPS, respectively. However, at FLH = 7'000 a wind-DPS saves 0.24 whereas a solar-DPS only 0.2 €/kg. Shown in Figure 31, when considering a very high curtailment scenario for example of $P_{Max}/P_{Nom} = 1/3$, relative LCOH savings for either solar or wind reach relative savings of the order between 8 and 12%. Hence, extreme curtailment scenarios promise LCOH-savings in the same order as TSO grid services. However, such high curtailment scenarios correspond to approximately 1'500 and 2'500 curtailment hours for solar and wind DPS, respectively. It is highly questionable whether such extreme situations are experienced in Germany in the future as discussed in section 5.9 where the best location for CM in Germany in 2024 could result in curtailed hours totalling 729 h [6].

Figure 30: Absolute LCOH (upper) and LCOH-Savings (lower) from curtailment.

Figure 31: Relative LCOH savings (relative to the base case with the respective FLH)

6.5 Interim conclusion

It can be concluded, that for WE operation characterized up to 6000 FLH, FCR in Germany has the highest potential to reduce the LCOH and might reduce it up to about 10%. For high FLH-operation, aFRR in Germany is the most attractive grid service. mFRR in Germany as well as in Norway have only a minor effect on LCOH. As for CM, the potential is highly depended on the grid topology or more specifically, on the number of curtailed hours. However, in order to have a reduction potential of the same order as for the most promising TSO grid services (aFRR and FCR), the number of curtailed hours has to be unrealistically high. It is at least questionable whether such a situation can be observed in the future, at least in Germany.

7 Conclusions

In most European countries, the TSO grid service markets develop towards similar structures, driven by the harmonization efforts of ENTSO-E. As such, many countries support an aggregator business model, where distributed WEs can become part of a VPP operated by a BSP. This configuration makes the BSP the most important business partner of the WE operator for the provision of balancing services. At the same time, it opens several of the European TSO grid service markets to WEs. Long-term reliability, speed of electrical power control as well as level and stability of the electrical power consumption determine the value that the WE has for the BSP.

The main aim of this study is to identify four promising grid services for further analysis in work packages 6.3 and 6.4 of the QualyGridS project. As such, 85 TSO grid services and one DSO grid service case were analysed and in a first step reduced to eight cases. For that purpose, the data available from literature was extended by a survey and an extensive verification round, where members of different TSOs were contacted and interviewed and the official data sets of the TSOs consulted. A multi-criteria evaluation, that considered not only grid service prices but also the attractiveness of national hydrogen markets, lead to the selection of German FCR, mFRR+, mFRR-, aFRR+ and aFRR-, Norwegian mFRR+ and mFRR- and one congestion management case. These were then further evaluated.

In order to assess the impact of these grid services, current WE business cases were considered at first. This was essential to formulate the operation restrictions, which influence the offering of grid services. Being aware of these limitations enabled deriving an optimal scheduling for each grid service product. By integrating these optimal scheduling procedures into a discounted cash flow model and by thoroughly testing it with historical data, it was possible to derive the levelised cost of hydrogen under different setups. By analysing the disparities of different setups with and without grid services, the influence of each grid service could be obtained. From the results, it becomes clear that FCR is the most profitable grid service that can reduce the levelised cost of hydrogen up to a maximum of 22 percent for PEM WE with high overload capacity, or more realistically around 10 percent. For business cases with Alkaline WE with 5500 or more full-load hours, aFRR is more promising than FCR.

A secondary aim was to determine the value of CM by evaluating its effect on a business case. However, due to its novelty, no specific case could be selected. Instead a model was developed to give insight into the LCOH savings that can be achieved through all possible full-load hours at various levels of grid strength for a hypothetical wind and solar-DPS. It is revealed that at low FLH solar yields greater savings while the converse is true at significantly higher FLH. Furthermore, only in extreme curtailment scenarios (in excess of 2000 FLH) can LCOH savings reach 10%, a similar level of savings that can be expected from TSO grid services.

As an outcome of the report, the cases in Table 12 have been shown to be the most compelling with the highest potential and are thus proposed for further analysis in WP6.3 and WP6.4.

Table 12 The most promising grid service products for each business case category / WE-type (peak percentage of LCOH savings).

	ALK-WE	PEM-WE
Business Case Category A	aFRR (8%)	aFRR (7%) or FCR, positive Sensitivity (up to 22%*)
Business Case Category C	FCR (13%)	FCR (11%)

* if the influence of increased CAPEX due to over dimension is neglected

8 Outlook

The influence of grid services on WE use cases were computed and are now comparable.

However, there are still many uncertainties due to the simplified model, assumptions and the future development with regards to electricity and grid-service prices.

The main limitations of the models and assumptions used include the following:

- The influence of stand-by power consumption is neglected.
- The influence of grid-services on storage infrastructure is neglected.
- The future development of electricity prices is uncertain.
- The future development of grid service prices is uncertain.
- The influence of grid services on OPEX and stack replacement rate is not considered.
- The influence of grid services on the power-to-hydrogen efficiency is neglected.

By defining different scenarios in regard to price development and by modelling the features of WEs more realistically, many of the uncertainties due to the above limitations can be reduced. These will be addressed by the QualyGridS work packages 6.3 and 6.4.

In the specific case of congestion management, the following possible future developments have the potential to impact the case of PtH and grid services positively for the most part:

- The continued decrease of or exemption from EEG levy.
- The introduction of green hydrogen grid injection tariffs similar to biomethane tariffs.
- Forecasted increases in carbon pricing that could in turn increase the wholesale natural gas price, thus placing higher value on traded green hydrogen.
- New grid optimisation technologies that have the potential to lower grid investment costs, rendering them more attractive than grid investment deferral options.

What is almost certain to take place is the decrease of WE technology cost, which will undoubtedly improve the profitability of all business cases.

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10 Appendix

10.1 Detailed FLH scenario results for TSO products

		ALK-WE					PEM-WE					
Germany	Base-Case	#h@P_nom	2008	4015	6022	8030	8760	2008	4015	6022	8030	8760
		PV, OPEX/CAPEX [kEuro]	1737	1829	1942	2062	2106	2269	2543	2834	3130	3238
		PV, Tot Electricity [kEuro]	456	1044	1755	2587	2934	456	1044	1755	2587	2934
		PV, H2 Production [tons]	367	734	1101	1468	1602	338	676	1014	1352	1474
		Icoh [euro/kg]	5.98	3.91	3.36	3.17	3.15	8.07	5.31	4.55	4.22	4.21
		FCR	#h@P_nom	113	401	3426	7329	8760	113	401	3426	7329
	#h@FCR(P=0.5*Pnom)		3789	7228	5191	1401	0	3789	7228	5191	1401	0
	PV Revenue Avail. [kEuro]		311	593	427	115	0	311	593	427	115	0
	PV Cost elect.[kEuro]		513	1238	1868	2607	2934	513	1238	1868	2607	2942
	PV H2 Production [tons]		367	734	1101	1468	1602	338	676	1014	1352	1474
	Icoh [euro/kg]		5.28	3.37	3.08	3.1	3.16	7.31	4.72	4.24	4.15	4.22
	FCR (sensitivity)	#h@P_nom = #h@FCR						2008	4015	6022	8030	8760
		PV Revenue Avail. [kEuro]						317	634	952	1269	1384
		PV Cost elect.[kEuro]						456	1044	1755	2587	2934
		Icoh [euro/kg]						7.13	4.37	3.61	3.29	3.27
	aFRR	#h@aFRR+	2008	4015	6022	8030	8760	2008	4015	6022	8030	8760
		#h@aFRR-	6752	4745	2738	730	0	6752	4745	2738	730	0
		#h@a P=Pnom (corr. due UT)	2244	3995	5734	7462	8088	2244	3995	5734	7462	8088
		#h@a P=0 (corr. due UT)	6516	4765	3026	1298	672	6516	4765	3026	1298	672
		UT positive [MWh/a]	121	270	432	611	671	121	270	432	611	671
		UT negative [MWh/a]	358	250	143	43	0	358	250	143	43	0
		PV Revenue Avail.+[kEuro]	84	157	225	295	321	84	157	225	295	321
		PV Revenue Avail.-[kEuro]	57	37	22	6	0	57	37	22	6	0
		PV Cost elect. [kEuro]	455.8	1044	1755	2587	2934	455.8	1044	1755	2587	2934
		PV Cost inkl. Ut./Av.[kEuro]	283.6	710	1250	1902	2188	283.6	710	1250	1902	2188
		PV H2 Production [tons]	410.3	730	1048	1364	1479	377.7	672	965	1256	1361
		Icoh [euro/kg]	4.95	3.47	3.03	2.88	2.89	6.84	4.84	4.21	3.93	3.94
	mFRR	#h@mFRR+	2008	4015	6022	8030	8760	2008	4015	6022	8030	8760
		#h@mFRR-	6752	4745	2738	730	0	6752	4745	2738	730	0
		#h@a P=Pnom (corr. due UT)	2022	4005	5982	7955	8669	2022	4005	5982	7955	8669
#h@a P=0 (corr. due UT)		6738	4755	2778	805	91	6738	4755	2778	805	91	
UT positive [MWh/a]		8	24	46	78	93	8	24	46	78	93	
UT negative [MWh/a]		-23	-12	-5	-1	0	-23	-12	-5	-1	0	
PV Revenue Avail.+[kEuro]		7	15	26	40	47	7	15	26	40	47	
PV Revenue Avail.-[kEuro]		46	27	13	3	0	46	27	13	3	0	

	PV Cost elect.[kEuro]	455.8	1044	1755	2587	2934	455.8	1044	1755	2587	2934
	Cost inkl. Ut./Av.[kEuro]	401.7	975	1641	2374	2646	401.7	975	1641	2374	2646
	PV H2 Production [tons]	369.8	732	1094	1454	1585	340.4	674	1007	1339	1459
	lcoh [euro/kg]	5.78	3.83	3.28	3.04	3.01	7.85	5.22	4.46	4.1	4.05
Norway	#h@aFRR+	2008	4015	6022	8030	8760	2008	4015	6022	8030	8760
	#h@aFRR-	6752	4745	2738	730	0	6752	4745	2738	730	0
	#h@a P=Pnom (corr. due UT)	2164	4083	6007	7934	8636	2164	4083	6007	7934	8636
	#h@a P=0 (corr. due UT)	6516	4765	3026	1298	672	6516	4765	3026	1298	672
	UT positive [MWh/a]	21	46	78	113	127	21	46	78	113	127
	UT negative [MWh/a]	-177	-117	-63	-16	0	-177	-117	-63	-16	0
	PV Revenue Avail.+ [kEuro]	18	45	79	115	128	18	45	79	115	128
	PV Revenue Avail.- [kEuro]	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	PV Cost elect.[kEuro]	493.9	1022	1571	2141	2358	493.9	1022	1571	2141	2358
	PV Cost inkl. Ut./Av.[kEuro]	508.2	987	1480	1991	2186	508.2	987	1480	1991	2186
	PV H2 Production [tons]	395.5	747	1098	1451	1579	364.1	687	1011	1335	1454
lcoh [euro/kg]	5.69	3.78	3.12	2.79	2.73	7.68	5.15	4.28	3.82	3.74	

10.2 Appendix – TSO Questionnaire

Introduction and Background

Grid operators are responsible for maintaining safe and reliable power transfer from the production units to the end users. This is achieved through a number of grid services. Examples at the transmission level are balancing services, capacity management and congestion management. Typical balancing services with approximate time scales are shown in the following figure:

You, S. (2017). Deliverable Report Electrical Grid Service Catalogue for Water Electrolyser, based on: entso-e 28.06.2013. Supporting Document for the Network Code on Load-Frequency Control and Reserves. Online (2017-12-01): http://www.acer.europa.eu/Official_documents/Acts_of_the_Agency/Annexes/ENTSO-E%E2%80%99s%20supporting%20document%20to%20the%20submitted%20Network%20Code%20on%20Load-Frequency%20Control%20and%20Reserves.pdf

The European grid service markets are constantly being developed as more fluctuating renewables are being fed into the grid. This increases the importance of grid services and opens up opportunities for more flexible generation and consumption. A flexible load which can increase or decrease its power demand can technically offer the same balancing services as a generator decreasing or increasing production. An example of a load providing such flexibility is a water electrolyser.

The purpose of this survey is to collect and analyse empirical data from European TSOs in order to identify opportunities in the TSO grid service markets for flexible loads. The most interesting cases will be followed up in a second round. This study is part of the research project *QualyGridS*. The results will be published by June 2018, a copy will be sent to the contributors of this survey.

This survey is planned and executed by Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts on behalf of the European Union (EU) Research Project, *QualyGridS* (Project 735485, www.qualygrids.eu).

Contact information

In case of questions or remarks please contact:

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How to answer the survey

The survey consists of 4 parts:

- Part A, three pages: a table with four columns for balancing services (FCR, aFRR, mFRR, RR) according to the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E, 2013), and ten questions arranged in rows. Each question shall be answered for each service by either ticking the corresponding answer box (to change your answer: fill the box, and tick the correct one) or giving a short textual explanation. The type of answer expected is indicated by the column 'Type of answer'. Questions that cannot be answered can be left out.
- Part B, three pages: a table for additional services specific to your country that are provided by flexible loads is arranged similarly to part A.
- Part C, one page: four general questions to be answered as free text.
- Part D, one page: any remarks as free text.
- Appendix: additional empty forms for Part B.

Please return the answered survey **by 20 December 2017** to:

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts HSLU, Lucerne School of Engineering and Architecture, Prof. Dr. Christoph Imboden, Technikumstrasse 21, CH-6048 Horw

or by email to:

christoph.imboden@hslu.ch

Thank you, we greatly appreciate your support!

Part A: FCR³⁵, aFRR³⁶, mFRR³⁷, RR³⁸

Each question shall be answered for each of the services FCR, aFRR, mFRR and RR. Questions that cannot be answered can be left out.

Question	Type of answer	Service: FCR	Service: aFRR	Service: mFRR	Service: RR
National/ regional service name	Text				
1 Is a non-rotating mass ³⁹ accepted to provide the service?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>			
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>			
	Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)
2 Is a load accepted for providing the service?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>			

³⁵ Frequency Containment Reserve is an automatic operating reserve which is activated in the whole synchronous area to stabilize the power system frequency if there is an imbalance between production and consumption.

³⁶ Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve will be activated automatically in the responsible country to restore the system frequency to the nominal frequency.

³⁷ Manual Frequency Restoration Reserve will be activated manually in the responsible country to replace the aFRR and restore the nominal frequency until the balance is reached again.

³⁸ Replacement Reserve is an optional manually activated reserve which helps to restore the operating reserves (FCR, aFRR, mFRR) to be prepared for a further system imbalance.

³⁹ Rotating masses (inertia) store kinetic energy stabilizing the grid frequency

Question	Type of answer	Service: FCR	Service: aFRR	Service: mFRR	Service: RR
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 			
3 Can geographically distributed loads or generators be aggregated ⁴⁰ and contribute to the service?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>			
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 			
4 How is the service shaped? (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Text
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, what might change and how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' What (text)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 			

⁴⁰ 'Aggregation' is to be understood as the representation of a number of power generating modules and/or demand facilities providing grid services as if it was a single power generating module or demand facility. 'Geographically distributed loads' is to be understood as loads being connected to the grid at different metering points.

Question	Type of answer	Service: FCR	Service: aFRR	Service: mFRR	Service: RR
	Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)
5 Is the service provision symmetrical ⁴¹ / asymmetrical ⁴² ?	Tick symmetrical ('sy') or asymmetrical ('as')	sy <input type="checkbox"/> as <input type="checkbox"/>			
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>			
	Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)
6 Does the service provision have to be dynamic ⁴³ / non-dynamic ⁴⁴	Dynamic (dyn)/ non-dynamic (non)	dyn <input type="checkbox"/> non <input type="checkbox"/>			

⁴¹ On demand by the TSO or DSO a load or generator has to be able to increase and decrease its power.

⁴² On demand by the TSO or DSO a load or generator has to be able to increase only or decrease only its power.

⁴³ Load can follow a continuous signal.

⁴⁴ Load is switched between two values.

Question	Type of answer	Service: FCR	Service: aFRR	Service: mFRR	Service: RR
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 			
7 What is the requested maximum output duration of one activation ⁴⁵ ?	Time (seconds/ minutes/ hours) sec minutes hours			
8 What is the requested minimum output duration of one activation ⁴⁶ ?	Time (seconds/ minutes/ hours) sec minutes hours			
9 What was the average availability ⁴⁷ price for the service in 2016	€/MW				

⁴⁵ The maximum period during which the technical unit delivers the requested power.

⁴⁶ The minimum period during which the technical unit delivers the requested power.

⁴⁷ The technical unit is kept available for being called, but it's not yet providing control energy.

Question	Type of answer	Service: FCR	Service: aFRR	Service: mFRR	Service: RR
10 What was the average utilisation ⁴⁸ price in 2016? If there are multiple product shapes (question 4) refer to the most valuable one.	€/MWh* (to be read as '€ per MW and hour of reserve')				
11 What is the market mechanism (procurement method) of the service?	Bilateral agreement/ market tendering/ obligation/ other (please specify)

⁴⁸ The price for the provision of energy

Part B: Additional services

Names of additional services that might be provided by flexible loads are to be listed in the first row, and each question shall be answered for each of these additional services. Questions that cannot be answered can be left out. Additional pages for space can be found in the appendix.

Question	Type of answer	Service:	Service:	Service:
1. Is a non-rotating mass ⁴⁹ accepted to provide the service?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
2. Is a load accepted for providing the service?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

⁴⁹ Rotating masses (inertia) store kinetic energy stabilizing the grid frequency.

Question	Type of answer	Service:	Service:	Service:
3 Can geographically distributed loads or generators be aggregated ⁵⁰ and contribute to the service?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
4 How are services shaped? (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Text
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

⁵⁰ 'Aggregation' is to be understood as the representation of a number of power generating modules and/or demand facilities providing grid services as if it was a single power generating module or demand facility. 'Geographically distributed loads' is to be understood as loads being connected to the grid at different metering points.

Question	Type of answer	Service:	Service:	Service:
5 Is the service provision symmetrical ⁵¹ / asymmetrical ⁵² ?	Tick symmetrical ('sy') or asymmetrical ('as')	sy <input type="checkbox"/> as <input type="checkbox"/>	sy <input type="checkbox"/> as <input type="checkbox"/>	sy <input type="checkbox"/> as <input type="checkbox"/>
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
6 Does the service provision have to be dynamic ⁵³ / non-dynamic ⁵⁴	dynamic (dyn)/ non-dynamic (non)	dyn <input type="checkbox"/> non <input type="checkbox"/>	dyn <input type="checkbox"/> non <input type="checkbox"/>	dyn <input type="checkbox"/> non <input type="checkbox"/>
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

⁵¹ On demand by the TSO or DSO a load or generator has to be able to increase and decrease its power.

⁵² On demand by the TSO or DSO a load or generator has to be able to increase only or decrease only its power.

⁵³ Load can follow a continuous signal.

⁵⁴ Load is switched between two values.

Question	Type of answer	Service:	Service:	Service:
7 What is the maximum output duration of one activation ⁵⁵ ?	Time (seconds/minutes/hours) sec minutes hours sec minutes hours sec minutes hours
8 What is the minimum output duration of one activation ⁵⁶ ?	Time (seconds/minutes/hours) sec minutes hours sec minutes hours sec minutes hours
9 What is the average availability ⁵⁷ price for the service in 2016	€/MW			
10 What is the average utilisation ⁵⁸ price in 2016?	€/MWh*			

⁵⁵ The maximum period during which the technical unit delivers the requested power.

⁵⁶ The minimum period during which the technical unit delivers the requested power.

⁵⁷ The technical unit is kept available for being called, but it's not yet providing control energy.

⁵⁸ The price for the provision of energy

Question	Type of answer	Service:	Service:	Service:
If there are multiple product shapes (question 4) refer to the most valuable.	(to be read as '€ per MW and hour of reserve')			
11 What is the market mechanism (procurement method of the services)?	Bilateral agreement/market tendering/ obligation/other (please specify)			

Part C: General questions

Please answer the following questions as free text.

Are there any trends not mentioned so far that may have a relevant impact on the grid service market in your country? If so please name and describe them, or give a reference link to a description.	
Are there aggregators ⁵⁹ active on the market? If yes, could you give us contact	

⁵⁹ 'Aggregator' is to be understood as the legal entity responsible for the operation of a number of power generating modules and/or demand facilities by means of aggregation for the purpose of offering grid services.

Your contact data for further enquiries

First name:

Surname:

Company:

Address:

Email:

Telephone:

Appendix

This table can be used if you need space for additional services

Question	Type of answer	Service:	Service:	Service:
1. Is a non-rotating mass ⁶⁰ accepted to provide the service?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
2. Is a load accepted for providing the service?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
3. Can geographically distributed loads or	Tick 'Yes' or 'No'	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

⁶⁰ Rotating masses (inertia) store kinetic energy stabilizing the grid frequency.

Question	Type of answer	Service:	Service:	Service:
generators be aggregated ⁶¹ and contribute to the service?				
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
4 How are services shaped? (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Text
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

⁶¹ 'Aggregation' is to be understood as the representation of a number of power generating modules and/or demand facilities providing grid services as if it was a single power generating module or demand facility. 'Geographically distributed loads' is to be understood as loads being connected to the grid at different metering points.

Question	Type of answer	Service:	Service:	Service:
	
5 Is the service provision symmetrical ⁶² / asymmetrical ⁶³ ?	Tick symmetrical ('sy') or asymmetrical ('as')	sy <input type="checkbox"/> as <input type="checkbox"/>	sy <input type="checkbox"/> as <input type="checkbox"/>	sy <input type="checkbox"/> as <input type="checkbox"/>
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
6 Does the service provision have to be dynamic ⁶⁴ / non-dynamic ⁶⁵ ?	dynamic (dyn)/ non-dynamic (non)	dyn <input type="checkbox"/> non <input type="checkbox"/>	dyn <input type="checkbox"/> non <input type="checkbox"/>	dyn <input type="checkbox"/> non <input type="checkbox"/>
Is this expected to change in the next 5 years? If so, how probable would this change be?	Tick 'Yes' or 'No' Probability (low, medium, high, 100%)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> 	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
7 What is the maximum output duration of one activation ⁶⁶ ?	Time (seconds/minutes/hours)			

⁶² On demand by the TSO or DSO a load or generator has to be able to increase and decrease its power.

⁶³ On demand by the TSO or DSO a load or generator has to be able to increase only or decrease only its power.

⁶⁴ Load can follow a continuous signal.

⁶⁵ Load is switched between two values.

⁶⁶ The maximum period during which the technical unit delivers the requested power.

Question	Type of answer	Service:	Service:	Service:
		<p>.....</p> <p>..... sec</p> <p>..... minutes</p> <p>..... hours</p>	<p>.....</p> <p>..... sec</p> <p>..... minutes</p> <p>..... hours</p>	<p>.....</p> <p>..... sec</p> <p>..... minutes</p> <p>..... hours</p>
<p>8 What is the minimum output duration of one activation⁶⁷?</p>	<p>Time (seconds/minutes/hours)</p>	<p>..... sec</p> <p>..... minutes</p> <p>..... hours</p>	<p>..... sec</p> <p>..... minutes</p> <p>..... hours</p>	<p>..... sec</p> <p>..... minutes</p> <p>..... hours</p>
<p>9 What is the average availability⁶⁸ price for the service in 2016</p>	<p>€/MW</p>			
<p>10 What is the average utilisation⁶⁹ price in 2016? If there are multiple product shapes (question 4) refer to the most valuable.</p>	<p>€/MWh* (to be read as '€ per MW and hour of reserve')</p>			

⁶⁷ The minimum period during which the technical unit delivers the requested power.

⁶⁸ The technical unit is kept available for being called, but it's not yet providing control energy.

⁶⁹ The price for the provision of energy

Question	Type of answer	Service:	Service:	Service:
11 What is the market mechanism (procurement method of the services)?	Bilateral agreement/market tendering/ obligation/other (please specify)			

10.3 Appendix – DSO Questionnaire

Introduction and Background

Grid operators are responsible for maintaining safe and reliable power transfer from the production units to the end users. This is achieved through a number of grid services. Examples at the distribution level are congestion management, capacity management and voltage control. The European grid service markets are constantly being developed as more fluctuating renewables are being fed into the grid. This increases the importance of grid services and opens up opportunities for more flexible generation and consumption. An example of a load providing such flexibility is a water electrolyser.

The purpose of this survey is to collect and analyse empirical data from European DSOs in order to identify opportunities for flexible loads in the DSO grid service markets. The most interesting cases will be followed up in a second round. This study is part of the research project *QualyGridS*. The results will be published by June 2018, a copy will be sent to the contributors of this survey.

The survey is planned and executed by Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts on behalf of the European Union (EU) Research Project, *QualyGridS* (Project 735485, www.qualygrids.eu).

Contact information

In case of questions or remarks please contact:

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts HSLU
Lucerne School of Engineering and Architecture
Prof. Dr. Christoph Imboden
Technikumstrasse 21
CH-6048 Horw

www.hslu.ch/en/lucerne-school-of-engineering-architecture/

Email christoph.imboden@hslu.ch

Tel. +41 41 349 3752

How to answer the survey

The survey consists of 4 parts:

- Part A, one page: a table with two columns for balancing services (Congestion Management and Capacity Management) and three questions. Each question is to be answered for each service. The type of answer expected is indicated by the column 'Type of answer'. Questions that cannot be answered can be left out.
- Part B, one page: a table for additional services specific to your country that are provided by flexible loads is arranged similarly to part A.
- Part C, one page: three general questions to be answered as free text.
- Part D: any remarks as free text are welcomed.
- Appendix: Appendix: additional empty forms for Part B.

Please return the answered survey **by 20 December 2017** to:

Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts HSLU, Lucerne School of Engineering and Architecture, Prof. Dr. Christoph Imboden, Technikumstrasse 21, CH-6048 Horw

or by email to:

christoph.imboden@hslu.ch

Thank you, we greatly appreciate your support!

Part A: Congestion management, Capacity management, Voltage control

Each question is to be answered for each service - congestion management and capacity management.

1 year = 8000 operational hours

Question	Type of answer	Service: Congestion Management	Service: Capacity Management
1	Scenario 1, symmetrical service: a load can be <u>increased and decreased</u> remotely within less than 10 seconds (full activation time).		
How much would you pay for the availability ⁷⁰ ?	(€/MW/yr)		
How many hours per year would you typically activate the service?	(h/yr)		
2	Scenario 2, asymmetrical service+: a load can be <u>decreased</u> remotely within less than 10 seconds (full activation time).		
How much would you pay for the availability ¹ ?	(€/MW/yr)		
How many hours per year would you typically activate the service?	(h/yr)		
3	Scenario 3, asymmetrical service-: a load can be <u>increased</u> remotely within less than 10 seconds (full activation time).		
How much would you pay for the availability ¹ ?	(€/MW/year)		
How many hours per year would you typically activate the service?	(h/yr)		

⁷⁰ The load is kept available for being called.

Part B: Additional Services

Simplified equivalent circuit of a service providing unit: the load may be varied on demand within seconds. The load is connected to the grid through an AC/DC converter. Detailed specifications may be fitted for a specific service.

1 year = 8000 operational hours

Question	Service: Voltage Control	Service:	Service
Short description of the service [Text]

Part C: General Questions

<p>Are there any trends that may have a relevant impact on the DSO grid services⁷¹ required by your company? If so please name and describe them, or give a reference link to a description.</p>	<p>.....</p>
<p>Are there pilot projects testing DSO grid services² provided by flexible loads? If so please name and describe them, or give a reference link to a description.</p>	<p>.....</p>
<p>Are there aggregators⁷² active on the market? If yes, could you give us contact addresses or an Internet link for contact addresses?</p>	<p>.....</p>

⁷¹ DSO grid services are to be understood as services demanded by the DSO. These are to be distinguished from TSO grid services such as balancing services (FCR, FRR, RR). The latter ones are dealt with in a separate survey.

⁷² 'Aggregator' is to be understood as the legal entity responsible for the operation of a number of power generating modules and/or demand facilities by means of aggregation for the purpose of offering grid services.

Part D: Remarks

Your contact data for further enquiries

First name	
Surname	
Company	
Company	
Address	
Email	
Telephone number	

Appendix

This page can be used in case you need space for additional services.

Simplified equivalent circuit of a service providing unit: the load may be varied on demand within seconds. The load is connected to the grid through an AC/DC converter. Detailed specifications may be fitted for a specific service.

1 year = 8000 operational hours

Question	Service: Voltage Control	Service:	Service
Short description of the service [Text]

10.4 Appendix – Survey Results TSO

Load accessibility for different products in different EU countries

Non-rotating mass accessibility for different products in EU countries

Possibility of aggregation

Product shape (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)

10.5 Appendix – Survey Results DSO

Summary of key statements and conclusions from the DSO survey

Country/ DSO	Statements	Summary	Described products	Remuneration	Contractual situation
Bulgaria/ CEZ Distribution Bulgaria	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) In Bulgaria there is specific split of the network. For the most part our network consists of single MV feeders. HV lines and more of substations 110 kV/MV are Bulgarian TSO's property. 2) According to legislation we as a DSO cannot operate in real time the RES. 3) Voltage regulation in the distribution network, as part of voltage and reactive power management in the Power system, is tertiary regulation. This is done by changing the transform coefficient (switching under load of the tap changer) of the transformers in the substations 110 kV/MV. 4) We receive fixed prices first for access to the distribution network (based on installed power) and second for electricity transmission through the network (based on consumption). The TSO provides network balancing. 	<p>Survey not filled in, Most part of DSO grid consists of single MV feeders; according to legislation DSO cannot operate RES in real time; Voltage regulation is tertiary regulation (on-load tap changing at 110 kV/MV); TSO provides network balancing</p>	Voltage regulation	-	Voltage regulation is tertiary regulation. TSO provides network balancing.
Czech Republic/ CEZ Distribuce	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Possible future grid services are defined by Clean Energy Package introduced by the European Commission. DSOs will be allowed to procure only non-frequency ancillary services. However, it's expected 	<p>InterFlex WP6 flexibility requirements are foreseen for DER/EV in future without remuneration; Retailers act as</p>	Voltage control (through reactive power)	Voltage control through reactive power with limited range of	-

	<p>that CEZ Distribuce will procure only limited amount and only in places where CEZ Distribuce really needs it. At this moment ancillary service "voltage control" through reactive power is procured only from large generation connected to HV or MV grids which provide very wide range of reactive power. Voltage control through reactive is the most promising and cost-effective way for DER integration on DSO level. Moreover, voltage control through reactive power with limited range of reactive power is compulsory for all new generation as the requirement for connections without any remuneration (no payments from DSO to generation for this feature). Decrease of loads in case of Czech Republic is already solved by demand response system (through narrow band simple one-way PLC communication) which directly controls significant loads and change on-peak and off-peak electricity prices.</p> <p>2) InterFlex - WP6: focus on flexibility on DER and EV side. Flexibility is foreseen as a future requirement for new connection of DER or EV without any remuneration.</p> <p>3) Aggregation of loads or generation is done by retailers. No special entity foreseen in Clean Energy Package is needed in case of Czech Republic.</p> <p>4) DSO is responsible for voltage quality. This could be secured by effective voltage</p>	<p>aggregators; DR in place to deal with decreasing load; According to clean energy package DSO will only be allowed to procure non-frequency AS; Voltage control (obligation of DSO) through reactive power management from large generating assets in HV/MV grid; New generating assets are required to have reactive power control without remuneration from DSO provided.</p>		<p>reactive power is compulsory for all new generation.</p>	
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	<p>regualtion through ractive power. Voltage control through reactive is the most promising and cost effective way for DER integration on DSO level.</p> <p>5) Decrease of loads in case of Czech Republic is already solved by demand response system.</p>				
Germany/ E-On	-	No answer received.	-	-	-
Ireland/ ESB Networks	1) Suggest contact EirGrid, as they are the Market Operator. ESB networks, as DSO has no contractual relationship with aggregators.	Does not perceive flexible high power load as valuable.	-	-	ESB networks (DSO) has no contractual relationship with EirGrid (TSO).
Latvia/ Sadales tikls AS	<p>1) We don't have significant impact from distributed generation or problems with network capacity.</p> <p>2) No, no business cases yet</p> <p>3) Congestion & capacity management are provided by TSO, voltage regulation in MV are provided with local regulation of transformer voltage output if necessary.</p> <p>4) Latvia does not have a significant number of DG units or problems with work capacity - This is the reason why as DSO we don't work to create flexibility services yet.</p>	Congestion & capacity management are provided by TSO. Small number of distributed generating units, no need to create flexibility services yet.	Voltage regulation in MV are provided with local regulation of transformer voltage output if necessary.	-	-
Slovenia/ Regional distribution company: Elektro-Gorenjska	<p>1) Elektro-Gorenjska has not yet been involved in DSO grid services.</p> <p>2) No aggregators are active in DSO grid services provision.</p>	No aggregators are active in DSO grid services provision	-	-	-

<p>Spain/ endesa</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Unfortunately, in the Iberian Peninsula (Spain + Portugal) the effective participation of demand in the provision of ancillary services is still not allowed, so the questions are not applicable. 2) In my opinion, the basic principle of the design of any service should be that all suppliers participate in equal conditions for the same product. In this sense, if the participation of demand in ancillary services were allowed in Spain or Portugal, no payment for capacity (€/MW/ yr) in congestion management would be justified until the same scheme were implemented for generators and both (generators & demand) would be able to participate in a transparent and competitive allocation process (currently we have only a short-term mechanism that only rewards the energy actually requested - €/MWh). The same principle would apply in the services of voltage control or primary regulation (FCR) that are currently being provided by generators in a mandatory and unpaid scheme. 3) No specific services have been developed for the distribution network that could be covered in the future by demand aggregators. 	<p>No specific services have been developed for the distribution network that could be covered in the future by demand aggregators.</p>	<p>-</p>	<p>-</p>	<p>-</p>
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10.6 Appendix – PESTEL Analysis

PESTEL stands for analyzing **P**olitical, **E**conomic, **S**ocial, **T**echnical, **E**nvironmental and **L**egal factors. We looked at the factors of a `classical` PESTEL-Analysis that could have consequences for the implementation of WEs in grid services. The relevant factors – mainly economic and environmental ones - were analysed based on literature search and available pricing. Data we are referencing is from 2016 or newer.

Risks and chances corresponding to each factor are identified, trends are derived and potential consequences for the use of WEs in grid services are summarized.

Summary of trends and consequences of the environment on the implementation of WEs for grid services base on the details given in the next table.

factor	country	trends	possible consequences on the implementation of WEs for grid services
economic factors: energy demand, energy pricing	Europe	→ electricity demand globally projected to grow by 60% by 2040; this has to be aligned with the goals for shares of RES → electricity demand and economic growth correlate less strongly	Decoupling of electricity demand and economic growth is driven by structural transformation; WEs could support this transformation.
economic factors: grid services market transparency	Nordic countries/ Finland/D enmark	→ increased market transparency could enhance business opportunities in the grid services markets → Finland the first to implement the 15-minute trade period in electricity market, this enables producers to balance the electricity system in real time → increased transparency also in Denmark	Improved transparency could help to implement WEs providing balancing energy in the Nordic countries
economic factors: H2-industrial-market volume & pricing	Europe	→ pricing in industry not transparent; this hinders market entrance → high transmission costs of hydrogen could foster WEs as they provide scalable local production	The current status favors providing regulating energy as main income, instead of selling hydrogen
economic factors: H2 market potential in mobility	Europe	→ there is a specific involvement of automotive industry in hydrogen → market volume between 1.7-3 Mt by 2030 → hydrogen as a technology in the mobility sector is immature and is dependent on governmental fiscal incentives and policies → the mobility H2 market is promoted by governments across Europe → mobility sector is a market where green hydrogen is valued	To sell the H2 produced by WEs, the H2-for-mobility-market is currently and also in the next years the most promising hydrogen market segment

<p>environmental factors: share in renewables</p>	<p>Europe</p>	<p>→ RES shares influence control reserve markets strongly → high RES shares correlate with positive business outlook for WEs → the amount of variable REs is further expected to grow → Germany and Spain are large producers in absolute terms → Denmark has currently the highest share of variable renewables and therefore a high need of control energy → wind power grows, and grows more important: electricity generation by wind is forecasted to reach 27% by 2040 → methods for wind power regulation/ storage of wind energy also get more important</p>	<p>WEs most promising in countries with high and growing RES shares, and specifically high variable RES shares.</p>
<p>legal</p>	<p>Denmark</p>	<p>→ subsidies for RES are discontinued in Denmark</p>	<p>No subsidies on electricity from wind in Denmark</p>

Derivation of trends from literature

country	source/literature	excerpts	trends
global			
economic factors: energy demand	IEA World Energy Outlook 2017 [116, p. 239]	Economic growth continues to be a strong driver of electricity demand growth, and prior to the global financial crisis in 2008, a 1% rise in global economic growth required an increase of close to 1% in global electricity demand. However, the link is weakening and the relationship between GDP growth and electricity demand has even been negative in certain regions after the start of the financial crisis. Globally in the New Policies Scenario, ⁷³ electricity demand is projected to grow by 60%, while GDP grows by 124% by 2040, meaning that less electricity is required to produce each unit of economic output than in the past. Decoupling of electricity demand and economic growth is driven by structural transformation and by enhanced energy efficiency efforts globally.	→ electricity demand globally projected to grow by 60% by 2040; this has to be aligned with the goals for shares of RES → electricity demand and economic growth correlate less strongly
economic factors: H2 pricing	CertifHy Project [37] IEA Technology Roadmap H2 2015 [117, p. 37]	2018, hydrogen market splits in 3 segments: (mostly captive) H2 in industry (95%), merchant H2 (4%) and emerging applications such as in mobility (<1%). Pricing in industry is not transparent, also because trading is taking place bilaterally with individualized contracts rather than in organized exchange type of markets with standardized contracts, but current prices are estimated to be around 10-60 €/kg depending on the purity level and the location of consumption. Transmission costs of around USD 50 per MWh occur if hydrogen needs to be transported over a longer distance of 100 km; by comparison, if a shorter distance of 50 km is seen, transport amounts to USD 25 per MWh. Adding the transmission costs to the generation costs for centrally produced hydrogen using natural gas at USD 40/MWh together with SMR and CCS, renewable hydrogen could be cost competitive if produced from electricity at prices of up to USD 20/MWh and at lower annual utilisation factors of around 15%. Alternatively, electricity prices of up to USD 60/MWh at high	→ pricing in industry not transparent; this hinders market entrance → high transmission costs of hydrogen could foster WEs as they provide scalable local production → hydrogen from WEs requires low-cost RES electricity and a combination of higher natural gas and carbon prices to be cost-competitive → hydrogen production costs by employing WEs depend on the annual

⁷³ The *New Policies Scenario* incorporates not just the policies and measures that governments around the world have already put in place, but also the likely effects of announced policies, as expressed in official targets or plans. The Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) made for the Paris Agreement provide important guidance as to these policy intentions in many countries, although in some cases these are now supplemented or superseded by more recent announcements – including the decision by the US administration to withdraw from the Agreement. Our reading of the national policy environment is also influenced by policies and targets adopted by sub-national authorities, i.e. by state-level entities in federal systems, by cities and municipalities, as well as the commitments made by the private sector.

		annual utilisation factors of around 80% would also result in cost competitiveness.	utilisation factor of the WEs
H2 market volume	ELYntegration D6.4 [50]	Global H2 demand was estimated at 43 Mt, while the European H2 demand accounted for around 16% of the global hydrogen demand (6.9 Mt/year, 2010). The industry sector accounts for more than 90% of the hydrogen demand within Europe (6.2 Mt/year). Within the industry sector, 63% of hydrogen demand originates in the chemical industry, around 31% in the crude refinery industry and 6% in the metal processing industry. Less than 1% of hydrogen consumption is used in liquefied form e.g. for rocket and automotive fuels.	→ as volume is very small, the current status might favor providing regulating energy as main income, instead of selling hydrogen
H2 market potential in mobility	IEA on hydrogen [38] CertifHy Project [37, pp. 15-17] ELYntegration D6.4 [50, p. 16]	The hydrogen energy business is building on the foundation of the global industrial gas business with support from global automotive manufacturers (such as Toyota, Hyundai, Honda, Daimler, BMW), which have developed FCEVs. H2 demand in mobility between 1.7-3 Mt by 2030. Projected share of fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs) in Europe between 7 and 12% by 2030.	→ there is a specific involvement of automotive industry in hydrogen →market volume between 1.7-3 Mt by 2030
H2 pricing in mobility	CertifHy Project [37] IEA on hydrogen [38]	Hydrogen in mobility is sold for 10 €/kg in Switzerland; for 9.50 €/kg in Germany and for 9.00 €/kg in Austria. The current retail price in european countries is in general about 10 €/kg, while prices could be 5-7 €/kg by 2030. In 2016, there were 220 HRS's worldwide, thereof 35 in Germany, 10 in Denmark, 4 each in Austria and the UK, 1 in Switzerland.	→ hydrogen as a technology in the mobility sector is immature and is dependent on governmental fiscal incentives and policies
Europe			
political/legal factors: H2 in mobility	ELYntegration D6.4 [50]	A promising market for the sales of hydrogen might be the mobility sector where hydrogen is used as a fuel as there are several initiatives in Europe to promote hydrogen mobility. However, an estimation of future hydrogen demand within this sector is challenging because of high uncertainties of its future development. This is due to competition by other alternatives to combustion engine vehicles and high dependencies on national legislation in terms of funding support for fuel	→ this market is promoted by governments across Europe

		cell electric vehicles and hydrogen refuelling stations.	
economic factors: H2 in mobility	ELYntegration D6.4 [50, p. 15]	Many studies indicate that the mobility sector might be the key sector that may generate substantial growth and demand for green hydrogen thus representing one of the main target sectors for hydrogen generated by electrolyser applications.	→ mobility sector is a market where `green`/low-carbon hydrogen is valued
environmental factors: current share in renewables	IEA Renewables Information 2017 [118, p. table 8]	shares of electricity production from renewables, excluding hydro power: 2016 in OECD Europe: 17.2% Austria: 16.5% Denmark: 60.6% Finland: 21.5% France: 6.7% Germany: 26.0% Greece: 19.1% Ireland: 22.1% Italy: 23.6% Netherlands: 12.9% Norway: 1.5% Poland: 12.4% Slovenia: 3.4% Spain: 25.2% Sweden: 16.8% Switzerland: 5.2% UK: 23.1%	→ Denmark has currently the highest share of variable renewables and a high need of control energy
environmental factors: share in renewables simulated for 2034	ELYntegration D2.3 [50]	shares of electricity production from renewables, excluding hydro power: 2034 in OECD Europe: Austria: 27% Denmark: 75% Finland: 29% France: 22% Germany: 43% Greece: Ireland: Italy: Netherlands: 35% Norway: 50% Poland: Slovenia: Spain: Sweden: Switzerland: UK: 20%	→ In 2034, Denmark and Norway will presumably have high variable RES shares

	IEA Renewables Information 2017 [118, p. 15]	In 2016, wind grew by 25.9% per annum in OECD Europe. Between 1990 and 2016, wind power increased from 3.8 TWh to 599.4 TWh, achieving an average annual growth rate of 21.4%. This is the second fastest growth rate of renewable electricity after solar photovoltaic. In absolute terms, the United States, Germany and Spain are the largest producers of electricity from wind within the OECD, producing 229.3 TWh, 77.4 TWh and 48.9 TWh respectively.	→ the amount of variable REs is further expected to grow → Germany and Spain are large producers in absolute terms
	IEA World Energy Outlook 2016 [116, p. 231]	The European Union, notably Germany and France, continues to be among the global leaders in wind power, adding 13 GW in 2016. Global wind power capacity additions were 52 GW in 2016, down about 20% from 2015.	
	IEA World Energy Outlook 2016 [116]	Wind power surpasses nuclear to become the second-largest low-carbon source of electricity by 2040. It plays the largest role in the European Union, reaching 27% of generation in 2040 due the strong growth of both onshore and off-shore wind.	→ wind power grows, and grows more important → methods for wind power regulation/storage of wind energy also get more important
Northern Europe			
economic factors: announced changes in the regulating energy markets	Fingrid Annual Report 2017 [17]	The European electricity market is in the process of introducing a shorter, 15-minute trade period. The relevant legislation, which came into force in December 2017, requires the introduction of a 15-minute trade period in late 2020, unless the roll-out is postponed by a decision by the authorities. Finnish TSO Fingrid has started an imbalance settlement project for the 15-minute period, Fingrid's objective is to create new opportunities for electricity market operators to participate in balancing the electricity system in real time. As an imbalance power model, this would mean a one-price system, in which the price of imbalance power would be available to the electricity market operators in real time. Fingrid wants to harmonize the imbalance power pricing in the Nordic countries.	→Finland the first to implement the 15-minute trade period in electricity market, this enables producers to balance the electricity system in real time

<p>economic factors: grid services market transparency</p>	<p>Fingrid Annual Report 2017 [17]</p>	<p>In order to increase market transparency, Fingrid implemented, in the winter of 2016–2017, a pilot project on the publication of balancing market prices during scarcity situations. The project resulted in a decision by Fingrid to continue publishing real-time prices during scarcity of up-grid services. In late 2017, Fingrid expanded the publication of prices to cover real-time price information for down-grid services as well.</p>	<p>→ increased market transparency could enhance business opportunities in the grid services markets</p>
	<p>Fingrid Annual Report 2017 [17]</p>	<p>Reserves required to maintain the power balance of the electricity system were procured from Finland, the other Nordic countries, the Baltic countries and Russia. Countertrade costs amounted to EUR 3.9 (1.8 in 2017) million.</p>	<p>→ countertrade market volume: 3.9 million EUR</p>
<p>legal aspects: announced changes</p>	<p>National Report Danish Energy Regulating Authority (DERA) 2017 [19]</p>	<p>In November 2016, the Danish parliament passed new legislation concerning the PSO (public service obligations) payment, which covers subsidies for renewable energy and energy research. According to new regulation, the current PSO payment will gradually be reduced from 2017 and is abolished in 2022 for all electricity consumers. The costs of PSO will instead be financed by the government's annual budget.</p>	<p>→ subsidies for RES are discontinued in Denmark</p>
		<p>Legislation from June 2015 has obliged DERA to operate a new national online portal for electricity prices, which was launched on 1 April 2016. According to executive order No. 1279 of 25 October 2016, all prices/products offered at the electricity market for consumers with an annual consumption below 100,000 kWh have to be reported to the new price comparison tool (PCT). The PCT is called elpris.dk, and it is operated by DERA.</p>	<p>→ increased transparency also in Denmark</p>

specifically Finland	Government report on the National Energy and Climate Strategy for 2030 [18]	The TSO grid service system will be preserved and developed towards greater flexibility. It will be justified to increase the TSO grid service subjected to a tendering process by the Energy Authority from the current 299 MW to some 600 MW.	→in Finland balancing market volume doubles
Denmark			
economic factors: electricity pricing	-Statista -National Report Danish Energy Regulating Authority (DERA) 2017 [19]	In Denmark, 2016 the end user price for electricity in industry was 0.0942 €/kWh, thereof the energy costs were 0.028 €/kWh. Grid charges amounted to 0.058 €/kWh. The VAT amounts to 0.062 €/kWh. There is a charge by the government to promote REs of 0.15 €/kWh that is paid by all consumers.	
	IEA on hydrogen [38]	The current leaders in the use for PtG and mobility are: Japan, California (United States) and Germany, followed by the United Kingdom, South Korea, and Denmark. Each leader has its own strategy and implementation plans.	→ Germany, UK, and Denmark leaders in H2 for PtG and mobility
environmental factors: shares in renewables	Energinet Environmental Report 2017 [119]	By 2016, Denmark had a total share of RES of 61.7%. (net generation), a share of electricity generated by biofuels and waste of just under 17% and a share of electricity generated by wind of 44% (12.78 GWh). Thereof 4.65 GWh were produced by offshore wind turbines. The RES share of electricity generation in Denmark is expected to be increased to approx. 87% until 2026. The increase in RE generation is primarily expected to come from an increased expansion of wind power as well as the conversion of a number of central power stations to wood firing. In 2026, wind power is expected to account for about 66% of total electricity generation from RE sources.	→Denmark has currently a 44% share of electricity generation by wind that is expected to grow to 66% until 2026
Finland			
economic factors: electricity pricing	Table 1, Energy Authority Finland [120]	In Finland, 2016 the end user price for electricity in industry was 0.069 €/kWh, thereof the energy costs were 0.027€/kWh. Grid charges amounted to 0.004 €/kWh, taxes to 0.007 €/kWh. The government promotes REs by a subsidy in form of a feed-in tariff of 0-0.018 €/kWh.	

environmental factors: shares in renewables	Statistics Finland [121]	Finland has a total share of 45% of RES in electricity production, thereof 24% hydro power. Wind accounted 2016 for 5%. Finland imported 22% of its electricity in 2016.	
Switzerland			
economic factors: electricity pricing	Swiss electricity statistics 2016 [122]	In Switzerland, 2016 the end user price for electricity in industry was 0.156 €/kWh, thereof the energy costs were 0.0587 €/kWh. Grid charges amounted to 0.0835 €/kWh. There is a charge by the government to promote REs of 0.0119 €/kWh that is paid by all consumers. Subsidies for WEs do not exist.	
environmental factors: share of RES, energy storage capacities	Swiss electricity statistics 2016 [90] Weekly reports: water levels of reservoirs [123]	In 2016, Switzerland had a total share of RES of 64.1%, thereof 59% hydro power. Switzerland has ideal geologic conditions for hydro power and storage of electricity by pump hydro stations. 2016, the country had a storage capacity of 8.805 TWh by pumped hydro energy storage (PHES), which corresponds to 15% of its electricity demand. An extension of hydropower by 0,37 TWh is planned. Imports account to 6.2%.	→ Switzerland's high storage capacity by pump hydro stations lowers demand for regulating energy or storage by other means.

10.7 Appendix – Business Logic Example

The following describes the business logic for the Swiss aFRR case based on [124]. Criteria selected are defined by the business model canvas approach introduced in chapter 3.4.

In the following, a business model example is given for the provision of secondary control power in Switzerland.

Canvas example for SRL (Swiss product for aFRR) provision of a generating unit to an aggregator

Field	General description	Example
Value creation	How the value is generated.	<p>Role of the generating unit in the value chain</p> <p>Generating unit (in the sense of control reserves)</p> <p>Power trading in the free market (if the yearly electric power consumption of the water electrolyser exceeds 100 MWh).</p> <p>Way of integration of resources and capabilities in the value chain</p> <p>Generating unit provides service to the aggregator</p> <p>Aggregators have their individual requirements for generating units (generally, the requirements are less hard concerning availability and delivery period, activation time and minimum capacity than for direct provision to Swissgrid).</p> <p>Technology specific prequalification (not every plant has to be prequalified separately).</p> <p>Coordination of transactions in the value chain</p> <p>Long term cooperating contract between generating unit and aggregator under private law</p> <p>For electrical energy supply, several contracts in parallel are possible with different suppliers (can be chosen as 100% renewable (guarantee of origin)) under private law</p> <p>Grid connection is provided by the DSO based on its connection regulations under public law.</p>
Value proposition	Definition of the value an organization offers to its customers.	Quickly available (if necessary symmetrical) and permanent callable control reserve for the integration in the pool and offering to Swissgrid.
Channels	Definition of how the value is communicated and gets to the customer.	<p>Value communication</p> <p>Aggregators (2018 in CH totally 13 prequalified aggregators [125]) apply to market the control power of the individual generating unit.</p> <p>Generator can directly contact potential aggregators or set up a call for proposals.</p> <p>Value transfer</p> <p>Call via remote control</p> <p>Offers typically via web-interface of the aggregator</p>
Customers/ Market segments	Definition and value of the market segments addressed by the organization.	<p>Market segments</p> <p>Aggregator</p> <p>For generating units with capacities higher than 5 MW also direct offering to Swissgrid is possible (but this is only economically feasible for generating units with very high capacities).</p> <p>Value for the generating unit</p> <p>Availability price (yearly weighted (by the contracted power) average 2016: 40.92 Fr./MW/h) is shared between aggregator and generating unit according to their contract</p> <p>Positive utilization is reimbursed with day-ahead SwissIX+20% but at least weekly base, negative utilization is sold to the contractor for day-ahead SwissIX-20% but not more than weekly base. With an average</p>

		<p>yearly market price [65] of 37.68 €/MWh the average profit from activation (with a call probability of 100%) is approximately:</p> $\text{Approximate average yearly profit from SRL} = 37.68 * 1.2 - 37.68 = \frac{7.5\text{€}}{\text{MWh}}$ <p>This value is shared between the aggregator and the generating unit according to the individual contract.</p>
Value capture	Definition of how earning is generated out of the value which the organization provides to its customers.	<p>Customer value</p> <p>Generating unit as part of the pool.</p> <p>Aggregator can define its own call strategy.</p> <p>Advantages of water electrolyser technology which are credible with the test protocols (technical and economical properties), economic advantage is measurable with the marginal cost of a call.</p> <p>Organisation value</p> <p>Profit from the activation bases on the difference between activation price and energy price.</p>
Value dissemination	How the earning is distributed between the stakeholders.	Revenue of availability and activation is shared between aggregator and generating unit according to their contract.
Value developments	Description of how the organization develops the value within the scope of the business model. How sustainability is achieved through development of the business logic.	<p>The product is developed further to comply with international standardized products. Relevant regulations and the ongoing energy market development will be taken into account. The product should be as flexible and non-discriminatory as possible. [126]</p> <p>The product SCR will be developed as follows [126]:</p> <p>2013: Increasing of the participation possibility for small generating units and controllable loads through the pooling concept.</p> <p>2014-2017: SCR and TCR can be procured on a weekly basis in a combined call for tenders. The bids for SCR and TCR are selected in light of the anticipated costs for daily tenders by stochastic optimisation. With that distribution between SCR and TCR procurement volumes and between weekly and daily tenders can be optimized. For example, if lower prices are expected in daily tenders, less power will be contracted in the weekly tendering process.</p> <p>2018/2019: Reduction of the market barriers through cancellation of symmetrical provision.</p> <p>2020: Reduction of the market barriers through introduction of SCR daily product that makes it possible to offer flexibility that is only available for short time.</p> <p>2020: New pricing mechanism to improve market liquidity and price signals by harmonizing prices for balance energy and control energy and to create incentives for an efficient balancing mechanism.</p> <p>2022: Ensuring compatibility with standard product for enabling netting and internationally coordinated requests. Go-live of aFRR platform.</p>

10.8 Appendix – Multi-Criteria Evaluation Details

Ranking including the criterion ‘Future H₂ market potential’

Ranked grid service products for scenario 1) (remuneration from activation is ignored)

Scenario 1): ignored activation								
Asymmetric negativ			Asymmetric positiv			Symmetric only		
Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score
1	Germany mFRR-	7.5	1	Germany aFRR+	7.6	1	Germany FCR (symmetric)	7.6
2	Germany aFRR-	7.5	2	Germany mFRR+	7.5	2	UK FFR (symmetric)	6.4
3	UK RR-	6.4	3	UK RR+	6.4	3	Finland FCR-N (hourly, symmetric)	5.3
4	Finland aFRR-	5.3	4	Finland FCR-D+ (hourly)	5.5	4	Netherlands FCR (symmetric)	5.2
5	Netherlands aFRR-	5.2	5	Finland aFRR+	5.4	5	Finland FCR-N (yearly, symmetric)	5.1
6	Netherlands mFRRda-	5.1	6	Netherlands aFRR+ (symmetric)	5.2	6	Austria FCR (symmetric)	5.0
7	Denmark FCR- (DK1, daily)	5.0	7	Netherlands mFRRda+	5.1	7	Denmark aFRR (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	4.9
8	Austria aFRR- (weekly average)	4.9	8	Finland FCR-D+ (yearly)	5.0	8	Norway FCR-N (symmetric)	4.9
9	Austria mFRR- (weekly average)	4.9	9	Finland mFRR+	5.0	9	Denmark FCR-N (DK2, yearly, symmetric)	4.3
10	Denmark aFRR- (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	4.9	10	Austria mFRR+ (weekly average)	4.9	10	Switzerland aFRR (symmetric)	3.9
11	Sweden mFRR- (SE1-SE4)	4.7	11	Austria aFRR+ (weekly average)	4.9	11	Switzerland FCR (symmetric)	3.6
12	Norway aFRR-	4.1	12	Denmark aFRR+ (symmetric)	4.9	12	France aFRR (symmetric)	2.3
13	Denmark mFRR- (DK1, DK2)	4.1	13	Sweden mFRR+ (SE1-SE4)	4.7			
14	Norway mFRR-	4.0	14	Denmark FCR+ (DK1, daily)	4.4			
15	Switzerland aFRR- (symmetric)	3.9	15	Denmark FCR-D+ (DK2, yearly)	4.2			
16	Slovenia mFRR-	3.7	16	Norway aFRR+	4.1			
17	Slovenia RR-	3.6	17	Denmark mFRR+ (DK1)	4.1			
18	Switzerland mFRR- (weekly)	3.6	18	Norway mFRR+	4.0			
19	France aFRR- (symmetric)	2.3	19	Switzerland aFRR+ (symmetric)	3.9			
20			20	Slovenia mFRR+	3.7			
21			21	Slovenia RR+	3.6			
22			22	Switzerland mFRR+ (weekly)	3.6			
23			23	France aFRR+ (symmetric)	2.3			
			24	France mFRR+	2.1			
			25	France RR+	2.1			

Ranked grid service products for scenario 2) (remuneration from activation is considered where known). The impact of scenario 3) simulation is shown as blh = black horse; blh->x indicates the ranking improvement for scenario 3, where products with unknown activation probability are treated as if they had the same activation probability as the highest one.

Scenario 2): activation + availability								
Asymmetric negativ			Asymmetric positiv			Symmetric only		
Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score
1	Germany aFRR-	7.5	1	Germany aFRR+	7.6	1	Germany FCR (symmetric)	7.6
2	Germany mFRR-	7.5	2	Germany mFRR+	7.5	2	UK FFR (symmetric)	6.4
3	UK RR-	6.4	3	UK RR+	6.4	3	Finland FCR-N (hourly, symmetric)	5.3
4	Finland aFRR-	5.3	4	Finland FCR-D (hourly)+	5.5	4	Netherlands FCR (symmetric)	5.2
5	Sweden mFRR- SE1	5.3	5, blh ->4	Finland aFRR+	5.4	5, blh ->4	Finland FCR-N (yearly, symmetric)	5.1
6	Sweden mFRR- SE2	5.3	6	Sweden mFRR+ (SE1)	5.3	6	Austria FCR (symmetric)	5.0
7	Sweden mFRR- SE3	5.3	7	Sweden mFRR+ (SE2)	5.3	7	Denmark aFRR (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	4.9
8	Sweden mFRR- SE4	5.3	8	Sweden mFRR+ (SE3)	5.3	8	Denmark FCR-N (yearly, DK2, symmetric)	4.3
9	Netherlands aFRR- (symmetrical)	5.2	9, blh ->7	Sweden mFRR+ (SE4)	5.3	9	Norway FCR-N (symmetric)	4.0
10	Netherlands mFRR-	5.1	10	Netherlands aFRR+	5.2	10, blh ->9	Switzerland aFRR (symmetric)	3.9
11	Finland mFRR-	5.0	11	Netherlands mFRRda+	5.1	11	Switzerland FCR (symmetric)	3.6
12	Norway aFRR-	5.0	12	Finland FCR-D (yearly)+	5.0	12	France aFRR (symmetric)	2.3
13, blh ->10	Austria aFRR- (weekly average)	4.9	13, blh ->12	Finland mFRR+	5.0			
14, blh ->4	Austria mFRR- (weekly average)	4.9	14	Norway aFRR+	5.0			
	Denmark aFRR- (DK1 & DK2) (symmetrical)	4.9	15, blh ->5	Austria mFRR+ (weekly average)	4.9			
16, blh ->15	Norway mFRR-	4.8	16, blh ->11	Austria aFRR+ (weekly average)	4.9			
	Denmark FCR- (DK1, daily)	4.1	17	Denmark aFRR+ (symmetric)	4.9			
18, blh ->17	Denmark mFRR- (DK2)	4.1	18	Norway mFRR+	4.9			
19	Switzerland aFRR- (symmetrical)	3.9	19	Denmark FCR+ (DK1, daily)	4.4			
20	Slovenia mFRR-	3.7	20	Denmark FCR-D+ (DK2, yearly)	4.2			
21	Switzerland mFRR- (Weekly)	3.7	21	Denmark mFRR+ (DK1)	4.1			
22, blh ->20	Slovenia RR-	3.6	22	Switzerland aFRR+ (symmetric)	3.9			
23	France aFRR- (symmetrical)	2.3	23	Slovenia mFRR+	3.7			
24			24	Slovenia RR+	3.6			
25			25	Switzerland mFRR+ (weekly)	3.6			
26			26	France aFRR+ (symmetric)	2.3			
27			27	France mFRR+	2.1			
			28	France RR+	2.1			

Ranked grid service products for scenario 3), black horse (remuneration from activation is considered where activation probability is known, and calculated with max. activation probability of 23% elsewhere).

Scenario 3) Black horse								
Asymmetric negativ			Asymmetric positiv			Symmetric only		
Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Rank	Rank	Country/Product	Rank
1	Germany aFRR-	7.5	1	Germany aFRR+	7.6	1	Germany FCR (symmetric)	7.7
2	Germany mFRR-	7.5	2	Germany mFRR+	7.5	2	UK FFR (symmetric)	6.5
3	UK RR-	6.4	3	UK RR+	6.7	3	Finland FCR-N (hourly, symmetric)	5.8
4	Austria mFRR- (weekly average)	5.8	4	Finland aFRR+	5.5	4	Finland FCR-N (yearly, symmetric)	5.5
5	Sweden mFRR- SE1	5.3	5	Austria mFRR+ (weekly average)	5.5	5	Netherlands FCR (symmetric)	5.3
6	Sweden mFRR- SE2	5.3	6	Finland FCR-D (hourly)+	5.5	6	Austria FCR (symmetric)	5.2
7	Sweden mFRR- SE3	5.3	7	Sweden mFRR+ (SE4)	5.4	7	Denmark aFRR (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	4.5
8	Sweden mFRR- SE4	5.3	8	Sweden mFRR+ (SE3)	5.3	8	Denmark FCR-N (yearly, DK2, symmetric)	4.5
9	Finland aFRR-	5.2	9	Sweden mFRR+ (SE1)	5.3	9	Switzerland aFRR (symmetric)	4.2
10	Austria aFRR- (weekly average)	5.2	10	Sweden mFRR+ (SE2)	5.3	10	Norway FCR-N (symmetric)	4.0
11	Netherlands aFRR- (symmetrical)	5.1	11	Austria aFRR+ (weekly average)	5.2	11	Switzerland FCR (symmetric)	3.8
12	Netherlands mFRR-	5.1	12	Finland mFRR+	5.2	12	France aFRR (symmetric)	2.5
13	Finland mFRR-	5.0	13	Netherlands aFRR+	5.2	13		
14	Norway aFRR-	4.9	14	Netherlands mFRRda+	5.1	14		
15	Norway mFRR-	4.8	15	Finland FCR-D (yearly)+	5.0	15		
16	Denmark aFRR- (DK1 & DK2) (symmetrical)	4.7	16	Norway aFRR+	5.0			
17	Denmark mFRR- (DK2)	4.4	17	Denmark aFRR+ (symmetric)	4.9			
18	Denmark FCR- (DK1, daily)	4.1	18	Norway mFRR+	4.9			
19	Switzerland aFRR- (symmetrical)	3.8	19	Denmark FCR+ (DK1, daily)	4.4			
20	Slovenia RR-	3.7	20	Denmark FCR-D+ (DK2, yearly)	4.2			
21	Slovenia mFRR-	3.7	21	Denmark mFRR+ (DK1)	4.1			
22	Switzerland mFRR- (Weekly)	3.6	22	Switzerland aFRR+ (symmetric)	3.9			
23	France aFRR- (symmetrical)	2.3	23	Slovenia mFRR+	3.7			
24			24	Slovenia RR+	3.6			
25			25	Switzerland mFRR+ (weekly)	3.6			
			26	France aFRR+ (symmetric)	2.2			
			27	France mFRR+	2.2			
			28	France RR+	2.2			

Ranking excluding the criterion ‘Future H₂ market potential’

Ranked grid service products for the case remuneration from activation is ignored, and the factor Future H₂ market potential is excluded from the evaluation

Asymmetrical negativ			Asymmetrical positiv			Symmetrical only		
Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score
1	Germany mFRR-	4.6	1	Finland FCR-D+ hourly	4.8	1	Norway FCR-N (symmetric)	4.9
2	Germany aFRR-	4.6	2	Germany aFRR+	4.7	2	Germany FCR (symmetric)	4.7
3	Finland aFRR-	4.6	3	Finland aFRR+	4.7	3	Finland FCR-N (hourly, symmetric)	4.5
4	Netherlands aFRR- (symmetrical)	4.4	4	Germany mFRR+	4.6	4	Netherlands FCR (symmetric)	4.5
5	Netherlands mFRRda-	4.3	5	Netherlands aFRR+	4.4	5	Finland FCR-N (yearly, symmetric)	4.4
6	Norway aFRR-	4.1	6	Netherlands mFRRda+	4.4	6	Switzerland aFRR (symmetric)	3.9
7	Norway mFRR-	4.0	7	Finland FCR-D+ yearly	4.3	7	Switzerland FCR (symmetric)	3.6
8	Switzerland aFRR- (symmetrical)	3.9	8	Finland mFRR+	4.3	8	Austria FCR (symmetric)	3.6
9	Slovenia mFRR-	3.7	9	Norway aFRR+	4.1	9	UK FFR (symmetric)	3.5
10	Slovenia RR-	3.6	10	Norway mFRR+	4.0	10	Denmark aFRR (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	3.5
11	Switzerland mFRR- (weekly)	3.6	11	Switzerland aFRR+ (symmetrical)	3.9	11	Denmark FCR-N (DK2, yearly, symmetric)	2.9
12	Denmark FCR- (DK1)	3.5	12	Slovenia mFRR+	3.7	12	France aFRR (symmetric)	1.6
13	UK RR-	3.5	13	Slovenia RR+	3.6			
14	Austria aFRR- (weekly average)	3.5	14	Switzerland mFRR+ (week)	3.6			
15	Austria mFRR- (weekly average)	3.5	15	UK RR+	3.5			
16	Denmark aFRR- (DK1 & DK2) (symmetrical)	3.5	16	Austria mFRR+ (weekly average)	3.5			
17	Sweden mFRR- (SE1-SE4)	3.3	17	Austria aFRR+ (weekly average)	3.5			
18	Denmark mFRR- (DK1 & DK2)	2.6	18	Denmark aFRR+ (symmetrical)	3.5			
19	France aFRR- (symmetrical)	1.6	19	Sweden mFRR+ SE1-SE4	3.3			
20			20	Denmark FCR+ (DK1) daily	3.0			
21			21	Denmark FCR-D+ (DK2) yearly	2.7			
			22	Denmark mFRR+ (DK1)	2.6			
			23	France aFRR+ (symmetrical)	1.6			
			24	France mFRR+	1.4			
			25	France RR+	1.4			

Ranked grid service products for the case remuneration from activation considered, and the factor Future H₂ market potential is excluded

Asymmetrical negativ			Asymmetrical positiv			Symmetrical only		
Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score	Rank	Country/Product	Score
1	Norway aFRR-	5.0	1	Norway aFRR+	5.0	1	Germany FCR (symmetric)	4.7
2	Norway mFRR-	4.8	2	Norway mFRR+	4.9	2	Finland FCR-N (hourly, symmetric)	4.5
3	Germany aFRR-	4.7	3	Finland FCR-D (hourly)+	4.8	3	Netherlands FCR (symmetric)	4.5
4	Germany mFRR-	4.6	4	Germany aFRR+	4.7	4	Finland FCR-N (yearly, symmetric)	4.4
5	Finland aFRR-	4.6	5	Finland aFRR+	4.7	5	Norway FCR-N (symmetric)	4.0
6	Netherlands aFRR- (symmetrical)	4.4	6	Germany mFRR+	4.6	6	Switzerland aFRR (symmetric)	3.9
7	Netherlands mFRR-	4.3	7	Netherlands aFRR+ (symmetric)	4.4	7	Switzerland FCR (symmetric)	3.6
8	Finland mFRR-	4.3	8	Netherlands mFRRda+	4.4	8	Austria FCR (symmetric)	3.6
9	Switzerland aFRR- (symmetrical)	3.9	9	Finland FCR-D (Yearly)+	4.3	9	UK FFR (symmetric)	3.5
10	Sweden mFRR- SE1	3.8	10	Finland mFRR+	4.3	10	Denmark aFRR (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	3.5
11	Sweden mFRR- SE2	3.8	11	Switzerland aFRR+ (symmetric)	3.9	11	Denmark FCR-N (yearly, DK2, symmetric)	2.8
12	Sweden mFRR- SE3	3.8	12	Sweden mFRR+ SE1	3.8	12	France aFRR (symmetric)	1.6
13	Sweden mFRR- SE4	3.8	13	Sweden mFRR+ SE2	3.8	13		
14	Slovenia mFRR-	3.7	14	Sweden mFRR+ SE3	3.8	14		
15	Switzerland mFRR- (Weekly)	3.7	15	Sweden mFRR+ SE4	3.8	15		
16	Slovenia RR-	3.6	16	Slovenia mFRR+	3.7			
17	UK RR-	3.5	17	Slovenia RR+	3.6			
18	Austria aFRR- (weekly average)	3.5	18	Switzerland mFRR+ (Weekly)	3.6			
19	Austria mFRR- (weekly average)	3.5	19	UK RR+	3.5			
20	Denmark aFRR- (DK1 & DK2) (symmetrical)	3.5	20	Austria mFRR+ (weekly average)	3.5			
21	Denmark FCR- (DK1, daily)	2.7	21	Austria aFRR+ (weekly average)	3.5			
22	Denmark mFRR- (DK2)	2.6	22	Denmark aFRR+ (symmetric)	3.5			
23	France aFRR- (symmetrical)	1.6	23	Denmark FCR+ (DK1) daily	3.0			
24			24	Denmark FCR-D+ (DK2) yearly	2.7			
25			25	Denmark mFRR+ (DK1)	2.6			
			26	France aFRR+ (symmetric)	1.6			
			27	France mFRR+	1.4			
			28	France RR+	1.4			

Individual scores

Scores base on chapters 5.1, 5.2 and 5.3. Scales base on chapter 3.1, Table 2.

Individual scores for scenario 1), symmetric services.

Scenario 1) (ignored activation), symmetric services																
Country / Product	EVA of the grid service			Availability of information		RES potential			Aggregation is possible		Electricity price level			Future H2 market potential		Total score scenario 1)
	Availability price €/MW/h	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Future share	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Av. el. price €/MWh	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	
Austria FCR (symmetric)	14.76	1.5	9.5%	6.0	28.5%	27%	3.3	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	4.5	32%	5.0
Denmark FCR-N (DK2, yearly, symmetric)	25.34	2.5	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.00	8.2	9.0%	4.5	32%	4.3
Denmark aFRR (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	90	9.0	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.00	8.2	9.0%	4.5	32%	4.9
Finland FCR-N (yearly, symmetric)	17.42	1.7	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	2.3	32%	5.1
Finland FCR-N (hourly, symmetric)	34.7	3.5	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	2.3	32%	5.3
France aFRR (symmetric)	20.08	2.0	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	22%	2.6	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	36.75	4.5	9.0%	2.3	32%	2.3
Netherlands FCR (symmetric)	14.91	1.5	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	35%	4.2	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.24	6.4	9.0%	2.3	32%	5.2
Norway FCR-N (symmetric)	3.44	0.3	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	50%	6.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	25.99	9.0	9.0%	0.0	32%	4.9
Switzerland FCR (symmetric)	14.63	1.5	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	37.88	4.0	9.0%	0.0	32%	3.6
Switzerland aFRR (symmetric)	37.65	3.8	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	37.88	4.0	9.0%	0.0	32%	3.9
Germany FCR (symmetric)	14.82	1.5	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	43%	5.2	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	32%	7.6
UK FFR (symmetric)	4.03	0.4	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	20%	2.4	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	47.44	0.0	9.0%	9.0	32%	6.4

Individual scores for scenarios 2) and 3), symmetric services.

Scenario 2)/3) (availability + activation), symmetric services																					
Country / Product		EVA of the grid service					RES potential			Electricity price level			Aggregation is possible		Availability of information		Future H2 market potential		Total score scenario 2)	Total score scenario 3)	
		Availability price (€/MW/h)	Activation prob. (neg.)	Activation prob. (pos.)	Profit from availability + activation €/year/MW	Score scenario 2)	Weight	Future share	Score	Weight	Av. day ahead price €/MWh	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Score			Weight
Switzerland	FCR (symmetric)	14.63			128'510	1	9.5%		0	14.5%	37.88	4	9.0%	9	6.5%	9	28.5%	0.00	32.0%	3.6	3.8
Switzerland	aFRR (symmetric)	37.6464	4.0%	5.6%	340'157	4	9.5%		0	14.5%	37.88	4	9.0%	9	6.5%	9	28.5%	0.00	32.0%	3.9	4.2
Germany	FCR (symmetric)	14.82			130'179	1	9.5%	43%	5	14.5%	28.98	8	9.0%	9	6.5%	9	28.5%	9.00	32.0%	7.6	7.7
Finland	FCR-N (yearly, symmetric)	17.42			153'017	2	9.5%	29%	3	14.5%	32.45	6	9.0%	9	6.5%	9	28.5%	2.25	32.0%	5.1	5.5
Finland	FCR-N (hourly, symmetric)	34.7			304'805	3	9.5%	29%	3	14.5%	32.45	6	9.0%	9	6.5%	9	28.5%	2.25	32.0%	5.3	5.8
Austria	FCR (symmetric)	14.76			129'652	1	9.5%	27%	3	14.5%	28.98	8	9.0%	9	6.5%	6	28.5%	4.50	32.0%	5.0	5.2
Netherlands	FCR (symmetric)	14.91			130'969	1	9.5%	35%	4	14.5%	32.24	6	9.0%	9	6.5%	9	28.5%	2.25	32.0%	5.2	5.3
France	aFRR (symmetric)	20.08			176'383	2	9.5%	22%	3	14.5%	36.75	4	9.0%	9	6.5%	0	28.5%	2.25	32.0%	2.3	2.5
Norway	FCR-N (symmetric)	3.44	19.9%	22.8%	36'723	0	9.5%		0	14.5%	25.99	9	9.0%	9	6.5%	9	28.5%	0.00	32.0%	4.0	4.0
Denmark	FCR-N (yearly, DK2, symmetric)	25.34			222'587	3	9.5%	75%	9	14.5%	29.4	8	9.0%	9	6.5%	0	28.5%	4.50	32.0%	4.3	4.5
Denmark	aFRR (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	90			790'560	9	9.5%	75%	9	14.5%	28.0	8	9.0%	9	6.5%	0	28.5%	4.50	32.0%	4.9	4.5
UK	FFR (symmetric)	4.03			35'400	0	9.5%	20%	2	14.5%	47.44	0	9.0%	9	6.5%	9	28.5%	9.00	32.0%	6.4	6.5

Individual scores for scenario 1), asymmetric negative services.

Scenario 1 (ignored activation), asymmetric negative services																	
Country / Product	EVA of the grid service			Availability of information		RES potential			Aggregation is possible		Electricity price level			Future H2 market potential		Total score scenario 1	
	Availability price €/MWh	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Future share	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Av. el. price €/MWh	Score	Weight	Score	Weight		
Austria aFRR- (weekly average)	2.1	0.4	9.5%	6.0	28.5%	27%	3.3	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.9	
Austria mFRR- (weekly average)	1.52	0.3	9.5%	6.0	28.5%	27%	3.3	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.9	
Denmark FCR- (DK1, daily)	1.56	0.3	9.5%	6.0	28.5%	27%	3.3	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.00	8.2	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	5.0	
Denmark aFRR- (DK1, DK2, symmetric)	45	9.0	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.00	8.2	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.9	
Denmark mFRR- (DK1, DK2)	0	0.0	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.00	8.2	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.1	
Finland aFRR-	19.7	3.9	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	5.3	
France aFRR- (symmetric)	10.04	2.0	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	22%	2.6	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	36.75	4.5	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	2.3	
Germany aFRR-	0.845	0.2	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	43%	5.2	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	32.0%	7.5	
Germany mFRR-	0.859	0.2	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	43%	5.2	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	32.0%	7.5	
Netherlands aFRR-	6	1.2	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	35%	4.2	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.24	6.4	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	5.2	
Netherlands mFRRda-	0	0.0	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	35%	4.2	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.24	6.4	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	5.1	
Norway aFRR-	6.78	1.4	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	25.99	9.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	4.1	
Norway mFRR-		0.0	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	25.99	9.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	4.0	
Slovenia mFRR-	4.84	1.0	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	35.60	5.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	3.7	
Slovenia RR-	0	0.0	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	35.60	5.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	3.6	
Switzerland aFRR- (symmetric)	18.825	3.8	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	37.88	4.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	3.9	
Switzerland mFRR- (weekly)	4.03	0.8	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	37.88	4.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	3.6	
Sweden mFRR- (SE1-SE4)	0	0.0	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	0.0	6.5%	28.95	7.8	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.7	
UK RR-	1.8	0.4	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	20%	2.4	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	47.44	0.0	9.0%	9.0	32.0%	6.4	

Individual scores for scenarios 2) and 3), asymmetric negative services.

Scenario 2) / 3) (availability + activation), asymmetric negative services																					
Country / Product		EVA of the grid service						RES potential			Electricity price level			Aggregation is possible		Availability of information		Future H2 market potential		Total score scenario 2)	Total score scenario 3)
		Availability price €/MW/h	Utilitsation price €/MWh	Activation prob.	Profit from availability+ activation €/year/MW	Score	Weight	Future share	Score	Weight	Av. day ahead price €/MWh	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Score	Weight		
Switzerland	aFRR- (symmetrical)	18.8232	28.91	4.0%	168'501	3.8	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	37.88	4.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	3.9	3.8
Switzerland	mFRR- (Weekly)	4.03	-65.05	3.2%	64'280	1.5	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	37.88	4.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	3.7	3.6
Slovenia	mFRR-	4.84	-180	0.0%	42'715	1.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	35.6	5.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	3.7	3.7
Slovenia	RR-	0	13		0	0.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	35.6	5.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	3.6	3.7
Finland	aFRR-	19.7	22		173'045	3.9	9.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	5.3	5.2
Finland	mFRR-	3.6	22		31'622	0.7	9.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	5.0	5.0
Germany	aFRR-	0.85	-17.22	4.3%	24'958	0.6	9.5%	43%	5.2	14.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	9.0	32.0%	7.5	7.5
Germany	mFRR-	0.9	-78.83	0.3%	10'920	0.2	9.5%	43%	5.2	14.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	9.0	32.0%	7.5	7.5
Austria	aFRR- (weekly average)	2.1	-49.61		18'446	0.4	9.5%	27%	3.3	14.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	6.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.9	5.2
Austria	mFRR- (weekly average)	1.52	-232.57		13'352	0.3	9.5%	27%	3.3	14.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	6.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.9	5.8
Netherlands	aFRR- (symmetrical)	6	16.93	0.1%	52'886	1.2	9.5%	35%	4.2	14.5%	32.24	6.4	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	5.2	5.1
Netherlands	mFRR-	0	-74	0.0%	9	0.0	9.5%	35%	4.2	14.5%	32.24	6.4	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	5.1	5.1
France	aFRR- (symmetrical)	10.04	26.38		88'191	2.0	9.5%	22%	2.6	14.5%	36.75	4.5	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	2.3	2.3
Norway	aFRR-	6.78	29.3	6.3%	64'165	1.5	9.5%	50%	6.0	14.5%	25.99	9.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	5.0	4.9
Norway	mFRR-		17.72	11.6%	8'424	0.2	9.5%	50%	6.0	14.5%	25.99	9.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	4.8	4.8
Denmark	FCR- (DK1, daily)	1.56			13'703	0.3	9.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	28	8.2	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.1	4.1
Denmark	aFRR- (DK1 & DK2) (symmetrical)	45			395'280	9.0	9.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	28	8.2	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.9	4.7
Denmark	mFRR- (DK2)	0	19.63		0	0.0	9.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	28	8.2	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.1	4.4
UK	RR-	1.8	73.08		15'811	0.4	9.5%	20%	2.4	14.5%	47.44	0.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	9.0	32.0%	6.4	6.4
Sweden	mFRR- SE1	0	20.01		0	0.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	28.95	7.8	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	5.3	5.3
Sweden	mFRR- SE2	0	20.81		0	0.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	28.95	7.8	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	5.3	5.3
Sweden	mFRR- SE3	0	20.78		0	0.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	29.24	7.6	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	5.3	5.3
Sweden	mFRR- SE4	0	24.22		0	0.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	29.53	7.5	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	5.3	5.3

Individual scores for scenario 1), asymmetric positive services.

Scenario 1 (ignored activation), asymmetric positive services																
Country / Product	EVA of the grid service			Availability of informtaion		RES potential			Aggregation is possible		Electricity price level			Future H2 market potential		Total score scenario 1
	Availability price €/MWh	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Future share	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Av. el. price €/MWh	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	
Austria aFRR+ (weekly average)	1.12	0.2	9.5%	6.0	28.5%	27%	3.3	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.9
Austria mFRR+ (weekly average)	1.25	0.3	9.5%	6.0	28.5%	27%	3.3	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.9
Denmark FCR+ (DK1, daily)	17.98	3.6	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.00	8.2	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.4
Denmark FCR-D+ (DK2, yearly)	6.18	1.2	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.00	8.2	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.2
Denmark aFRR+ (symmetric)	45	9.0	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.00	8.2	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.9
Denmark mFRR+ (DK1)	0.62	0.1	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.00	8.2	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.1
Finland FCR-D+ (yearly)	4.5	0.9	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	5.0
Finland FCR-D+ (hourly)	30.3	6.1	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	5.5
Finland aFRR+	23.4	4.7	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	5.4
Finland mFRR+	3.6	0.7	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	5.0
France aFRR+ (symmetric)	10.04	2.0	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	22%	2.6	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	36.75	4.5	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	2.3
France mFRR+	2.37	0.5	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	22%	2.6	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	36.75	4.5	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	2.1
France RR+	2.23	0.4	9.5%	0.0	28.5%	22%	2.6	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	36.75	4.5	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	2.1
Germany aFRR+	4.25	0.9	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	43%	5.2	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	32.0%	7.6
Germany mFRR+	0.982	0.2	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	43%	5.2	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	32.0%	7.5
Netherlands aFRR+ (symmetric)	6	1.2	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	35%	4.2	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.24	6.4	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	5.2
Netherlands mFRRda+	1.28	0.3	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	35%	4.2	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	32.24	6.4	9.0%	2.3	32.0%	5.1
Norway aFRR+	7.05	1.4	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	25.99	9.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	4.1
Norway mFRR+	1.44	0.3	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	25.99	9.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	4.0
Slovenia mFRR+	5.71	1.1	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	35.60	5.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	3.7
Slovenia RR+	0	0.0	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	35.60	5.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	3.6
Switzerland aFRR+ (symmetric)	18.825	3.8	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	37.88	4.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	3.9
Switzerland mFRR+ (weekly)	2.38	0.5	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	37.88	4.0	9.0%	0.0	32.0%	3.6
Sweden mFRR+ (SE1-SE4)	0	0.0	9.5%	9.0	28.5%		0.0	14.5%	0.0	6.5%	28.95	7.8	9.0%	4.5	32.0%	4.7
UK RR+	0.9	0.2	9.5%	9.0	28.5%	20%	2.4	14.5%	9.0	6.5%	47.44	0.0	9.0%	9.0	32.0%	6.4

Individual scores for scenarios 2) and 3), asymmetric positive services.

Scenario 2) / 3) (availability + activation), asymmetric positive services																				
Country / Product		EVA of the grid service					RES potential			Electricity price level			Aggregation is possible		Availability of information		Future H2 market potential		Total score scenario 2)	Total score scenario 3)
		Availability price €/MWh	Activation prob.	Profit from availability + activation €/year/MW	Score	Weight	Future share	Score	Weight	Av. day ahead price €/MWh	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Score	Weight	Score	Weight		
Switzerland	aFRR+ (symmetric)	18.8232	5.6%	171'656	3.9	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	37.88	4.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	3.9	3.9
Switzerland	mFRR+ (weekly)	2.38	2.9%	29'883	0.7	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	37.88	4.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	3.6	3.6
Slovenia	mFRR+	5.71	0.3%	53'683	1.2	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	35.6	5.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	3.7	3.7
Slovenia	RR+			0	0.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	35.6	5.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	3.6	3.6
Finland	FCR-D (yearly)+	4.5		39'528	0.9	9.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	5.0	5.0
Finland	FCR-D (hourly)+	30.3		266'155	6.1	9.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	5.5	5.5
Finland	aFRR+	23.4		205'546	4.7	9.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	5.4	5.5
Finland	mFRR+	3.6		31'622	0.7	9.5%	29%	3.4	14.5%	32.45	6.3	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	5.0	5.2
Germany	aFRR+	4.25	8.1%	55'774	1.3	9.5%	43%	5.2	14.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	9.0	32.0%	7.6	7.6
Germany	mFRR+	0.982	1.0%	15'161	0.3	9.5%	43%	5.2	14.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	9.0	32.0%	7.5	7.5
Austria	aFRR+ (weekly average)	1.12		9'838	0.2	9.5%	27%	3.3	14.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	6.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.9	5.2
Austria	mFRR+ (weekly average)	1.25		10'980	0.3	9.5%	27%	3.3	14.5%	28.98	7.7	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	6.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.9	5.5
Netherlands	aFRR+	6	0.1%	53'001	1.2	9.5%	35%	4.2	14.5%	32.24	6.4	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	5.2	5.2
Netherlands	mFRRda+	1.28	0.0%	11'279	0.3	9.5%	35%	4.2	14.5%	32.24	6.4	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	5.1	5.1
France	aFRR+ (symmetric)	10.04		88'191	2.0	9.5%	22%	2.6	14.5%	36.75	4.5	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	2.3	2.2
France	mFRR+	2.37		20'818	0.5	9.5%	22%	2.6	14.5%	36.75	4.5	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	2.1	2.2
France	RR+	2.23		19'588	0.4	9.5%	22%	2.6	14.5%	36.75	4.5	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	2.3	32.0%	2.1	2.2
Norway	aFRR+	7.05	0.0%	61'931	1.4	9.5%	50%	6.0	14.5%	25.99	9.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	5.0	5.0
Norway	mFRR+	1.44	8.9%	19'184	0.4	9.5%	50%	6.0	14.5%	25.99	9.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	0.0	32.0%	4.9	4.9
Denmark	FCR+ (DK1, daily)	17.98		157'936	3.6	9.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	28	8.2	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.4	4.4
Denmark	FCR-D+ (DK2, yearly)	6.18		54'285	1.2	9.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	28	8.2	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.2	4.2
Denmark	aFRR+ (symmetric)	45		395'280	9.0	9.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	28	8.2	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.9	4.9
Denmark	mFRR+ (DK1)	0.62		5'446	0.1	9.5%	75%	9.0	14.5%	28	8.2	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	0.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	4.1	4.1
UK	RR+	0.9		7'906	0.2	9.5%	20%	2.4	14.5%	47.44	0.0	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	9.0	32.0%	6.4	6.7
Sweden	mFRR+ (SE1)			0	0.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	28.95	7.8	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	5.3	5.3
Sweden	mFRR+ (SE2)			0	0.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	28.95	7.8	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	5.3	5.3
Sweden	mFRR+ (SE3)			0	0.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	29.24	7.6	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	5.3	5.3
Sweden	mFRR+ (SE4)			0	0.0	9.5%		0.0	14.5%	29.53	7.5	9.0%	9.0	6.5%	9.0	28.5%	4.5	32.0%	5.3	5.4

10.9 Appendix - Remuneration flows compared between Germany and Switzerland

Intention and extent

The following text focuses on the differences in the remuneration of balancing energy in the grid service markets of Germany and Switzerland. It serves as an example of how tricky it may be to evaluate the commercial value of balancing energy from an RPU's point of view.

It remains to further explain the causes of the differences. It also remains to consider call probabilities as well as reserve prices in order to value grid services as a whole.

Earnings from balancing energy in Germany

Remuneration of *balancing energy* in Germany bases on [127]. It mainly involves the following parties:

- TSO,
- *Balancing group (BG) and supplier*,
- *Aggregator* (if any),
- *RPU providing control reserves*.

The TSO forwards the *balancing energy* price to the *aggregator* (see figures below). The *aggregator* remunerates both the *BG/Supplier* as well as the *RPU* for their effort and risks according to bilateral contracts.

Arrows show flows as differences to the schedule. Red: energy flow; Blue: money flow. Arrows define positive value flow.

Example:

- Price of BE+: $54\text{€}/\text{MWh}$

- x = remuneration paid to the BG/supplier for its effort and risks

Example money flow for positive balancing energy (BE+) in the German grid service markets. BG = balancing group, BE = balancing energy

Arrows show flows as differences to the schedule. Red: energy flow; Blue: money flow. Arrows define positive value flow.

Example:

- Price of BE-: $-20\text{€}/\text{MWh}$ (i.e. aggregator pays to the TSO)

- x = remuneration paid to the BG/supplier for its effort and risks

Example money flow for negative balancing energy (BE-) in the German grid service markets. BG = balancing group, BE = balancing energy

The economic value added (EVA) of balancing energy (compared to regular energy trades) is distributed between aggregator, BG/Supplier and technical unit. In total, it is equivalent to:

$$BE+: \quad EVA_{BE+} = p_{BE} - p_{trade} \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

$$BE-: \quad EVA_{BE-} = p_{BE} + p_{trade} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where p_{BE} is the price of balancing energy (in the example of the figure above: $54\text{€}/\text{MWh}$), and p_{trade} is the regular energy trading price.

Note: In the example of the figure above, consider that p_{BE} is negative, i.e. the TSO receives money from the aggregator, which partly is paid to the BG causing the unbalance.

Average balancing energy prices in Germany, 2016. The surplus is calculated with an average price at the German day ahead auction 2016 of $28.2 \text{€}/\text{MWh}$ [128],⁷⁴ which is taken as p_{trade}

	Average balancing energy price (€/MWh)	Average EVA (€/MWh)
aFRR+	54.8	26.6
aFRR-	17.2	45.4
mFRR+	106.2	78.0
mFRR-	78.8	107.0

The table estimates the value of balancing energy for the German market in 2016 based on yearly averages.

Earnings from balancing energy in Switzerland

Remuneration of *balancing energy* in Switzerland involves the following parties [124, pp. 35-36] (and [129]):

⁷⁴ Average German price at the day ahead auction is an approximation of the actual tariff the BG/supplier gets (pays) for energy deliveries (calls).

- TSO,
- *Balancing group (BG) and supplier,*
- *Aggregator (if any),*
- *Technical unit providing control reserves.*

The TSO splits the *balancing energy* price into a contribution remunerated via BG / *supplier* and via *aggregator* (see figures below). The sum of both payments equals the total balancing energy price. For remunerations (fees) to the BG / *supplier* the *SwissIX hourly day ahead tariffs* are used.

The BG/*supplier* remunerates (bills) the *technical unit's balancing energy* delivered (consumed) according to the supply contract set up between *supplier* and *technical unit*.

The *aggregator* remunerates the *technical unit* according to the contract set up between the two. (Note: some *aggregators* forward the full reward for *balancing energy* to the *technical unit*.)

Money flow as difference to schedule, arrows define positive value flow

Example:

- Energy market price (SwissIX, hourly day ahead): 37€/MWh
- Price of BE+: 54€/MWh

Example money flow for positive balancing energy (BE+) in the Swiss grid service markets. Based on [129]. BG = balancing group, BE = balancing energy

The figure below shows an example of the money flow in case of delivery of positive *balancing energy* (aFRR+ or mFRR+).

Money flow as difference to schedule, arrows define positive value flow

Example:

- Energy market price (SwissIX, hourly day ahead): 37€/MWh
- Price of BE-: -20€/MWh

Example money flow for negative balancing energy (BE-) in the Swiss grid service markets. Based on [129]. BG = balancing group, BE = balancing energy

The figure above shows an example of the money flow in case of delivery of negative *balancing energy* (aFRR- or mFRR-).

In spite of the fact that the cash flow is split, the total economic value added (EVA) of balancing energy (compared to regular energy trades), which is distributed by the TSO, can again be described by Eq. 8 and Eq. 9.

Note: as in the German case, it needs to be considered in the example of the figure above that p_{BE} is negative, i.e. in total, the TSO receives money from aggregator plus BG/Supplier, which partly is paid to the BG causing the unbalance.

Average balancing energy prices in Switzerland, 2016. The surplus is calculated with an average price at the Swiss hourly day ahead auction 2016 of 37.7 €/MWh.⁷⁵

	Average balancing energy price (€/MWh)	Average EVA (€/MWh)
aFRR+	50.8	22.8
aFRR-	28.9	56.9
mFRR+	73.1	45.1
mFRR-	-65.1	-37.1

The table above estimates the value of balancing energy for the Swiss market in 2016 based on yearly averages.

⁷⁵ *Average Swiss price at the hourly day ahead auction is an approximation of the actual tariff the BG/supplier gets (pays) for energy deliveries (calls).*

10.10 Appendix - Description of selected products
Finland, FCR-N (hourly)

Country	Finland
TSO	Fingrid Oyj
Address	Läkkisepäntie 21, Helsinki, Finland
Product	FCR
National / regional service name	FCR-N (Frequency containment reserve for normal operation)
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Hourly
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Symmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	30 min for storages, normally 1 hour
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	1 sec
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€34.7/MW/h
Average utilization price in 2016	€22/MWh down; €77/MWh up

Finland, FCR-N (yearly)

Country	Finland
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TSO	Fingrid Oyj
Address	Läkkisepäntie 21, Helsinki, Finland
Product	FCR
National / regional service name	FCR-N (Frequency containment reserve for normal operation)
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Yearly
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Symmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€17.42/MW/h
Average utilization price in 2016	22/MWh down; €77/MWh up

Finland, FCR-D (hourly)

Country	Finland
TSO	Fingrid Oyj
Address	Läkkisepäntie 21, Helsinki, Finland

Product	FCR
National / regional service name	FCR-D (Frequency containment reserve for disturbances)
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Hourly
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	30 min for storages, normally 1 hour
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	1 sec
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€30.3/MW/h up
Average utilization price in 2016	€/MWh

Finland, FCR-D (yearly)

Country	Finland
TSO	Fingrid Oyj
Address	Läkkisepäntie 21, Helsinki, Finland
Product	FCR
National / regional service name	FCR-D

	(Frequency containment reserve for disturbances)
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€4.5/MW/h up
Average utilization price in 2016	€0/MWh

Finland, aFRR

Country	Finland
TSO	Fingrid Oyj
Address	Läkkisepäntie 21, Helsinki, Finland
Product	aFRR
National / regional service name	
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y

Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Hourly
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	1 hour
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	10 sec
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€19.7/MW/h down; €23.4/MW/h up
Average utilization price in 2016	€22/MWh down; €77/MWh up

Finland, mFRR

Country	Finland
TSO	Fingrid Oyj
Address	Läkkisepäntie 21, Helsinki, Finland
Product	mFRR
National / regional service name	
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Hourly
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical

Requested maximum output duration of one activation	1 hour
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	1 min
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€3.6/MW/h up
Average utilization price in 2016	€22/MWh down; €77/MWh up

Germany, Sekundärregelreserve

Country	Germany
TSO	Amprion GmbH
Address	Von-Werth-Strasse 274, 50259 Pulheim, Germany
Product	aFRR
National / regional service name	Sekundärregelreserve
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Prequalified but hardly participate
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Weekly peak/off-peak product
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	4 hours
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	4 sec
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€4.25/MW/h up,

	€0.845/MW/h down
Average utilization price in 2016	€54.85/MWh up. €17.14/MWh down

Germany, mFRR

Country	Germany
TSO	Amprion GmbH
Address	Von-Werth-Strasse 274, 50259 Pulheim, Germany
Product	
National / regional service name	Minutenreserve
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	daily (4 hour) product
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	4 hours
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	15 min
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€0.98/MW/h up, €0.86/MW/h down
Average utilization price in 2016	€106.20/MWh up, €78.83/MWh down

Netherlands, aFRR

Country	Netherlands
TSO	TenneT TSO B.V.
Address	Utrechtsweg 310, Arnhem, P.O. box 718, 6800 AS Arnhem, The Netherlands
Product	aFRR
National / regional service name	
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Partly weekly auction, partly monthly auction
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Symmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	Total contract period
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	4 sec
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€12/MW/h
Average utilization price in 2016	€55/MWh up, €16.93/MWh down

Netherlands, FCR

Country	Netherlands
TSO	TenneT TSO B.V.

Address	Utrechtsweg 310, Arnhem, P.O. box 718, 6800 AS Arnhem, The Netherlands
Product	FCR
National / regional service name	
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	weekly auction and bids
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Symmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	constant frequency following: contract period
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	constant frequency following: contract period
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€14.91/MW/h
Average utilization price in 2016	non; availability price includes the “delivery” costs

Netherlands, mFRR

Country	Netherlands
TSO	TenneT TSO B.V.
Address	Utrechtsweg 310, Arnhem, P.O. box 718, 6800 AS Arnhem, The Netherlands
Product	mFRR

National / regional service name	mFRRda manual Frequency Restoration Reserve directly activated
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	PTU blocks
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	Bid period
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	15 min
Average availability price for the service in 2016	1.28 €/MWh up, Down: not traded
Average utilization price in 2016	€147/MWh up €-74/MWh down

Switzerland, aFRR

Country	Switzerland
TSO	Swissgrid
Address	Werkstrasse 12, Laufenburg, Switzerland
Product	aFRR
National / regional service name	SRL (Sekundärregelung)
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y (the unit must be synchronized)

Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Weekly auctions, pay as bid
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Symmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	168 hours (these limits refer to the entire pool. The operators can regulate the technical units as they desire)
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	168 hours (these limits refer to the entire pool. The operators can regulate the technical units as they desire)
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€37.65/MW/h
Average utilization price in 2016	€50.82/MWh (up) €28.91/MWh (down) (exchange rate: 1:0.862)

Switzerland, FCR

Country	Switzerland
TSO	Swissgrid
Address	Werkstrasse 12, Laufenburg, Switzerland
Product	FCR
National / regional service name	PRL (Primärregelung)
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y (the unit must be synchronized)
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y

Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	Weekly auctions, pay as bid
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Symmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	168 hours (these limits refer to the entire pool. The operators can regulate the technical units as they desire)
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	continuously for unlimited energy storage units. For limited check the new network code.
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€14.63/MW/h
Average utilization price in 2016	-

United Kingdom, FCR

Country	United Kingdom
TSO	System Operator for Northern Ireland Ltd
Address	
Product	FCR
National / regional service name	FRR (Firm frequency response) Sub products are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic Primary Response • Dynamic Secondary Response • Dynamic High Response • Static Primary Response • Static Secondary Response

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Static High Response (not procured in 2016)
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	24 hours a day
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	FCR Primary Response: symmetrical FCR Secondary Response: symmetrical FCR High Response: asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	NA
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	NA
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€4.03/MW/h
Average utilization price in 2016	NA

Austria, mFRR

Country	Austria
TSO	Austrian Power Grid AG
Address	Wagramer Straße 19, IZD Tower, 1220 Wien, Austria
Product	mFRR
National / regional service name	Tertiärregelreserve TRR
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y

Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	weekly
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	Product length
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	15 min
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€1.6/MW/h (Peak Up) €1.46/MW/h (Off-Peak Up) €0.77/MW/h (Sa+So Peak Up) €0.33/MW/h (Sa+So Off-Peak Up) €0.46/MW/h (Peak Down) €1.94/MW/h (Off-Peak Down) €1.57/MW/h (Sa+So Peak Down) €3.09/MW/h (Sa+So Off-Peak Down)
Average utilization price in 2016	€188.94/MWh (Peak Up) €163.08/MWh (Off-Peak Up) €163.01/MWh (Sa+So Peak Up) €160.23/MWh (Sa+So Off-Peak Up) €-188.45/MWh (Peak Down) €-271.6/MWh (Off-Peak Down) €-200.81 (Sa+So Peak Down) €-277.04 (Sa+So Off-Peak Down)

Austria, aFRR

Country	Austria
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TSO	Austrian Power Grid AG
Address	Wagramer Straße 19, IZD Tower, 1220 Wien, Austria
Product	aFRR
National / regional service name	Sekundärregelreserve SRR
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	weekly
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	Product length
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	No minimum
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€0.72/MW/h (Peak Up) €1.75/MW/h (Off-Peak Up) €0.84/MW/h (Weekend Up) €0.72/MW/h (Peak Down) €3.49/MW/h (Off-Peak Down) €2.1/MW/h (Weekend Down)
Average utilization price in 2016	€93.24/MWh (Peak Up) €113.14/MWh (Off-Peak Up) €98.07/MWh (Weekend Up) €-23.23/MWh (Peak Down) €-56.88/MWh (Off-Peak Down) €-73.5/MWh (Weekend Down)

Denmark (DK1), FCR

Country	Denmark
TSO	Energinet
Address	Tonne Kjærsvvej 65, DK- 7000 Fredericia
Product	FCR
National / regional service name	FCR (DK1)
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	hourly
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	15 min
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€17.98/MW/h up, €1.56/MW/h down (both long term contracts)
Average utilization price in 2016	NA

Norway, mFRR

Country	Norway
TSO	Statnett SF

Address	Nydalen Allé 33, N-0484 Oslo PB 4904 Nydalen, 0423 Oslo
Product	mFRR
National / regional service name	Capacity: RKOM Utilisation: RK (Nordpool terminology: Regulating power)
Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	RKOM: weekly RK: hourly
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	1 hour
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	15 min
Average availability price for the service in 2016	€1.44/MW/h up
Average utilization price in 2016	€34.39/MWh up €17.72/MWh down

Slovenia, mFRR

Country	Slovenia
TSO	ELES
Address	Hajdrihova ulica 2, 1000 Ljubljana
Product	mFRR
National / regional service name	

Non-rotating mass accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Load accepted for provision of the service (Y/N)	Y
Geographically distributed loads or generators are aggregated and able to contribute to the service (Y/N)	Y
Service description (e.g. products with weekly, daily or hourly blocks)	yearly
Symmetrical / asymmetrical service provision	Asymmetrical
Requested maximum output duration of one activation	
Requested minimum output duration of one activation	
Average availability price for the service in 2016	pos: €5.71/MW/h neg: €4.84/MW/h
Average utilization price in 2016	pos: €173.8/MWh neg: €-180/MWh

10.11 Appendix – Windgas Haßfurt

Control and monitoring architecture of the PtG unit Windgas Haßfurt

Bürgerwindpark Sailerhäuser Wald parameters

Wind farm location	Haßfurt, Bavaria Germany	
Year commissioned	November 2015	[130]
Wind farm capacity	24 MW (10 x 2.4MW)	[131]
Manufacturer	Nordex SE	[131]
Capital Investment	11.6 million euros	[130]
Owner	Bürgerwindpark Sailerhäuser Wald GmbH & Co. KG	[131]
2016 / 2017 power generation	54 / 61 GWh	[131]
Average regular wind energy compensation, 2016	105.58 €/MWh	[132]
Curtailment compensation	95% of the regular wind energy compensation	[132]

PtG facility Windgas Haßfurt parameters

PEM water electrolyser	Siemens SILYZER 200 PEM electrolyzer	[131] [132, p. 20]
Rated stack capacity	1.25 MW	[130, p. 31] [132, p. 20]
Date commissioned	20.10.2016	[133]
Efficiency	65%	[134] [132, p. 20]

Output pressure	Up to 35 bars	[132, p. 20]
Hydrogen production rate	225 Nm ³ /h (20.22 kg/h)	[130, p. 31] [132, p. 20]
Hydrogen purity (depending on operating point)	99.5% - 99.9%	[132, p. 20]
Life cycle design	>80'000h	[132, p. 20]
Fresh water demand	1.5l / Nm ³ H ₂ (16.689 l/ kg H ₂)	[132, p. 20]
Owners	Windgas Haßfurt GmbH & Co. KG (Haßfurt municipal utility and Greenpeace Energy)	
CAPEX, approx.	2 million euros	[134]
Annual maintenance cost, approx.	4% of CAPEX	[134, p. 5]
Annual hydrogen production, expected	1 GWh	[135]
Electricity purchase wholesale price	€30.00 €/MWh	[130, p. 31]
Approx. EEG surcharge, 2016	68 €/MWh	[131]
Water costs, approx.	2'000 €/a	[134]
Hydrogen price	59 €/MWh HHV	[131]
Expected lifetime	20 years	

*Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz - EEG (Renewable Energy Sources Act surcharge)